

**Exploring the factors essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment
of Business strategy and IT strategy: A case of a UK Forex SME.**

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Declaration

I, W.K.B Mesaj Fernando, hereby declare that this work has not been previously accepted in substance for any degree programme and is not being concurrently submitted for any other qualification. I also declare that this research is a result of my own independent work and research, except where otherwise stated (a bibliography is attached).

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Abstract

As modern technologies are becoming more and more sophisticated, the modern business environment is becoming increasingly competitive. Businesses nowadays have access to an extensive scale of data, and they can make more informed decisions than ever before. This has made the modern business environment excruciatingly competitive and businesses that operate in the traditional way can no longer survive, particularly in industries such as Foreign Exchange (Forex). This is because the companies in the Forex industry utilise cutting edge technologies in their business processes and achieving cross-department strategic alignment is critical to the success of a Forex firm. A wide number of existing studies investigated the factors of strategic alignment in the context of big companies, however, an extensive review of the literature indicated that no empirical research previously investigated Forex SMEs to explore the factors of strategic alignment as well as the challenges SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment. This research, therefore, seeks to fill the existing knowledge gap by exploring the critical success factors that are essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy by investigating a UK-based Forex SME as a case.

This research adopted the interpretivist research philosophy and utilised a qualitative research design by interviewing 16 participants that are currently working in various departments of the case organisation. In order to analyse the research data, thematic analysis was conducted whilst utilising NVivo 12 pro.

This research revealed that factors such as *Communication maturity, Competency maturity, IT governance maturity, Scope and architecture of the IT maturity, Partnership maturity, Skills maturity, and Web systems maturity* play critical roles in terms of achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. Besides, this research also revealed numerous challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment. They include *lack of senior management commitment, lack of coordination between departments, resistance to change culture, and slow decision-making*. The findings of this research make significant contributions to the literature by reconceptualising the existing Luftman's strategic alignment maturity model in the context of Forex SMEs. The findings also make contributions to the literature by adding new insights and filling the existing knowledge gap.

Keywords: *Strategic Alignment, SMEs, Business Strategy, IT Strategy, Forex Firm, Organisational Performance, Profitability*

Table of Contents

DECLARATION	II
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	III
ABSTRACT	IV
TABLE OF CONTENTS	V
TABLES AND FIGURES	VIII
ABBREVIATIONS	IX
1. CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. RESEARCH BACKGROUND.....	1
1.1.1. <i>Foreign Exchange Industry</i>	2
1.1.2. <i>The UK Foreign Exchange Market</i>	4
1.1.3. <i>Company Background</i>	6
1.2. RESEARCH PROBLEM.....	10
1.3. RESEARCH AIM, OBJECTIVES, AND QUESTIONS.....	12
1.3.1. <i>Research Objectives</i>	12
1.3.2. <i>Research Questions</i>	12
1.4. RATIONALE	13
1.5. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	14
1.6. STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS	15
1.7. SCOPE AND THE LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH.....	16
1.8. CHAPTER SUMMARY	17
2. CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW	18
2.1. INTRODUCTION	18
2.2. SMEs AND THEIR IMPORTANCE.....	19
2.2.1. <i>Defining SMEs</i>	19
2.2.2. <i>Importance of SMEs</i>	21
2.2.3. <i>Characteristics of SMEs</i>	23
2.2.4. <i>SMEs Contributions to the UK Economy</i>	24
2.2.5. <i>SMEs Business Success Factors</i>	25
2.3. ORGANISATIONAL STRATEGIES	27
2.3.1. <i>Business Strategy</i>	27
2.3.2. <i>IT Strategy</i>	31
2.4. STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT	36
2.4.1. <i>Theoretical Background of Strategic Alignment</i>	36
2.4.2. <i>Strategic Alignment in SMEs</i>	38
2.4.3. <i>Advantages of Strategic Alignment</i>	40
2.4.4. <i>Models for Strategic Alignment</i>	42
2.4.5. <i>Factors Determining Successful Strategic Alignment</i>	56

2.4.6.	<i>Challenges for Ensuring Successful Strategic Alignment</i>	64
2.4.7.	<i>Strategic Alignment and Organisational Performance</i>	69
2.5.	KNOWLEDGE GAPS	70
2.6.	RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	72
2.7.	CONCLUSIONS	74
3.	CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	75
3.1.	INTRODUCTION	75
3.2.	RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY & PHILOSOPHICAL ASSUMPTIONS.....	75
3.2.1.	<i>Ontology</i>	76
3.2.2.	<i>Epistemology</i>	77
3.3.	RESEARCH APPROACH	80
3.4.	RESEARCH STRATEGY	81
3.4.1.	<i>Case Study</i>	81
3.5.	RESEARCH DESIGN: QUALITATIVE	85
3.6.	SAMPLING	86
3.6.1.	<i>Sample Size and Justifications</i>	87
3.7.	DATA COLLECTION.....	88
3.7.1.	<i>Interviews</i>	88
3.7.2.	<i>Semi-Structured Interviews</i>	89
3.8.	DATA ANALYSIS	92
3.8.1.	<i>Qualitative Data Analysis</i>	92
3.9.	RESEARCH RELIABILITY, VALIDITY, AND QUALITY	95
3.9.1.	<i>Reliability and Validity</i>	95
3.9.2.	<i>Research Quality</i>	96
3.10.	ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS	97
3.11.	CHAPTER SUMMARY	98
4.	CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH FINDINGS	100
4.1.	INTRODUCTION	100
4.1.1.	<i>Profile of the Respondents</i>	100
4.2.	THE FACTORS OF STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT	103
4.2.1.	<i>Communication Maturity</i>	104
4.2.2.	<i>Competency Maturity</i>	105
4.2.3.	<i>IT governance maturity</i>	107
4.2.4.	<i>Scope and architecture of the IT maturity</i>	109
4.2.5.	<i>Partnership maturity</i>	111
4.2.6.	<i>Skills maturity</i>	113
4.2.7.	<i>Web (Internet) systems maturity</i>	114
4.3.	CHALLENGES FACED BY COMPANY A FOR ACHIEVING STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT.....	116
4.3.1.	<i>Lack of senior leadership's support and commitment</i>	117
4.3.2.	<i>Lack of coordination between IT department and business managers</i>	118
4.3.3.	<i>Resistance to change culture</i>	119
4.3.4.	<i>Slow decision making due to stringent company policies</i>	121
4.3.5.	<i>Knowledge and Skills Deficit</i>	122
4.3.6.	<i>Lack of Sufficient Financial Resources</i>	124

4.4.	ACHIEVING HARMONIOUS STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT OF BUSINESS AND IT STRATEGY OF A FOREX SME	125
4.4.1.	<i>Effective cross-department communication and coordination</i>	125
4.4.2.	<i>Management knowledge and commitment</i>	126
4.4.3.	<i>Appropriate distribution of organisational resources</i>	128
4.4.4.	<i>Regular training and development of front-line staffs</i>	129
4.5.	OUTCOMES OF STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT	131
4.6.	CONCLUSIONS	132
5.	CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSIONS.....	133
5.1.	INTRODUCTION	133
5.2.	EXPLORING THE FACTORS OF STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT IN A FOREX SME	133
5.3.	CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH ACHIEVING STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT IN FOREX SMEs.....	141
5.4.	ACHIEVING HARMONIOUS STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT OF BUSINESS STRATEGY AND IT STRATEGY IN FOREX SMEs.....	147
5.5.	EVALUATIONS OF THE FINDINGS	150
5.6.	CHAPTER SUMMARY	151
1.	CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	152
6.1.	INTRODUCTION	152
6.2.	SUMMARY OF THIS RESEARCH	152
6.3.	ACHIEVING RESEARCH AIM AND OBJECTIVES	154
6.3.1.	<i>Objective One</i>	154
6.3.2.	<i>Objective Two</i>	155
6.3.3.	<i>Objective Three</i>	156
6.3.4.	<i>Objective Four</i>	156
6.3.5.	<i>Objective Five</i>	157
6.4.	CONTRIBUTIONS OF THE RESEARCH	157
6.4.1.	<i>Theoretical Contributions</i>	157
6.4.2.	<i>Practical Contributions</i>	160
6.5.	RECOMMENDATIONS	161
6.5.1.	<i>Recommendations to Forex SMEs</i>	162
6.5.2.	<i>Recommendations to the Case Company for Strategic Alignment</i>	163
6.6.	POSSIBLE LIMITATIONS OF THE FINDINGS	164
6.7.	FURTHER RESEARCH.....	165
7.	REFERENCES.....	167
8.	APPENDICES.....	213

Tables and Figures

Tables

Table 2-1: SMEs in the UK by 2020	25
Table 2-2: Definitions of Strategic Alignment	36
Table 2-3: Enablers and Inhibitors of Strategic Alignment.....	46
Table 2-4: A summary of strategic alignment models.....	52
Table 2-5: Factors determining successful strategic alignment.....	57
Table 3-1: Comparisons of objectivism and subjectivism.....	76
Table 3-2: Advantages and disadvantages of the case study research strategy	82
Table 4-1: Profile of Participants.....	100
Table 4-2: Roles and Responsibilities of the interview participants	101

Figures

Figure 1-1: The United Kingdom and other Forex trading countries (Forex turnover).	5
Figure 1-2: The UK and other Forex trading countries (market share percentage).....	5
Figure 1-3: Organizational structure of Company A (case company).....	8
Figure 2-1: Definition of business categorisation according to European Union (EU).	20
Figure 2-2: SMEs in the United Kingdom from the year 2000.	21
Figure 2-3: SMEs (formal and informal) global finance gaps.....	22
Figure 2-4: Strategic Alignment Model (SAM).	42
Figure 2-5: Luftman's Strategic Alignment Maturity Model	51
Figure 2-6: Framework for strategic alignment of SMEs.....	73
Figure 3-1: Word cloud produced from NVivo	95
Figure 5-1: Strategic Alignment Maturity Model for Forex SMEs.....	140
Figure 5-2: Challenges associated with achieving strategic alignment.	141
Figure 6-1: Conceptual Model for Strategic Alignment of Forex SMEs.	158

Abbreviations

Forex	Foreign Exchange
FinTech	Financial Technology
FxPOS	Foreign Exchange Point of Sale
FedS	Case Firm Previous Main Trading System
SAMM	Strategic Alignment Maturity Model
SAM	Strategic Alignment Model
SMEs	Small Medium-Sized Enterprises
OTC	Over The Counter
UK	United Kingdom
GBP	Great British Pounds
JPY	Japanese Yen
USD	United States Dollar
EUR	Euros
BoE	Bank of England
MS-DOS	Microsoft Disk Operating System
NASDAQ	New York City Stock Exchange
COVID-19	Coronavirus Pandemic

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1. Research Background

For many decades, the actual value of Information Technology (IT) on business has piqued academics' curiosity (Homburg et al., 2019; McCardle et al., 2019; Slim et al., 2021). Therefore, many businesses and IT leaders are putting their best efforts to succeed in strategic planning, but eventually, many will end up failing due to a lack of knowledge in strategic planning (Ilmudeen et al., 2019). It is evident in the literature that strategic alignment has a significant impact on an institution's success, especially in the business domain (Liang et al., 2017; El-Masri et al., 2015). In the corporate sector, strategic planning relates to the procedure by which institutions define their unique strategy or path and make choices about how to distribute and use their unique resources to accomplish their organisational strategies (Sharma and Behl, 2020). As such, strategic planning for information systems could be described as the procedure of developing an institution's information systems/IT strategy (Sharma and Behl, 2020; Sabherwal et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2008).

Numerous studies examined the impact of technology on organizational performance investigating how IT may improve a businesses' effectiveness in influencing organizational performance (Odiit et al., 2014; Kotusev, 2020; Henriques et al., 2019; Majstorovic, 2016). A vast majority of academic research identified strategic alignment as a critical missing connection between technology and organizational performance (MacDonald and Yapp, 1992; Henderson and Venkatraman, 1999; Preston, 2014; Coltman et al., 2015; Bi et al., 2017; Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Njanka et al., 2021). Many previous literatures in strategic IT management have concentrated on either the alignment of business and IT plans/strategies, which is known as strategic alignment, or the integration of business and IT structures termed structural alignment (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; El-Masri et al., 2015). This research seeks to explore the strategic alignment aspect of organisations by investigating the factors that are necessary for achieving the alignment of IT strategies and business strategies.

Strategic alignment requires the establishment of processes, structures, dynamic capacities, partnerships, and the alignment of business strategies and IT strategies (Gerow et al., 2015; Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019; Slim et al., 2021). Henderson and Venkatraman (1993) proposed a 'strategic alignment model' to conceptualise strategic alignment. This model explicitly shows the components needed for strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy, but the framework does not say how organizations can achieve strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy. Luftman (2003) introduced the Strategic Alignment Maturity Model (SAMM), which is one of the commonly used models by researchers in the areas of Strategic alignment. This model consists of six dimensions namely, communication maturity, competency maturity, IT governance maturity, scope and architectures of the IT maturity, partnership maturity and skills maturity.

Many existing studies investigated strategic alignments of large organizations (Jia et al., 2018; Majstorovic, 2016; Gutierrez et al., 2006), but limited work has been done in the area of SMEs (Slim et al., 2021), and no work in the specific context of foreign exchange (Forex) SMEs. This research explicitly focuses on strategic business-IT alignment in the SME business context, and research outcomes may provide recommendations to UK forex SMEs. Indeed, SMEs make substantial contributions to the world economy, similarly to large organizations. But limited research is conducted in the area of strategic alignment of SMEs. Most of the academic literature highlighted the success and failure factors of strategic alignment (Alghazi et al., 2017; Reksoatmodjo et al., 2012; Luftman and Brier, 1999; Wang and Rusu, 2018). Afandi (2020) have pointed out that strategic alignment success and failure factors differ depending on the industry an SME operates in. This research, therefore, seeks to investigate the UK Forex SMEs to explore what are the factors that determine the success or failure of Forex SMEs. The next section now provides a description of the Forex industry in general and the UK Forex industry.

1.1.1. Foreign Exchange Industry

The Foreign Exchange market (also known as '*Forex*', '*Fx*', '*currency trading*', or '*currency market*') can be defined as a unique live market that never sleeps but determines the exchange rates for currencies every day (Barker, 2007; Melvin, 2017). Forex exchange rates are the indicators that connect every currency in the world economy, delivering the exact value of one single currency into another currency (Faure, 2013). The foreign exchange market, often known

as the over-the-counter market ('*OTC*'), is a decentralized global market where trading currencies happen (Barker, 2007). In Forex business, an exchange rate confirms under what single price two currencies should exchange more precisely. According to Barker (2007), Foreign Exchange (Forex) is a term that refers to the commodity that is traded in currency notes. Thus, the Foreign Exchange trading market can be understood as a marketplace for purchasing and selling foreign currencies.

According to Melvin and Norrbín (2017; p. 43), the term "foreign exchange market" refers to the global organizations that are only there to exchange currencies of different countries. Forex business is divided into two subsections, namely, retail and wholesale. The retail tier focuses on where smaller foreign exchange dealers buy and sell currency while the wholesale section comprises banks and currency brokers, where they operate business operations with one another and with large organisations (Baruník et al., 2017). Foreign exchange operations are divided into major three time zones. Each day, Forex market trading starts in Sydney and proceeds around the globe when each financial centre's business day begins, respectively, Tokyo, London, and New York at last (Barker, 2007). There is no central location for foreign exchange operations where Forex traders can convene to conduct operations; however, Forex markets are the world's major financial marketplaces (Frankel and Rose, 1996).

The leading markets in the Forex industry is "*London (daily trade is above 40% of the entire world's trade), New York (17%), Singapore (7%), Hong Kong (8%), and Tokyo (6%)*" (TheCityUK, 2018; BoE, 2019; p. 12). There are other markets too (e.g., Zurich, Frankfurt, Paris, and Amsterdam), but their daily trade amount is much lower than the leading markets (TheCityUK, 2018). The USD is the most frequently exchanged currency worldwide (Barker, 2007; Baruník et al., 2017), accounting for 88% of trades/operations (BoE, 2019a). By the end of 2019, USD and EUR was the most used pair currency exchange in 2019, accounting for 23% of worldwide turnover, followed by USD and JPY transactions of 18% and USD and GBP at 9% of transactions (BoE, 2019a; BIS, 2019).

Foreign exchange trading occurs 24 hours a day, seven days a week, on all global markets. This procedure is continuous, regardless of weekends or holidays, as long as participants are active in trading operations. According to Barker (2007), Melvin and Norrbín (2017), Faure (2013), BoE (2019a), BoE (2020), government/central banks, Forex dealers, corporations, investment banks,

commercial banks, hedge funds, retail brokers, and holidaymakers are the primary participants in the foreign exchange market. One of the most significant distinctions between the Forex markets and other financial markets is the general activity of firms to facilitate day-to-day business operations and mitigate longer-term risks (BoE, 2021). In the Forex business, currency prices are offered OTC by Forex brokers/dealers, and transactions between buyers and sellers are negotiated immediately (Barker, 2007). However, Glantz and Kissell (2014) assert that the Forex market is similar to the '*NASDAQ*' market structure; it is a worldwide network of marketplaces connected by sophisticated computer systems. All countries, including London, New York, Paris, Zurich, Frankfurt, Singapore, Hong Kong, and Tokyo, are well-connected to the Forex markets (Barker, 2007; BIS, 2019). However, London continues to be the world's largest Forex market (TheCityUK, 2018; BoE, 2019a). The Bank of International Settlements (BIS), which conducts surveys every three years, reported that the Forex market's daily turnover was approximately \$5.1 trillion in 2016; whereas by 2019 trading in Forex markets were at over \$6 trillion (BIS, 2019). This makes the Forex market the world's largest financial market (TheCityUK, 2018; BIS, 2019).

1.1.2. The UK Foreign Exchange Market

The value of the British pound changes every day, and speculation is the primary driver of today's Forex market (TheCityUK, 2018). Although predicting and assessing the extent of speculative activity in Forex trading is challenging, less than 5% of daily Forex operations in London arise from direct buying or selling to meet export and import requirements (TheCityUK, 2018). According to the Bank of England's survey results (16th of September 2019), the average daily turnover in the UK Forex market during the first quarter of 2019 exceeded US\$ 3,500 billion (reach US\$ 3.6 trillion), a significant increase from the US\$ 2,400 billion (reach US\$ 2.5 trillion) in April 2016 (BoE, 2019b). The foreign exchange market in the UK continues to grow although, exit from the European Union still operating as the most difficult challenge for the UK Forex industry (TheCityUK, 2018; BoE, 2021). Figure 1-1 shows how the United Kingdom is leading the global Forex trading markets.

Figure 1-1: The United Kingdom and other Forex trading countries (Forex turnover).

Source: (Bank of England, 2019b).

Furthermore, the UK has the largest foreign exchange market compared to other countries, accounting for more than 40% of the global turnover value, rising from 35% in late April 2016 (TheCityUK, 2018; BoE, 2019b). Figure 1-2 shows the comparison between market share percentage in the UK and other countries.

Figure 1-2: The UK and other Forex trading countries (market share percentage)

Source: (BoE, 2019b).

The United States dollar remains the most actively traded currency on the UK market (Lowes and Nenova, 2013; BoE, 2019b). 90% of all foreign exchange trades executed in the United

Kingdom involved the USD. Globally, the United Kingdom holds a 44% share of the US dollar market (BoE, 2019b). The USD/Euro pair is by far the most actively traded currency pairing globally (Kumar, 2014), accounting for little less than a quarter of all foreign exchange transactions. Foreign exchange swaps account for over 40% of worldwide Forex turnover (BoE, 2019) and exchanging in spot rates accounts for another 30% of total activity (Lowes and Nenova, 2013). Forex swaps are agreements between two parties to exchange currencies for a specified time (Lowes and Nenova, 2013). Forex swaps are also the most actively traded product in the United Kingdom, contributing over 45% of total Forex turnover in the first quarter of 2019 (BoE, 2019b). In the UK Forex market, businesses frequently use online business platforms to sell and promote their products and services in order to meet their business objectives and earn profits (Lowes and Nenova, 2013; BoE, 2019; GOV, 2017). The UK Forex market continues to dominate the global industry, with approximately £9 billion in foreign currency moved annually (BoE, 2019a; BoE, 2019b; BIS, 2019). As previously mentioned, this research seeks to explore the factors of strategic alignment in the context of Forex SMEs. In order to examine how SMEs operate in the UK Forex industry, a UK-based Forex SME will be reviewed as a case in this research. The next section presents a background of the case company.

1.1.3. Company Background

The organization selected for this research is a reputed Foreign Exchange (Forex) bureau in London. The organization will be referred to as "Company A" in this research due to confidentiality purposes. Company A is one of the leading and highly recognized Forex bureaus in London. Its former chairman founded Company A over two decades ago, and, being the founder and the CEO, he controlled all departments of Company A, virtually alone wielding his power. For almost 20 years, Company A has processed Forex transactions for nearly 35 currencies, provided corporate Forex trading rates, sell and buy Forex services, issued traveller's cheques, international bank transfers, Fast Cash transactions to Sri Lanka, and Western Union global services. Company A offers online Forex services such as "*click and collect*", "*click and sell*" and, also, the bureau offers a "*home delivery service*", which was in higher demand through the COVID-19 lockdown period as many customers ordered their travel money to their home doors due to government social distancing rules.

Company A operates in the Foreign Exchange industry, where the market is generally volatile and fluctuates every second of the day. The Forex industry also combines with the Fintech industry since financial services cannot operate without the help of technologies. The bureau currently has 30 branches across London and outside London, employing over 100 staff. According to UK Company House records, Company A generated revenue between £5 million to £10 million each year. The company employ's below 250 individuals and turnover below €40 million annually, according to the UK House of Commons Library and European Commission regulations, Company A is an SME (European Commission, 2008; Rhodes, 2019; Rhodes and Ward, 2020). Before the COVID-19 pandemic in the UK, the bureau had 45 branches inside and outside London. However, unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 pandemic severely disturbing the travel industry globally, the bureau's senior management decided to close 15 branches permanently and proceed with the employee redundancy procedure. Senior area team management is led by the senior area manager and area support managers and they are Company A's senior management, and they report back to the parent firm monthly. Figure 1.3 presents the current company structure of Company A.

Figure 1-3: Organizational structure of Company A (case company).

Source: The Author

Company A aims to be flexible in business and IT procedures to serve dynamic customer expectations, therefore the bureau did not maintain formal procedures such as strategic alignment. There was no proper IT strategy implemented in the bureau for nearly 20 years as the bureau operated as a standalone SME in the streets of London, and IT investment plans were approved by the founder after careful considerations. The bureau's business strategy and IT plans were independent of each other. The former chairman formulated the business strategy according to his needs and ways, whereas IT plans were designed temporarily by the IT manager to support business strategy. IT department and business development were not formally aligned in Company A's formative years, though it made substantial profits.

Company A's topmost priority is winning customer loyalty and support. Company A's main organisational objectives are, improving Forex sales figures monthly, always providing good customer services, retaining existing customers and increasing customer base, and achieving higher annual financial success. Company A's mission statement is listed below:

“We recognise that you are the most important person to us. We understand that without winning your loyalty and custom we cannot continue our business. We will always strive to offer you an excellent foreign exchange service based on trust, reliability, and unbeatable exchange rates. We will always treat you politely just the way we like to like to be treated. If we have impressed you with our service, please recommend us to your friends and colleagues. If we have not lived up to your expectations, please let us know and we will endeavour to put it right”¹.

Over the past two decades, the vision of Company A remains the same. Their vision is to be the leader in the foreign exchange market in the UK. Company A has undergone a vast organisational transformation in the past years. All Company A's systems were manual (lots of manual paperwork and questions raised regarding the data protection rules), and there was no integration back then. Previously, Company A's 'Fed\$' was a standalone Forex system, and it was thoroughly installed to each computer till in the bureau and did not need thorough integration. Company A's IT department did not have many IT personnel in previous years, but the IT

¹Company A's complete mission statement. This mission statement is largely engraved in a glass, in one of the branches in central London. The above said mission statement has not changed since the establishment of the bureau.

manager controlled all the major IT-related decisions and implementations. Company A grew more substantially because of the higher demand for their foreign bureau exchange rates, and the bureau was able to beat any Forex rate if the customers challenge it.

The Fed\$ were the main Foreign Exchange Point of Sale (FxPOS) terminal in Company A, and it was there till Company B acquired the bureau's whole network. The year 2018 was exceptional to Company A. The reason behind this was that a leading Irish financial group acquired Company A. The parent organization will be called 'Company B' in this research due to confidentiality purposes. From 2018 onwards, the year of acquisition by Company B group, the organization's culture of Company A commenced changing remarkably in IT plans and policies, HR practices, accounts departments and payroll systems in accordance with the Company B procedures. However, when Company A started to adapt to these new IT and business changes, employees/staff began to feel some 'teething' problems, gaps in the parent firm's IT strategies, and their understanding of strategic alignment. Focus on these problems will be made in detail in the next section.

1.2. Research Problem

Achieving strategic alignment is critical to the success of a firm in the modern marketplace. A review of the existing literature revealed that numerous studies were conducted for identifying the factors that are essential for achieving strategic alignment. For example, Miropoulos (2021), Luftman et al. (2017), Ilmudeen et al. (2019), Coltman et al. (2015), and Gerow et al. (2015) investigated big firms and identified that for an alignment between strategic business plans and IT strategies, senior managers support for IT, IT department fully understanding business goals, senior management knowledge about business, and top management's confidence in the IT department is essential. Additionally, Wang and Rusu (2018), Chan et al. (2019), Afandi (2017), and Cataldo and McQueen (2015) investigated SMEs in various contexts such as IT solutions, retail, food manufacturing, restaurant and agriculture industries and revealed that enhanced communication practices with employees, IT planners being aware of the overall organisational goals, business and IT managers interacting closely in strategic decisions, and rapid decision-making are vital for achieving strategic alignment. However, upon extensively reviewing the

literature, it was noted that no prior study was conducted in the context of Forex SMEs, leaving a knowledge void in the literature. This research, therefore, seeks to address this research problem by investigating a UK based Forex SME.

A review of the existing literature also highlighted numerous challenges organisations face whilst achieving strategic alignment. The challenges faced whilst achieving strategic alignment is fairly well known in the literature. For example, Rahimi et al. (2015) identified that sophisticated organisation structure is the biggest challenge for large firms when achieving strategic alignment. Also, Tallon et al. (2016) noted that IT personnel's lack of business knowledge negatively impacts strategic alignment. Additionally, Jia et al. (2018) highlighted that a lack of sufficient human and financial resources also impact strategic alignment. Moreover, some challenges faced by SMEs were also noted in the literature; they include lack of resources, lack of shared domain knowledge between business and IT managers, and the lack of trust between business managers and IT managers (Pascal et al., 2016; Bishop, 2017; Al-Surmi et al., 2019). However, the challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment is not previously reported in the literature. This study, therefore, seeks to identify the challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment to add new insights to the literature.

As aforementioned, Company A (*the case company*) is a UK-based Forex SME currently serving as one of the leading bureaus in central London. Company A has recently undergone restructuring as it was acquired by another firm. Following the acquisition, Company A's previous strategies, infrastructure capabilities and systems were replaced by the senior management since they had higher vulnerabilities against cyber threats. The branch managers and area support managers understood that ever since senior management implemented new IT strategies to Company A, the bureau has faced major problems such as reduced branch performance and increased customer complaints. On the surface, it appears that the problems Company A is facing are due to the lack of coordination between different departments leading to the lack of strategic alignment. Therefore, this research also seeks to investigate the challenges company A is facing and make recommendations for achieving strategic alignment and increasing business performance whilst filling the knowledge gaps mentioned above.

1.3. Research Aim, Objectives, and Questions

This research aims to make recommendations to the practitioners in the UK Forex SME sector for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business strategies and IT strategies upon exploring the factors essential for achieving strategic alignment and the challenges SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment.

1.3.1. Research Objectives

Five research objectives are formulated in order to accomplish the above aim:

- Objective One: To construct a conceptual framework upon critically reviewing academic literature related to the factors of strategic alignment and challenges organisations face in terms of achieving strategic alignment.
- Objective Two: To explore and evaluate the factors necessary for achieving strategic alignment by qualitatively examining a UK based Forex SME.
- Objective Three: To understand the challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment upon exploring a case of a UK based Forex SME.
- Objective Four: To reveal the critical success factors for achieving a harmonious strategic alignment of IT strategies and Business strategies in the context of a UK-based Forex SME.
- Objective Five: To provide strategic recommendations to UK Forex SMEs for achieving and maintaining strategic alignment of IT strategies and Business strategies for enhanced organisational performance.

1.3.2. Research Questions

The following research questions are developed to achieve the above objectives:

RQ1: What frameworks are available in the literature for assessing a firm's strategic alignment?

RQ 2: What are the factors that determine successful strategic alignment in a UK-based Forex SME?

RQ 3: What are the common challenges faced by Forex SMEs when pursuing strategic alignment?

RQ 4: How can the harmonious alignment of business strategy and IT strategy be achieved in Forex SMEs?

RQ5: What kind of recommendations are to be made to Forex SMEs for achieving successful strategic alignment and thereby enhancing organisational performance?

1.4. Rationale

The estimated value of the global Forex market is over US\$ 1.93 quadrillion (Brokernotes, 2021). The Forex industry not only mobilizes the global economy but also is a good indicator of how economies around the world are performing as forex indexes are constantly updating to reflect the socio-economic changes around the world (Glantz and Kissell, 2014; BIS, 2019). During April 2016 and April 2019, the average daily volume of UK Forex operations surged by 49% to US\$3,600 billion, an increase from US\$ 2,400 billion (BoE, 2019a). In 2019, the United Kingdom was registered as the leader in the Forex industry accounting for over 40% of worldwide exchange (BIS, 2019). Forex industry makes substantial contributions to the UK economy, contributing more than £50 billion to the UK economy annually (BoE, 2021), thus investigating the industry could yield several interesting insights.

To comply with constantly changing government procedures and to remain competitive in a fiercely competitive marketplace, Forex firms continuously amend their business strategies and IT strategies so that they serve their customer effectively. Not having an effective alignment of strategies can affect a Forex firm's performance severely, threatening its position in the market. In order to explore how Forex SMEs in the UK achieve strategic alignment and what are challenges they face in the process of achieving strategic alignment, this research qualitatively investigates a UK-based Forex SME. A review of the literature revealed that there is an abundance of literature in terms of factors of strategic alignment of large firms but no research previously investigated Forex SMEs to understand the factors essential for achieving strategic alignment. Although some studies have been undertaken in different SME business contexts for

strategic alignment, further research is needed in strategic alignment (between business strategy and IT strategy) in different SME industries to comprehend further regarding the process (Street et al., 2017). This is because every SME's business environment is different (Afandi, 2020). Therefore, this research seeks to fill this knowledge gap by investigating a UK based Forex SME.

Another rationale for this research is cyber-attack is one of the key problems faced by Forex bureaus in the UK. The need for investigating strategic alignment in the UK Forex SME is considered highly relevant due to a globally recognised Forex firm called "Travelex" faced cyber-attack in December 2019, costing it over £20 million to recover its sensitive business information (BBC, 2020; Reuters, 2020). These problems can be avoided if financial organisations properly align business and IT strategies to enhance organisational performance, protect corporate assets and information from external threats and forces (Alghazi et al., 2017). To achieve strategic alignment, it is necessary to understand the factors of strategic alignment that is specific to the sector/industry and have a framework in place to achieve strategic alignment. By achieving strategic alignment, a firm can benefit in numerous ways such as increased shared knowledge between business and IT departments and increased business protections (Tallon et al., 2016).

The researcher is currently employed in Company A and the researcher has full access to necessary data, information, and interview participants that are necessary for the completion of this research. Moreover, recommendations based on the findings of this research may assist Company A in their future strategic alignment purposes. Also, the researcher seeks to grow his career in the UK Forex industry, hence a robust understanding of how the sector works are expected to enhance his employability significantly.

1.5. Brief Description of the Research Methodology

The term methodology refers to the theory and philosophy governing the conduct of research (Saunders et al., 2019). For this research study, an interpretivist-qualitative approach is employed to explore the factors of strategic alignment of forex SMEs. The qualitative research method is chosen to analyse interview participants' views, opinions, personal experiences, and involvement in the current research phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2019).

This research used the case study strategy and investigated a UK-based forex SME for understanding the factors of strategic alignment as well as the challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment. In order to collect the primary research data, branch managers, senior managers, IT directors, and IT analysts from the case company were qualitatively interviewed. In order to ensure that the interview process is guided by the literature as well as to establish links between theory and practice, semi-structured interviews were conducted. To analyse the interview data, the researcher used 'Nvivo 12 Pro'. Nodes/codes were created to generate the themes for the current study. Although Nvivo 12 Pro supported the researcher in analysing the interview data, the researcher spent additional time reading the interview data manually and repeatedly to have a complete understanding of the data. Chapter Three of this thesis elaborates upon the methodological choices of this research along with the justifications.

1.6. Structure of the Thesis

This research comprises six distinct chapters as presented below:

Chapter One: Introduction

The research background is presented at the start, the research problems are defined, and a research aim is established. This chapter also presented research objectives and main research questions, which is followed by the rationale for the research. In addition, a brief description to the research methodology is presented along with the scope and limitations of the research.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

This chapter reviews key theories related to strategic alignment and strategic alignment in SMEs. An extensive review of the existing literature is conducted to have a broader understanding of the research area as well as to identify the research gaps. Based on a synthesis of the existing literature, a conceptual framework for the research is formulated in the latter part of this chapter.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

This chapter critically reviews different research philosophies and approaches in an attempt to select the most appropriate research design for the research. This chapter also provides

justifications for the chosen research strategy and design. Elaborations on the data collection and analysis process is also made in this chapter along with considerations of research quality and ethics.

Chapter Four: Findings

This chapter presents the findings of the research in detail. The findings of the research are presented under three key themes: factors of strategic alignment for Forex SMEs, challenges faced by Forex SMEs in the process of achieving strategic alignment, and the factors essential for harmonious strategic alignment of business and IT strategies in a Forex SME.

Chapter Five: Discussion of Findings

This chapter of the thesis discusses the findings of the research by locating them in the broader contexts and highlighting their contributions to professional practice as well as the body of knowledge. This chapter discusses findings related to each research objective in detail and together with the predicted and the actual outcomes. A conceptual model has been proposed in this chapter based on the findings of the research.

Chapter Six: Conclusions, Contributions, and Recommendations

This chapter concludes the thesis by highlighting the summary and main conclusions, the contribution to knowledge and practice, the recommendations for Company A's strategic alignment, and recommendations to Forex SMEs strategic alignment. This chapter also highlights the possible limitations of the research along with suggestions for further research.

1.7. Scope and the Limitations of the Research

This research study focuses on Company A's current strategic alignment procedures in an attempt to understand how forex SMEs achieve strategic alignment and what kind of challenges they face in the process of achieving strategic alignment. The research findings are based on an investigation of Company A, which is a UK-based Forex SME. Due to time and resource constraints, researchers usually work on their studies under strict limitations (Saunders et al., 2019). The findings of this research may be impacted by the following limitations:

- Generalisability of the findings: This study was undertaken within the setting of the UK's foreign exchange market. The findings may not be applicable to the foreign exchange market in countries other than the United Kingdom.
- Effects of COVID-19: Due to the effects COVID-19 pandemic in the UK, the majority of the data was collected virtually using telephone interviews and Zoom. The researcher, therefore, may not have been able to fully interpret the body language of all participants.
- Representativeness of the findings: The research data was collected from one UK-based forex SME. The findings therefore may not be representative of all UK based Forex SMEs.

1.8. Chapter Summary

This chapter provided a background to the research by providing a preliminary review of the literature on factors of strategic alignment, and the challenges SMEs face in the process of strategic alignment. This chapter also highlighted the research problem and stated how this study seeks to bridge the existing knowledge gaps. In order to address the research problems, the research aim, objectives, and questions were formulated. In addition, a rationale for the research was also provided, followed by a brief description of the methods used for achieving research objectives, possible limitations of the findings and the structure of the thesis. The following chapter now presents a critical assessment of the existing literature in the area of strategic alignment.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

With the modern marketplace is becoming increasingly competitive and sophisticated, strategic alignment is being seen as a critical factor of an organisation's success in recent years (Papadopoulos et al., 2020; Vial, 2019; Bundy et al., 2017; Sibanda and Ramrathan, 2017; Mayr et al., 2017). Strategic alignment can be considered as the constructive solution for the current dynamic business environment (González-Rodríguez et al., 2018). Strategic alignment enhances organisational performance and overall firm efficiencies, which eventually leads to improved customer experience; therefore, strategic alignment is important for organisations (Papadopoulos et al., 2020). Not only strategic alignment is essential for achieving a firm's organisational objectives, but it also assists firms to protect their sensitive business information (González-Rodríguez et al., 2018; Mayr et al., 2017). Strategically aligned firms perform better than non-aligned firms because strategically aligned firms' plans and goals are integrated with their IT plans and goals (McAdam et al., 2016). A review of the literature revealed that strategic alignment is extensively studied in the context of large firms. However, limited studies were conducted to explore the factors of strategic alignment in SMEs, with no study being conducted in the specific context of strategic alignment of Forex SMEs. Therefore, this research seeks to fill the knowledge gap in the literature by investigating the UK Forex SME sector.

This chapter examines relevant literature in the domain of strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy to understand the factors of strategic alignment in various contexts. For accessing the relevant literature, online search engines and journal databases such as Google Scholar, Science Direct, SAGE journals, Research Gate, Emerald Insight and Elsevier were accessed in addition to physical libraries. Keywords such as 'strategic alignment', 'strategic alignment in SMEs', 'business strategy', 'IT strategy', 'strategic alignment models', and 'challenges for strategic alignment' were used for gathering relevant peer-reviewed journals, books, and articles.

2.2. SMEs and their Importance

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (*SMEs*) are critical to a country's economic development as they play vital roles in the production of employment and income, as well as in improving the trade balance (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2020). SMEs are the primary engines of national economic progress as they contribute by creating new jobs and serving as the entry point for an industry's development (Distanont and Khongmalai, 2020; Street et al., 2017). Most large corporations that exist today evolved from SMEs (World Bank, 2021; Decker et al., 2006). SMEs have evolved as the main connection between finance and economies in the modern business era (Cataldo et al., 2012). According to World Bank (2021), a country's economy increases as long as SMEs flourish. Numerous countries have established policies supporting and promoting SMEs in order to boost the country's competitiveness (Padukkage et al., 2014). SMEs account for more than 90% of businesses and provide between 60% and 70% of new jobs opportunities worldwide (World Bank, 2021).

2.2.1. Defining SMEs

A globally agreeable definition of SMEs has not been established in the literature yet (Muriithi, 2017; Street et al., 2017; Madanchian et al., 2015; Pavlak and Pizar, 2020; Yang, 2016). The exact explanation for SMEs is still different in business (Lahiri et al., 2020). According to the European Commission (2012), SMEs are classified based on firms' characteristics: the total number of working people in the firm, the annual turnover, and the firm's final balance. However, there are other factors used to define SMEs: social capital figures, according to Robu (2013). According to EU Commission (2020), SMEs should have:

- Employees are less than 250 and cannot have more than 250.
- Firm turnover must be less than € 50 million, and annual balance is less than € 43 million.
- Cannot have more than 25% of another firm's authority.

SMEs are defined as organisations with less than 500 employees in the United States; and SMEs are defined as businesses with fewer than 250 employees and turnover should be less than € 50 million in the European Union and the United Kingdom (Akbar et al., 2017; Pavlak and Pizar, 2020; EU, Commission, 2020; ILO, 2021) According to Rhodes and Ward (2020; p. 5) "firms with below 250 employees are classified as SMEs".

In this research, the definition of the European Union and the United Kingdom is considered by considering organisations that employ up to 250 employees and trade below € 50 million annually as SMEs. SMEs work differently from one country to another as one country's development level is different to another country, and their resource availability and allocation, including labour/skill, is also quite different (Blackburn et al., 2013). EU Commission (2020) further categorised companies in larger, medium, small and micro-organisations according to their final turnover, the total number of employees they employ, and the final balance sheet capital (investment).

Figure 2-1: Definition of business categorisation according to European Union (EU).

Source: EU Commission (2020)

According to the Department for International Trade UK (2020, p. 5), SMEs are categorised into three types: "*micro (less than 10 employees and an annual turnover under €2 million), small (less than 50 employees and an annual turnover under €10 million) and medium-sized (less than 250 employees and an annual turnover under €50 million) businesses*". The UK hosts a large number of SMEs with SMEs providing substantial contributions to the country's economy. As presented in Figure 2.2, the number of SMEs in the UK is consistently growing with over 6 million SMEs being in operation as of 2021.

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Figure 2-2: SMEs in the United Kingdom from the year 2000.

Source: Ward (2021)

The forex SME being investigated in this research employs below 250 persons, and it has an annual turnover of below € 40 million; therefore, the firm qualifies as an SME as per the definitions of the UK government as well as the EU Commission.

2.2.2. Importance of SMEs

SMEs are the biggest wealth creators for every country and are considered as the "lifeblood of modern economies" (Rao et al., 2003: p 13). SMEs operate to create many new employments, increasing the motivation for business entrepreneurship, helping nations mitigate poverty and of course, improving the growth of the economy (Canhoto et al., 2021; Eller et al., 2020; Wonglimpiyarat, 2015). According to OECD (2020) and ILO (2021), globally, more than 90% of businesses are SMEs. Furthermore, in developed countries, smaller businesses generate over 60% of income to their GDP and 70% of total employment; whereas, in developing countries, smaller businesses are accountable for 63% of their GDP and 70% of total jobs were covered (OECD, 2020; ILO, 2021). According to Akbar et al. (2017), the importance of smaller firms grew significantly since new business industries started due to smaller firms and industrialisation foundation was built on top of SMEs initiatives and growth.

SME is a small business that is run and governed directly by the owner. Muriithi (2017) argues that in comparison to large corporations, SMEs are less bureaucratic, friendlier and more

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adaptable, but the owner makes all major business decisions. Therefore, SME business owners have the capacity to create new job opportunities since SMEs are flexible and open to any external environment whereas, larger organisations are more bureaucratic and follow business procedures to recruit new employees.

Akbar et al. (2017) and Berisha and Pula (2015) postulated that SMEs are the starting point for business entrepreneurship. The above idea was favoured by Munro (2013) where the author stated that more than creating general employment, SMEs are more favourable on bringing new entrepreneurial concepts to the economy. Stokes and Wilson (2010) highlighted that there is a strong relationship between business entrepreneurship and SME business management.

It is estimated that over 60 million enterprises, or over 35% of SMEs in developing countries, have an annual unfulfilled funding need of \$5 trillion, which is comparable to 1.4 times the present level of global SME lending, according to the International Finance Corporation (World Bank Group, 2020). As a result, the World Bank emphasises that there is an increasing demand for SMEs around the world each year and that these businesses require financial assistance in order to grow and provide new job opportunities for the economy. The below figure highlights SMEs' finance gaps worldwide (World Bank, 2021).

Figure 2-3: SMEs (formal and informal) global finance gaps.

Source: (World Bank, 2021)

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2.2.3. Characteristics of SMEs

Being small significantly influences an SME's business development and increases flexibility in business operations (Forsman, 2008). In alignment literature, being small brings many advantages to firms; however, it also brings disadvantages to SMEs too (Wijenwardena and Cooray, 1996; Spinelli et al., 2013; Eze et al., 2021). A firm with a smaller workforce can be categorised into an SME context, and being an SME, it has special unique characteristics compared to large firms. Although, many characteristics are mentioned in the literature for SMEs (Eze et al., 2021). However, Street et al. (2017) explained that three vital characteristics for SMEs namely, organisational size and resource constraints (Berisha and Pula, 2015; Akbar et al., 2017; Canhoto et al., 2021) strategic planning practices (Wijenwardena and Cooray, 1996), and business owner characteristics (Karami et al., 2006; Blackburn et al., 2013).

Regarding organisational size and resource availability, Cassia et al. (2011) and Flaminiano and Francisco (2021) mentioned that many SMEs have major issues when accessing resources. There are three strategic resources organisations need namely, financial, physical and human resources (Berisha and Pula, 2015; Canhoto et al., 2021; Flaminiano and Francisco, 2021). According to Street and Meister (2004), organisations cannot sustain their operations without having access to sufficient funds. Since SMEs revenues are generating slowly compared to large firms, financial capital limitations can hinder business performance (Sabherwal et al., 2019). According to Baker et al. (2011), physical resources are defined as the goods mainly tangible which require for a business to maintain its business operations. Some examples of physical resources are office materials, equipment, machines (printers, scanners, computers), etc. Gutierrez et al. (2009) highlighted that limitations in IT resources can reduce SME performance significantly. Further, it can reduce SMEs' business growth as well.

According to Lechner and Gudmundsson (2014), strategic planning practices decides SMEs' sustainable growth and happened to be crucial characteristics of SME firms. Indeed, large corporations do concern thoroughly regarding strategic planning in their organisational procedures for a longer time period (Wijnwardana and Coorey, 1996; Luftman and Brier, 1999; Alaceva and Rusu, 2015) however, SMEs focus on having strategic planning for a shorter time period (Afandi, 2020). While the aforementioned characteristics are critical; business owners' awareness and knowledge of their businesses is another critical quality in SMEs (Karami et al.,

2006). According to the literature on company owner characteristics Blackburn et al. (2013) elements including the owners' level of expertise Karami et al. (2006) and owner's level of experience Blackburn et al. (2013) are connected with the successful performance of SMEs (Wijenwardena& Cooray, 1996; Barbara-Sanchez et al., 2007).

Giacchero et al. (2007) stated that since SMEs are hard to modernize and they always lag behind in integrating into the latest technological software and hardware. This was discussed by Eller et al. (2020) and Assante et al. (2016) where authors stated that due to management resistance in SMEs, they are more like to continue with existing obsolete technologies in the firm. Moreover, another SME characteristic would be due to resource and financial constraints, SMEs are unable to organize employee training and development programmes (Giacchero et al., 2007). As SMEs have to spend further on capital to develop employee skills, they encourage employees to self-learn while they are at work (Li et al., 2018; Morgan-Thomas, 2016; Ferreira et al., 2019). Many SMEs have a smaller workforce in their management, and as demand rise, they intend to hire external people (recruit for a shorter period) and talent to serve the customers' demand (Weaven et al., 2021). Strategic decisions demand academic knowledge in managers since strategic management is based on theories (Weaven et al., 2021). According to Delmar and Wiklund (2008) and Richbell et al. (2006), many SME owners lack academic knowledge when they start their businesses. They promote the business with the best courage and their decisions can be made on a temporary basis according to the business situation they face and of course, decisions have higher flexibility (Sexton and Smilor, 1997; Littunen and Niittykangas, 2010).

2.2.4. SMEs Contributions to the UK Economy

In 2020, there were approximately 6 million SMEs in the UK accounting for more than 99% of all firms (Ward, 2021; FSB, 2021). According to FSB (2021), Ward (2021), Rhodes and Ward (2020) and stated by Rhodes (2019) SMEs represent 99% of the whole business community in the UK, highlighting that SMEs are the heart of the UK businesses. However, as compared to the previous year (2019) this represents an increase of over 113,000 new SMEs (FSB, 2021; Ward, 2021). Most SMEs are in the service industries accounting for more than half of all businesses in the UK. The scientific and technological sector, which accounted for 15% of all enterprises, was the most significant of the service sectors in terms of the number of establishments. 9% of all companies were in the retail, administrative and support services industries, respectively. Firms

operating in the retail business sector alone would be responsible for 18% of the total workforce and more than 30% of total revenue in 2020. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 pandemic more than a quarter of UK SMEs had to close their businesses permanently (FSB, 2021). Table 2.1 shows SMEs in the UK by industry in 2020.

Table 2-1: SMEs in the UK by 2020

Source: Ward (2021).

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2.2.5. SMEs Business Success Factors

SMEs are crucial to a country's economy as the efficiency of the SME sector is inextricably related to the nation's performance (Wonglimpiyarat, 2015; Madanchian et al., 2015). Compared to large organisations, SMEs can achieve their business success in a shorter period because they adapt to business environments rapidly (Kemayel, 2015). Many factors support SMEs' business expansion/rapid growth since SMEs don't allow layers of organisational policies internally in their management hierarchy. SMEs are always keen on simple business practices and procedures in their business table according to (Venkatraman and Fahd, 2016; Ward, 2016). However, Philip (2010) stated that internal organisation structure flexibility is essential for SMEs when pursuing business success. The reason behind this was, having more sophisticated organisational

structures will only lead to delay in decision making in business since many people's authorisation is required (Ossai and Lucky, 2012). SMEs can open their businesses in different geographical locations and in a range of different business sectors due to their lower commitments in organisational policies and having higher commitments for flexibility (Parveen and Maimani, 2014; Ward, 2016). However, having higher flexibility is advantageous for any business in general no matter whether it is SME or a larger firm, however, it can create some bottlenecks and potential risks in business since policies and procedures are not considered as a higher priority (Venkatraman and Fahd, 2016). Therefore, to some extent, it is wise to follow policies and procedures to protect business assets from unknown external threats and forces (Ciotti et al., 2020). Therefore organisations including smaller firms also implement strategic alignment procedures to maintain good equilibrium in the business.

According to Karami et al. (2006), Chittithaworn et al. (2011), and Forsman (2008) mentioned growth could be achieved by the interaction of three spheres, namely the entrepreneur, strategy and the firm. As there are many SMEs in the UK more than large firms, it is imperative that to some extent, SME business-owners should be sharper than larger firms (Bazhair and Sandhu, 2015). According to Ossai and Lucky (2012), business strategy matters most than any other strategy in the company. But for online retail businesses such as "*eBay, Amazon, Ocado*" prioritise their IT strategy more than their business strategy as they communicate to customers via many technology platforms (Evangelista, 2014; Bazhair and Sandhu, 2015). Therefore, prioritising the strategy decides SMEs' business success. SMEs business owners must have thorough knowledge about their business industry strengths, opportunities and their firm's capabilities to compete against industry rivals (Ramukumba, 2014). Since due to flexibility and openness in SMEs products and services towards their customers, is a positive remark, therefore, it is important that SME business owners should be well-experienced in their roles (Venkatraman and Fahd, 2016; Bazhair and Sandhu, 2015).

Business growth and successful performance can be measured through changes in turnover, profitability and employment levels over the last few years in a firm (Ghosh et al., 2001). However, as SMEs face challenges such as investment allocations, employment training, and resource allocation for business processes, business growth depends on how firms respond to the above challenges hence, it can be considered as success factors too.

Indarty and Langenberg (2005) recognised three critical components for analysing the commercial success of SMEs: the entrepreneurs' qualities, the SMEs' characteristics, and lastly the factors affecting SME development. Chittithaworn et al. (2011) highlighted that success in Thai SMEs depends on the owner's understanding of the overall business and to what extent the owner accepts strategic concepts for business growth. There are numerous factors SMEs business success namely, the SME's leadership and understanding towards employees and business (Swierczek and Ha, 2003), the firm's characteristics (Kristiansen et al., 2003), the goods and services offered (Hitt and Iralan, 2000; Wiklund et al., 2004), the consumer and business (William et al., 2005), the nature and method of conducting business (Hett and Iraland, 2000; Jariello, 1988), finance and assets (Kristiansen et al., 2003; Swierczek and Ha, 2003), strategy (Street et al., 2017; Spinelli et al., 2003; McMahon, 2001), and the surrounding environment in which the business operates (Indarty and Langenberg, 2005).

2.3. Organisational Strategies

All of the actions that businesses take in order to attain long-term business objectives are summarised in organisational strategies (Steensen, 2014). A firm's mission statement, which underlines the reason for the company's existence, will serve as the foundation for organisational strategy (Chivandi et al., 2014). This research specifically focuses on investigating the strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy; hence business strategy and IT strategy are discussed below.

2.3.1. Business Strategy

Andrews (1971) stated that business strategy determines a company's final strategic position to achieve the final goals and objectives. According to Mintzberg (1987), the word '*strategy*' is a military idea that has been modified for use in business in order to accomplish the firm's short- and long-term objectives. However different scholars and professionals consider the phrase '*strategy*' in different ways Mintzberg et al. (2003). According to Saad et al. (2017), business strategy is the process of determining the measures necessary to accomplish an aim while making the greatest use of existing resources and assets. Therefore, the strategy is bound by the organisation's business nature, which includes its resources, business surrounding, culture,

abilities and structure, in which it works (Blackburn et al., 2013; Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016; Alzahrani, 2019; Mitropoulos, 2021). Business strategies must be distinct from those of other businesses, and they must always focus on creating value for the organization's future (Alzahrani, 2019). Thus, business strategy can be thought of as a long-term master plan that outlines the path a business will take and the activities it will take to accomplish its objectives (Chivandi et al., 2014; Wunderlich, 2018; Gartlan and Shanks, 2007; Raymond and Bergeron, 2008; Saad et al., 2017; Rathnam et al., 2005).

Diverse perspectives exist on what makes a business strategy (Alzahrani, 2019). Ilmudeen and Malik (2016) described business strategy as a critical managerial function because it is a long-term plan of action designed to accomplish a set of objectives. Business strategy's fundamental purpose is to improve performance (Bartlett and Ghoshal, 1994). However, Zott and Amit (2008) state that business strategy, not only improves the performance of a firm but also provides a long-lasting competitive advantage. Thus the business strategy is one of the most important components of corporate success. Recent literature state that business strategy is a method for internal analysis, with the purpose of identifying strengths and weaknesses as part of the scanning process throughout the strategy creation stages (Saad et al., 2017; Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016; Mitropoulos, 2021).

2.3.1.1. Types of Business Strategies

In literature, the classifications of Miles and Snow's (1978) and Porter's (1980) have been established as the two prominent corporate strategy frameworks. 40 years back Miles and Snow (1978) constructed a precise thorough framework for examining the various ways in which firms identify and manage their domains of product and market, as well as the structures and procedures that enable them to succeed in the above domains (Slater and Olson, 2001; Slater et al., 2011). Miles and Snow established four models of how organisations deal with these difficulties in their study of the subject. According to Slater and Olson (2001), 'Prospectors' are constantly on the lookout for exploiting new products and market prospects, whereas 'Defenders' are attempting to lock off a section of the whole market in order to establish steady products and consumers. According to Raymond and Bergeron (2008), a firm is a prospector if it is inventive in its approach to introducing new technology and moving into new industries. As a middle ground between the two extremes, 'Analyzers' use the strengths of both prospectors and

defenders in order to carefully pursue prospectors into new product and market sectors while simultaneously securing the consistent products and consumers (Miles and Snow, 1978).

Academics recommended using Miles and Snow's classification because it is helpful when investigating different strategic orientations that firms may adopt in different business situations (Slater and Olson, 2001; Slater et al., 2011; Desarbo et al., 2005). Not only that Miles and Snow's (1978) typology introduced a fourth category, which is called reactor, which denotes a lack of a defined business strategy and is hence of little consequence.

However, to analyse Miles and Snow's typology in greater detail, Raymond and Bergeron (2008) stated that defenders are enterprises that concentrate their efforts on relatively secure niches within the business sector in which they operate. They have little interest in developing new items and market segments. Furthermore, the literature state that defenders prioritise operational effectiveness, cost reduction, product quality, shorter delivery times, and consumer satisfaction, as well as assuring profitability through economies of scale (Brunk, 2003; Shortell and Zajac, 1990; Allen and Helms, 2006; Raymond and Bergeron, 2008).

Analysers have several features with defenders and prospectors, most notably a preference for increased production in balanced markets, similar to how defenders do, but also similar to how prospectors do in uncertain situations (Miles and Snow 1978; Slater and Narver 1993). However, firms that serve as analyzers strive to maintain their goods' market success by efficient processes and inter-organizational integration/alignment (Blumentritt and Danis, 2001).

Prospectors are a strategic sort of SME that is primarily concerned with generating new products and markets - altering their product lines and attempting to capitalise on business opportunities (Galbraith and Schendel, 1983; Raymond and Bergeron, 2008). They conduct research and development in order to innovate and introduce new products/services. Their strategy is to incorporate new technologies that increase their capacity for innovation and their ability to rapidly generate new products (Galbraith and Schendel, 1983).

2.3.1.2. Importance of Business Strategy to SMEs

Developing a successful business strategy is a critical management activity that can be thought of as a long-term action plan aimed primarily at achieving a set of objectives (Barney, 2001; Grant,

2010). Oltra and Flor (2010) discovered that business strategy has a strong moderating effect on the association between company performance and operation strategy. Thus the importance of business strategy is extremely above for all firms.

Despite SMEs' numerous contributions to the world economy, still, SMEs are "*plagued by high failure rates and poor performance levels*" (Jocumsen, 2004; p. 659). In past years, research carried out in SMEs (Schwenk and Shrada, 1993; Miller and Cardinal, 1994; Hormozi et al., 2002) revealed that "*ceteris paribus*" meaning success in business always determine by strategic planning concepts. Bui and De Villiers (2017) and Croteau and Bergeron (2001) defined business strategy as being concerned with the formulation and executing long-term organizational objectives, as well as allocation of required resources to achieve objectives. However, compare to Anwar (2018) business strategy of an SME is all about gaining a competitive advantage over the competition. As stated by O'Regan and Ghobadian (2002, p. 664) the main objective of business strategy is helping the firm "*to gain as efficiently as possible, a sustainable edge over its competitors*".

Compelling evidence found on literature that in terms of business performance, SMEs who are strategically involved in business, perform better in general. For instance, SME firms who are involved thoroughly in strategic practices perform strong sales performance, profit margins are higher and employee motivation is promising too (Carland and Carland, 2003; Evans and Bosua, 2017; Dong et al., 2008). Moreover, SMEs who are engaged in strategic concepts of business and IT planning are the ones who are more successive, innovative, creating new products and services, recruiting new business and IT solutions and also, get more publicity (Karadağ, 2018; McAdam et al., 2017; Mazzarol et al., 2014). However, it is unquestionably true that strategic management in business and IT improves SMEs' business performance (McAdam et al., 2017). However, some studies show that when compared to strategic theories, strategic practices matter the most in terms of achieving business success (Mazzarol et al., 2014; Dong et al., 2008).

The fact why business strategy has piqued the interest of academics is due to the fact that it not only helps to increase profitability but also helps to extend the life span of an organisation (Karadağ, 2018). For the most part, many business professionals in financial institutions assume that strategy is designed only for larger organizations. However, evidence suggests that strategic practices are matching for SME environment also (Evans and Bosua, 2017; Karadağ, 2018;

Acquaah and Agyapong, 2015). In today's world, SMEs must prioritise business strategy since the increasing unpredictability of globalisation and the sophistication of customer expectations; as a result, SMEs have become more aware of the need to develop their knowledge of strategic thinking (Rehman and Anwar, 2019; Ammar and Chereau, 2018). Street et al. (2017) highlighted that business strategy assists and guide SMEs in search of new business opportunities. Therefore, business strategy is the first step toward achieving success in SMEs.

The importance of business strategy to the financial industry was discussed in previous studies. Pelham (2000) in his research examined how market orientation and other possible factors support SMEs' business performance. 1200 industrial manufacturing SMEs were selected for his research and Pelham stated that as the market environment changes, the business strategy needs to align with those changes to sustain performance. Bracker and Pearson (1986) examined financial accomplishment in SMEs who are engaged in the dry cleaning sector. The authors highlighted that financial accomplishment depends on to what extent business strategy understands customer expectations. Yusuf (1995) studied critical success factors for SME businesses and examined SMEs in various business sectors where he concluded that business strategy is one of the success factors for SMEs.

2.3.2. IT Strategy

Information Technology (IT) is a broad concept that aggregates all technological solutions, in order to support business operations in an organisation (Eller et al., 2020). According to Kamariotou and Kitsios (2019) IT strategy emphasis narrowly on technology. IT strategy is concerned with the management of both hardware and software resources within an organisation and enables organisations to shift their focus and resources in the future (Gradiesch and Gilbert, 2001, Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993, King, 1978). A clear explanation provided by Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017) and Broadbent and Weill (1993) highlighted that IT strategy can be considered as a data management procedure, which is the process of obtaining, classifying, and presenting data that is critical for decision making in businesses. In past years, numerous scholars have concluded that businesses cannot survive without a proper IT strategy (Mithas and Rust, 2016; Bharadwaj et al., 2013; Mithas et al., 2012; Moyo, 1996) while others have concluded that businesses cannot survive without an effective IT strategy (Mistry, 2019; Khuntia et al., 2018; Hong, 2009). Thus defining IT strategy is a difficult issue in today's business world.

So in a way of speaking, IT strategy entails the interaction of internal and external businesses with the goal of facilitating communication between the business and vendors (Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016; Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993). Singh and Hess (2017) highlighted that IT strategy is only a comprehensive guidance map designed specifically to support business goals and future expectations. To have maximum efficiency in an IT strategy, senior IT and business leaders should improve their understanding of each other and share knowledge repeatedly. Research carried out in Australian institutions by Gartlan and Shanks (2007) revealed that IT Directors wishes to be get involved in the business strategy formation process. However, Chief Executives do not believe that the involvement of IT Directors is not necessary for business strategy formation. Although, literature has highlighted that understanding between business and IT is one of the key issues that many organisations trying to resolve in the current business and IT context (Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019a).

Henderson and Venkatraman (1993) highlighted that IT strategy can be divided into three major components namely, “*the IT scope, the systematic competencies and IT governance component*” In previous years many businesses and IT scholars used Henderson and Venkatraman’s definition for IT strategy for their research studies (Coltman et al., 2015; Gerow et al., 2015; Ilmudeen, 2013; Chan and Reich, 2007; Chan et al., 1997). Moreover, previous scholars employed Henderson and Venkatraman’s definition to develop future models for IT strategy and strategic alignment (Al-Surmi et al., 2020; Sibanda and Ramrathan, 2017; Coltman et al., 2015; Gerow et al., 2015; Ilmudeen, 2013; Gerow, 2011).

Furthermore, researchers have stated that IT strategy encompasses the control of IT human resources in order to ensure alignment with the business technology strategy (Ilmudeen and Irshard, 2015; Gartlan and Shanks, 2007). Therefore, to summarise the views expressed concerning the IT strategy, an IT strategy is a strategic business platform that helps the organisation to structure future paths and monitor the efficient use and governance of available IT resources, IT relationships both internally and externally, and the maintenance of information flow and storage throughout the business organisation (Verhoef et al., 2019; Gartlan and Shanks, 2007).

Mithas and Rust (2016), as well as Mithas et al. (2012) shown unequivocally that in comparison to business strategy, IT strategy entails a greater risk of investment failure and project failure. As

a result, the authors emphasise that the IT strategy definition should be refined in accordance with the organization's business goal and should incorporate input from other business stakeholders. Ilmudeen and Irshard (2015) authors defined IT strategy as the manner in which IT will support the firm in winning, with IT leading the business strategy and IT executing the business strategy. Smith et al. (2007) revealed that an IT strategic plan must have an IT investment plan in order to stay competitive and lead the organisation to a winning position.

2.3.2.1. Types of IT Strategies

Sabherwal and Chan (2001, p. 13) proposed three types of IT strategies namely, “*flexibility, efficiency, and comprehensiveness*”. IT strategy for flexibility uses technology to monitor business data and developments in the market, as well as to provide a basis for decision-making processes. According to the researchers, this is compatible with organisations implementing prospector methods because flexibility and the emphasis of both prospectors and IT flexibility techniques are assessed as being of high value (Sabherwal and Chan, 2001). Using IT to monitor and regulate everyday operations, improve operational productivity, and support the functions of information exchange and communication in order to connect with consumers and suppliers are all examples of IT strategies for efficiency. Therefore, this type of IT strategy is particularly useful to defenders who place a high value on performance (Sabherwal and Chan, 2001). Thirdly, the IT strategy for comprehensiveness relates to the use of technology for monitoring business information and developments, as well as for assisting the role of information sharing and interaction for connecting with consumers and suppliers. In order to provide flexibility and productivity, this IT strategic approach is considered to be the optimal IT strategy for analysers, according to (Sabherwal and Chan, 2001).

2.3.2.2. Importance of IT strategies to SMEs

According to Sexton and Ven-Auken (1985) in past years, SMEs have been involved in strategic management practices to a lower level. To achieve competitive advantage and to improve organisational performance in overall Lyles et al. (1993) advocated that SMEs should consider formal strategic planning methods. Maranto-Vargas and Gomez-Tagle (2007) indicated that IT helps to the establishment of competitive advantages, more specifically, in improving soft technology which is "organisational processes, procedures, and technical expertise than

any 'hard' technology". Therefore, IT strategies are considered in SMEs to integrate the technical understanding of the organisation's IT with business expertise in order to develop executable plans to buildup the IT's engagement in business value.

The business plan and the IT strategy must be strategically aligned to achieve strategic alignment (Benbya and McKely, 2006; Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993). Thus, the IT strategy functions as a conduit or bridge between the business strategy and IT, re-aligning on a constant basis, or even as a catalyst for business change. While this relationship was discovered to be true for large enterprises (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Kappelman et al., 2013), it was also discovered to be valid for smaller firms (Hussin et al., 2002). Firms with a flexible and clear IT strategy for business objectives are a success element in strategic alignment and a positive sign, according to (Drechsler et al., 2016; Welsh and White, 1982). Therefore, the importance of IT strategy to SMEs is quite valuable.

2.3.2.3 Role of Information Technology in Forex SMEs

Information Technologies (IT) support Forex SMEs by providing tools, platforms, and solutions that enhance their operations, efficiency, and competitiveness in the global currency markets (Arshad et al., 2020). According to Fitriatia et al. (2020), trading platforms enable Forex SMEs to execute their trading and exchange operations in a secure environment. These platforms provide real-time market data, charts, and execution capabilities. Furthermore, IT offers advanced features like automated trading, algorithmic trading, and risk management tools, empowering SMEs to execute trades swiftly and effectively (Bagorogoza and de Waal, 2010).

Connectivity and alignment are crucial for Forex SMEs to perform their Forex trading accurately and securely (Dang and Lindsay, 2022). IT facilitates connectivity and integration between different market participants, such as SMEs, brokers, and payment systems. Seamless alignment allows for fast and secure transmission of trade data, trade confirmations, and settlement instructions, enabling smooth operations in the Forex market. According to Dang and Lindsay (2022), security and data protection are important given the sensitive nature of financial transactions. IT plays a critical role in ensuring security and data protection in Forex businesses. Robust cybersecurity measures, encryption techniques, and secure network infrastructure help safeguard SMEs' financial data and sensitive customer information (Syed et al., 2012).

Risk management is another important support provided by IT for Forex SMEs. Risk management tools such as automated stop-loss orders and position monitoring systems help SMEs mitigate potential losses and protect trading positions (Azam, 2015; Ashby et al., 2012). IT solutions also facilitate the implementation of risk management policies and procedures. IT systems streamline back-office operations, including trade settlement, accounting, and reporting (Azam, 2015). These systems automate processes, reduce paperwork, and ensure accurate and timely recording of transactions, improving operational efficiency for SMEs in the Forex sector (Dang and Lindsay, 2022).

Forex SMEs operate in a highly regulated environment. Ashby et al. (2012) highlighted that IT solutions assist in automating compliance processes and regulatory reporting. They guide SMEs in tracking and documenting transactions, ensuring adherence to anti-money laundering (AML) and know-your-customer (KYC) regulations (Andronova and Shelepov, 2019; Azam, 2015). This ensures compliance with legal requirements and prevents fraudulent activities. Moreover, Arshad et al. (2020) highlighted that IT solutions enable effective communication and collaboration among Forex SMEs, their clients, and other stakeholders. Email systems, video conferencing, and collaborative platforms facilitate real-time interaction, information sharing, and teamwork. This enhances customer service, improves operational efficiency, and fosters strong relationships with clients (Dang and Lindsay, 2022).

Overall, IT tools are essential for the smooth operation of today's Forex SME sector as they enable these businesses to access global markets, make informed trading decisions, manage risk effectively, automate processes, comply with regulations, and maintain the security and integrity of their operations. IT systems provide the foundation for the efficient functioning and strategic alignment of SMEs in the dynamic and fast-paced Forex market.

2.4. Strategic Alignment

2.4.1. Theoretical Background of Strategic Alignment

For almost 30 years, academia has articulated the concept of strategic alignment using various explanations or synonyms, though the research studies related to strategic alignment are still in an emerging position. In literature, multiple scholars have defined strategic alignment by using different terms. Conclusively, defining strategic alignment is as tricky as defining its purpose and use. Numerous views and explanations for strategic alignment available in academic literature include "Strategic Alignment", "Linkage" (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993); "Business-IT Alignment" (Maes et al., 2000); "Harmony" (Luftman, 1996); "Fit" (Venkatraman, 1989; Porter, 1996; Chan and Huff, 1992); "Bridge" (Ciborra, 1997), "Integration" (Weill and Broadbend, 1998), "Fusion" (Smaczny, 2001), and "Information Systems Alignment" (Chan et al., 2006; Benbya and McKelvey, 2006). The table below presents some key definitions of strategic alignment:

Table 2-2: Definitions of Strategic Alignment

Theoretical Explanation	Source
"The fit and integration among business strategy, IT strategy, business structures and IT structures"	De Haes and Grembergen [2015; 4]
"The degree to which the IT group understands the priorities of the business and expends its resources, pursues projects, and provides information consistent with these priorities."	Turban and Volonino [2010; 95]
"The degree to which the business strategy and plans, and the IT/IS strategy and plans, complement each other"	Chan and Reich [2007; 300]
"The coordination achieved when the company's IT/IS strategy is derived from the organization strategy"	Iman and Hartono [2007; 256]
"The degree to which the information technology mission, objectives, and plans support and are supported by the business mission, objectives, and plans"	Reich and Benbasat [2000; 82]
"The fit between business strategic orientation and information systems strategic orientation"	Chan et al. [1997; 56]
"Alignment is the degree to which the needs, demands, goals, objectives, and/or structures of one component are consistent with the needs, demands, goals, objectives, and/or structures of another component."	Nadler and Tushman [1983; 119]

As mentioned by Reich and Benbasat (2000), Chan (2008) and Bergeron et al. (2001), strategic alignment is a process of integrating IT, business plans and structures, as well as aligning IT and business processes. While some researchers such as Luftman (2004) stated that attaining strategic alignment needs increasing the enablers and decreasing the inhibitors. In contrast, others argued that matching both IT and business visions is the best way to achieve alignment (Peak et al., 2005; Kearns and Sabherwal, 2006). With the passage of time, several conceptual frameworks such as, "IT planning, strategic IT planning, and IT capability" have emerged in the alignment domain, making comprehending strategic alignment more difficult (Coltman et al., 2015; Gerow et al., 2015; Luftman et al., 2008; Karpovsky et al., 2014).

Previously, strategic alignment was viewed as a preparing event in the 1980s that resulted in the development of strategic plans to accomplish strategic goals through the integration of IT and business ideas. According to King (1978), strategic planning for an organisations' information expectations is critical for achieving its objectives since IT facilitates the achievement and maximization of competitive new possibilities in IT services and the provision of support for businesses. However, despite the formal nature of the approach to strategic alignment, some frameworks helped improve the process of strategic IT (King, 1978; Pyburn, 1983; Lientz and Chen, 1980; Wiseman 1985).

Strategic alignment, according to Henderson and Venkatraman (1993: p. 8) is the extent to which "IT strategy, business strategy, business infrastructure, and IT infrastructure" are in sync with one another. Although Chan et al. (1997) asserted that strategy by itself does not guarantee effective alignment. Maes et al. (2000: p. 21) examined strategic alignment from a dynamic viewpoint, defining it as "a continuous process; involving management and design sub-processes, of consciously and coherently interrelating all components of the business and IT relationship in order to contribute to the organization's performance over time". Scholars have broadened their knowledge base and considerations by conducting investigations to ascertain the characteristics that facilitate ("*enhance*") strategic alignment and those that obstruct ("*hinder*") strategic alignment. They are, "shared domain knowledge and planning practices, involvement of senior managers in strategic business-IT planning, involvement of IT department in business planning, senior management understanding of IT, communication between business and IT management" (Teo and Ang, 1999; Luftman et al., 1999; Reich and Benbasat, 2000).

Examining the planning and integration of technology and business goals was considered by Kearns and Lederer (2004) and Chan (2002) after measuring the strategic alignment as the extent to which "business mission, objectives and business plans" are continuously aided by IT's goals and mission. The above understanding is the basic principle of strategic alignment and firms searching for a framework to sustain it. However, business and IT amendments are inevitable due to various external forces such as government and economic changes. As a result, a focus on establishing strategic IT-business integration in firms becomes an intriguing subject of research for scholars (Kotusev, 2020; Afandi, 2020; Sharma and Behl, 2020; Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Wang, 2014). According to Chan and Reich (2007, p. 300), strategic alignment refers to the "degree to which the company strategy and plans and the IT strategy and plans complement one another".

It was noted that alignment studies are now concerned with preserving and maintaining dynamic strategic alignment since organisations lack knowledge of sustaining strategic alignment procedures (Luftman et al., 2015; Madsen, 2010; Kappelman et al., 2013). Organisations should accomplish strategic alignment because the dynamic economic climate creates new markets and business and technological practices for business, where organisations lack knowledge about (Madsen, 2010). Nevertheless, technological solutions are one of the necessary elements for business performance and also, maintaining strategic alignment has already become a continuous challenge for organisations (Williams et al., 2019). Strategic alignment is a process of finding the best tune for business and IT; therefore, many studies should be conducted under strategic alignment to comprehend further the concept (Miropoulos, 2021; Lerner, 2015).

2.4.2. Strategic Alignment in SMEs

Indeed, apart from the studies on strategic alignment in larger corporations, SMEs obviously demand an investigation on their own (Ahmed et al., 2016). Literature evaluation was limited to theories related to strategic alignment that were relevant to SMEs, as determined by the definition of strategic alignment above. There are many research studies exist in the literature regarding strategic alignment for large organisations and their success factors; however, only a few have focused on strategic alignment for SMEs compared to larger organisations (Wang and Rusu, 2018; Gutierrez et al., 2007; Gutierrez et al., 2009; Garg and Goyal, 2012). Wang and Rusu (2018) argued that less research focused on comprehending the factors that can hinder

strategic alignment, especially in Chinese SMEs. Scholars have highlighted recent research found distinct characteristics about strategic alignment for SMEs since compared to SMEs, larger firms have higher employees, resources availabilities and financial support (Slim et al., 2021; Afandi, 2020; Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019; Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Wang and Rusu, 2018). Therefore, procedures of strategic alignment which approved for large institutions will not be appropriate for SMEs. Surprisingly, many scholars and practitioners started investigating strategic alignment for SMEs in previous years due to high demand in the market (Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019). Similarly, SME managers lack understanding regarding strategic alignment concepts, and importantly, they are unaware of how to execute in their respective firms (Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019). However, in the literature, current knowledge regarding SMEs' strategic alignment is limited but requires further comprehensive solutions for future implementations (Afandi, 2020).

Scholars have highlighted that identifying determinants (or factors) that enable or barriers to strategic alignment can give firms a head start, as firms can prepare in advance to mitigate or avoid them (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015). Indeed, compared to large firms SMEs are weaker in strategic principles, and their technology can be obsolete (Chan et al., 2019). However, some studies argued that SME businesses should be more concerned about their strategic alignment in process base than strategies (Chan and Reich, 2007). Nevertheless, SMEs should execute strategic alignment based on the latest business and market environment and also, to sustain business flexibility it is wise to include management feedback (Abosedo et al., 2016). In relation to factors which enhance or hinder (or impede) strategic alignment in SMEs can be categorised as follows: "the significance of well-developed strategic planning procedures" (Wang and Rusu, 2018; Gutierrez et al., 2009; Chao, 2009; Bruce, 1998), "the institutional structure, size, and age of the organisation" (Garg and Goal, 2012; Raymond and Bergeron, 2008; Jouirou and Kalika, 2004), "features of the surrounding environment" (Raymond and Bergeron, 2008), "the level of firm's IT sophistication" (Mohammad and Ismail, 2010; Chao, 2009), "to what extent employees' are trust and committed in strategic alignment" (Wang and Rusu, 2018; Street et al., 2017), "to what extent SMEs believe in and approaching external IT support" (Mohamad and Ismail, 2010; Ismail and King, 2007), "the understanding and devotion of senior management to IT" (Chao and Chandra, 2012)

According to Williams et al. (2019), formal business practices always encourage strategic awareness and the need for alignment within organisations. In past years, various studies have investigated the correlation between strategic alignment and business performance in SMEs (Afandi, 2017; Luftman et al., 2015; Raymond et al., 1995). An SME might follow strategic alignment based on different solutions based on their market stability (Levy et al., 2011). Not only that an SME is capable of achieving higher performance in their business transactions only if they align the firm's business strategy with e-business capabilities (Raymond and Bergeron, 2008).

According to the literature, organisational size substantially impacts the relationship between strategic alignment and business performance (Sibanda and Ramrathan, 2017). Likewise, another study reveals that resource restrictions affect SMEs' alignment variables and outputs (Sibanda and Ramrathan, 2017; Nakhleh, 2017; Raymond et al., 2012; Raymond, 1985). SMEs are routinely described in research as resource-restricted and confronted with significantly different issues from those facing larger enterprises (Sibanda and Ramrathan, 2017). However, the popularity and demand in SMEs stress the need for new knowledge in strategic alignment, especially for SMEs in different business industries (Afandi, 2020).

2.4.3. Advantages of Strategic Alignment

After reviewing the literature three main advantages of strategic alignment were found: enhanced organisational performance (Kotusev, 2020; Bakotic, 2016; Birchall et al., 2004), enhanced organisational profitability (Onyama, 2021; Bernat and Karabag, 2019), and increased competitive advantage (Haseeb et al., 2019; Saeidi et al., 2015).

Organisational performance is the ultimate goal for any organisation (Latif et al., 2015; Birchall et al., 2004). Organisational performance is defined as evaluating an organisation's final performance compared to organisational objectives and goals (Kotusev, 2020). Similarly, organisational performance can be defined as containing the final results of an organisation compared to targeted results (Maduenyi et al., 2015). According to Bakotic (2016), there are four success factors for enhanced organisational performance such as organizational leadership, organisation culture, strategic alignment and organisational knowledge management. The authors further stated that organisational performance requires senior management involvement and their

dedication to improve it. It was noted in recent literature that most organisations witness poor firm performance due to incompatibilities in their business strategies and IT strategies (Pelletier and Cloutier, 2019; Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Karpovsky and Galliers, 2015). Strategic alignment decides the final direction of an organisation thus leading to enhanced organisational performance (Street et al., 2017). Organisational performance has a positive relationship with strategic alignment thus strategic alignment should revise regularly to maintain organisational performance (Al-Surmi et al., 2020; Latif et al., 2015; Maduenyi et al., 2015).

It was noted in the literature that no organisation can survive in the current business environment without maintaining enough profitability (Onyama, 2021; Zakery et al., 2017). Organisational profitability can be defined as the true profitability of an organisation after compared with the final expenses (Bernat and Karabag, 2019). Organisational profitability can be measured in various ways though in retail businesses it was measured by the margin price confirmed to customers (Sethibe and Steyn, 2016). Organisational profitability has a positive relationship with strategic alignment since efficient business and IT strategies work towards achieving organisational goals which relate to final profits (Fleury et al., 2013). Organisations may witness lower profitability due to inefficiencies in business strategies and IT strategies (Karpovsky and Galliers, 2015). It was noted by Wang and Rusu (2018) that reduced interaction between business strategy and IT strategy could lead to reduced organisational profits.

Competitive advantage was defined in literature as an organisation that requires a favourable position in order to generate higher revenues (Haseeb et al., 2019; Saeidi et al., 2015). Previous studies also highlighted that excellent customer service has a positive relationship with increased competitive advantage (Herrera, 2015). It was revealed that alignment between business strategy and IT strategy assist organisations in maintaining a higher competitive advantage (Haseeb et al., 2019). Moreover, Wang and Rusu (2018) highlighted that having an enhanced competitive advantage is necessary for Chinese SMEs thus organisational strategies must be flexible towards satisfying customers. Similarly, no organisation can have satisfied customers unless their organisational strategies are developed to understand customer expectations (Herrera, 2015). However, there are advantages firms can achieve when competitive advantage is achieved such as repetitive customers and recommendations, higher organisational performance and efficiency in supply chains (Haseeb et al., 2019; Mahdi et al., 2019).

2.4.4. Models for Strategic Alignment

Numerous theoretical models have been developed over time to evaluate an organisation's strategic alignment. Almost every model's purpose is to provide a pathway for organisations to achieve strategic alignment between their business and IT strategies. Some of the key models for strategic alignment are reviewed below:

2.4.4.1. Strategic Alignment Model (SAM)

Henderson and Venkatraman (1993) established the "Strategic Alignment Model (SAM)" on the basis of the model of MIT90, which is likely the most often mentioned of all models. This concept of strategic alignment was the first of its kind to capture the attention of professionals and academicians throughout the world (Henriques et al., 2019; Renaud et al., 2016). According to the theory, the SAM model consists of four interrelated domains namely, Business Strategy, IT Strategy, Organisational Infrastructure and Processes, and IT Infrastructure and Processes (Majstorović, 2016) (see Figure 2.4 below).

Figure 2-4: Strategic Alignment Model (SAM).

Source: (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993)

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According to Henderson and Venkatraman (1993; 1999), the business strategy consists of external and internal domains. The external domain of business strategy consists of the scope of the business (business will define their unique markets where they compete and what products and services they offer to customers), distinctive competencies component (identifying the critical success factors which are needed for business to achieve success), and business governance (says about the relationship between senior management and board of directors or shareholders). On the other hand, the business strategy's internal domain consists of the administrative structure of the organisation (the manner in which a business is organised), the "business process" segment (explains how firms will execute their business strategies), and human resources/skills need (skills and unique talent require for business success) (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993).

According to Henderson and Venkatraman (1993; 1999), the IT strategy is categorised into external and internal domains. The external domain of IT strategy consists of, the scope of the technology (defining the vital IT applications and supportive technologies needed for business), systematic competencies component (the ability to what extent does the IT strategy have access to business strategy information), and IT governance (making necessary decisions and defining the authority regarding the IT).

The SAM model is distinguished by two essential characteristics of strategic management, both of which influence the overall strategy of a business. The first characteristic is strategic integration (alignment) which is concerned with the interdependence of internal and external domains. The second characteristic is functional integration, which primarily refers to the alignment of the business and technological domains in one system (Gutierrez et al., 2008). However, in order to attain strategic alignment, it is necessary to consider both strategic fit and functional integration factors (Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993).

In the literature, there is a significant amount of empirical and practical evidence for SAM (see, Chan and Reich, 2007; Avison et al., 2004; Maes et al., 2000). A study conducted by Avison et al. (2004) validated the SAM's utility in financial sector businesses to see whether it is effective as a management tool for achieving strategic alignment between IT and business. However, while the SAM has many advantages, it also has certain drawbacks. According to Luftman et al.

(2017), the revealed that this model was solely conceptual and therefore incapable of analysing and detecting alignment levels.

SAM is conceptual; however, case study research has demonstrated that it correctly reflects modern corporate alignment notions (Cooper et al., 2000; Avison et al., 2004). Henderson and Venkatraman (1993) emphasised the importance of strategic IT alignment as a continual and dynamic process, which SAM facilitates. SAM does not provide guidelines in how to achieve strategic alignment but, it gives the starting point to strategic alignment, especially what includes in strategic alignment.

2.4.4.2. Duffy's (2001) Maturity Model

According to Duffy (2001), his concept is predicated on the premise that establishing a trustworthy, mutually compatible alliance between IT and business leaders is critical when attaining business-IT alignment. Therefore, it is impossible to get the intended outcome without first establishing this foundation. Duffy's model was developed based on key success factors such as, "human resource organisation and management, innovation and renewal strategy, IT and business architecture, IT and business partnership, operational excellence, and ROI strategy" (Duffy, 2001; p. 21). These drivers are implemented through KPIs where each success driver have five elements that contribute and are designed specifically to address explicit and implicit needs. Duffy (2001) revealed the six drivers which are helpful to measure strategic alignment mentioned below:

- Management and organisation of human resources - it is important that organisations should maintain the required level of work skills since organisational targets cannot be achieved without the right people. Therefore, particular emphasis is placed on the significance of recruiting the right skills and talents and retention for the firm (Duffy, 2001).
- A strategy for creativity and renewal - The emphasis here is on a firm's innovation, with a focus on money and validity, which has an effect on determining whether procedures and capacities inside an organisation need to be renewed or not (Duffy, 2001).

- IT and business architecture - This category is about where relationship and engagement of entities engaged in the information and applications that are used in the firm's business environment (Duffy, 2001).
- Collaboration between IT and business - This category represents the impact of the recent enhancement in the role of the technology function on a firm. "Technology is vital to business success, and this interdependence necessitates a win-win collaboration between IT and non-IT executives" (Duffy, 2001, p. 29).
- Excellence in operations management - This area is concerned with the results of the organization's performance evaluation. According to Duffy, operational excellence is only possible when a firm understands the significance of principles contained in learning and partnerships and is capable of responding quickly to market needs (Duffy, 2001).
- Management of ROI strategy - This area examines the critical nature of the metrics and methods required for effective and successful financial planning within organisations, as well as the importance of treating IT costs and benefits on an equal footing with business costs and benefits (Duffy, 2001).

The model addresses the claim of "IT and non-IT" as well as key strategic factors within a business, although it is made to understand that, there are no clearly - defined maturity levels for them in Duffy's framework. The model's six domains are instead combined into four BITA scenarios, in which businesses are classified as: "uneasy alliance", "supplier/consumer relationship", "co-dependence/grudging respect", and "together we succeed-split we fail." The model's six domains are instead combined into four BITA scenarios, in which businesses are classified as: "uneasy alliance", "supplier/consumer relationship", "co-dependence/grudging respect" and "together we succeed, split we fail". Nevertheless, these non-scientific terms are at best ambiguous, and despite the fact that they are intended to be descriptive, they simply serve to create confusion in their interpretation. These types of scenarios correspond to the model's maturity stages (Duffy, 2001).

2.4.4.3. Luftman’s Strategic Alignment Maturity Model (SAMM)

Among the most elaborate models in strategic alignment studies, Luftman’s Alignment Model (2004) depicts strategic alignment as a comprehensive, holistic procedure that begins with increasing enablers and decreasing inhibitors. According to Luftman (2004), many businesses have failed to optimise the long-term value of their IT investments due to inhibitors and enablers that should be avoided and enhanced respectively, in order to effectively integrate IT with business operations. Furthermore, according to Luftman et al. (2017; 1999) enablers and inhibitors that should be a concern in strategic alignment are mentioned in table 2.3.

Table 2-3: Enablers and Inhibitors of Strategic Alignment

Enablers	Inhibitors
Senior business leaders continuously support IT development.	Senior business leaders are unsupportive of IT development.
IT is included in the strategy creation process.	IT department does not involve in strategic decision making.
Technology comprehends business operations.	Current technology does not understand the business.
A partnership between business and IT.	There is a dearth of strong relationships between IT and business.
Providing higher priority for IT-related projects.	Providing lower priority for IT-related projects.
IT provides leadership in business operations.	IT management is ineffective due to a lack of leadership.
Effective communication between IT and business.	Miscommunication between business and IT.
IT resources are shared within the organisation.	Complications in financial and human resources.
IT used to gain a competitive advantage in business.	Complexities in IT systems delay competitive advantage.
IT and non-IT departments work closely together.	IT and non-IT departments are misaligned.

Source: Luftman et al. (2017; 1999).

Further, Alghazi et al. (2017) and Luftman et al. (2008) highlighted the importance of maintaining strategic alignment in their studies and stated that minimising the inhibitors in strategic alignment is the only path to success. There are a plethora of models for strategic alignment proposed by scholars in past decades. In previous years researchers aimed to illustrate how aligning IT and business adds value to the organisation (Zahir-Irani et al., 2013). It is critical for organisations to commence strategic alignment only when they have the requisite knowledge (Aversano et al., 2012; Liang et al., 2017) since, insufficient knowledge might result in time and resource loss, and as in last resort, a firm will be strategically misaligned (Zahir-Irani et al., 2013). Strategically misaligned businesses typically perform worse in company operations and have increased inefficiencies in business functions (Majstorovic, 2016).

As many organisations continue their business functions in a doubtful position whether they have achieved strategic alignment or not, Luftman's SAMM has been successful in providing clear guidance on improving strategic alignment in firms. This unique model is a critical expansion to the SAM (Alghazi et al., 2020; Gutierrez et al., 2006), and has achieved widespread acceptance among business-IT scholars and practitioners worldwide (Alghazi et al., 2018; Dulipovici and Robey, 2013). SAMM encompasses all aspects of strategic alignment, and it has been validated through considerable study (Luftman, 2017). To accomplish alignment, business and IT leaders must enhance enablers and reduce impediments (inhibitors). SAMM model support firms in assessing these activities in order to determine where they stand and how to strengthen certain areas in the strategic alignment procedure. SAMM clearly provides guidelines to business executives in future maturity of the strategic alignment (El-Masri et al., 2015). According to Luftman (2000; 2004), SAMM consists of six factors that firms can use to determine the extent of alignment between business-IT. These factors are as follows: "communication, competency, governance, partnership, technology scope and skills". Six factors are briefly explained below.

Communication maturity is defined as "the effective on-going exchange of knowledge and clear understanding between business and IT unite within organisations allowing them to comprehend the strategies, plans, risks, environments and priorities of the organisation and they to achieve them" (Luftman, 2004; 15). In a similar vein, communication is about understanding the level between business departments and IT departments and sharing knowledge between them. Alghazi et al. (2017) utilised the SAMM model in their research and, the authors

concluded that communication is the gateway share ideas and knowledge between different departments in a firm. Also, without having effective communication senior and mid-level managers cannot be aligned together (El-Telbany and Elragal, 2014). Business operations and platforms cannot execute without the help of the IT department in any organisation. Without maintaining effective communication business and IT managers cannot clarify their intentions and issues to each other (Dejarnett et al., 2004). According to Argenti (2016), corporate communication plays a crucial role in assisting organisations achieve strategic alignment. Communication ensures consistency between internal and external messaging. When employees receive consistent messages about the organisation's strategies, it enhances their understanding and ability to represent the firm's objectives to external stakeholders, including customers and suppliers. Therefore, by fostering a clear understanding and commitment to strategic objectives, communication helps organisations align their efforts towards achieving their long-term goals (Argenti, 2016). Further, communication is sharing each other knowledge and understanding with other departments in the organisation. Hence, excellent communication practices develop new concepts and ideas for any given organisation, as both business and IT managers are aligning their knowledge to develop new concepts (Njanka, et al., 2021). Therefore, strategic alignment cannot be a success if there is no proper flexibility and openness in communication practices (Njanka et al., 2021).

Competency maturity is defined by Luftman (2004; 15) as "demonstrating the value of IT in terms of contribution to the businesses in languages that the IT, as well as the business units, understand and accept". Under this maturity level, firms should conduct formal business-IT assessments to understand the gaps they have in the business and to make a necessary improvement (Luftman, 2004). Chatzoglou et al. (2011) asserted that there should be more quality reviews and assessments to improve business-IT alignment. However, Gerow et al. (2014) stated continuous improvement and adding further business and IT metrics will improve competency in a firm. The financial considerations and merits can improve a firm competency measurement (Krotov, 2015). By adding further financial support firms can implement more assessments. In this maturity section, both business and IT values are considered. The IT department's competency is measured by the current IT projects it's undertaking in the firm and also its financial cost and technical support for the business. According to Wu et al. (2015), many firms are unable to identify gaps in their current alignment, as they make temporary

solutions to business and IT alignment, thus, strategic alignment cannot achieve. Business competitiveness depends on the value of the formal business-IT assessments; therefore, senior managers should take serious considerations to improvements (Alghazi et al., 2017).

IT Governance maturity is defined as "ensuring that the appropriate business and IT participants formally discuss and review the priorities and allocation of IT resources" (Luftman, 2004; 18). This term refers to the extent to which the jurisdiction for making IT decisions has been established and distributed among management. To determine whether or not activities are being performed according to the understanding of business strategy. Governance is a comprehensive procedure; therefore, business managers must participate in strategic IT decision making and vice versa for IT managers (Wu et al., 2015). Gerow et al (2014) and Dent (2015) postulated that, when a firm shows an accurate reporting structure and hierarchy, it is a fact that, governance on that firm is strong. Krotov (2015) highlighted, in order to be successful in IT governance both business and IT authorities must maintain stable communication platforms hence, strategic business-IT decisions cannot be concluded. To be successful in IT governance both business and IT must agree on appropriate IT resources and investments (Zahir Irani et al., 2013). Large organisations tend to have a stable reporting structure, however, SMEs are lacking resources and strategic decisions, so they have poor IT governance structures (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015). Moreover, SMEs follow an informal decision structure to maintain flexibility in the business therefore, most small firms are not successful in IT governance (Hussin et al., 2002; Wu et al., 2015). IT governance is one of the parameters to assess whether strategic alignment has been achieved or not on a given firm (Seman and Salim, 2013).

Scope and architecture of the IT maturity examine how a firm's infrastructure, preparedness for change, structural flexibility, and management of emergent technologies are all integrated in order to facilitate corporate development and expansion (Luftman, 2004). Strategic alignment is a sophisticated process, however, there should be flexibility in IT to business operations and functions (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015). Businesses cannot gain their competitive advantage if the firm's infrastructure and structural design are not flexible and available at all times (Chatzoglou et al. (2011). According to Aversano et al. (2012), lack of flexibility in infrastructure and IT solutions can lead to reduced business performance and efficiency. In fact, most organisations cannot achieve adapt to emerging IT solutions because of the sophisticated infrastructure

present in the firm (Reynolds and Yetton, 2015). Further, having supportive and business-friendly IT and infrastructure solutions can help firms to generate more revenue (Seman and Salim, 2013). Also, firms cannot adapt to dynamic customer expectations if their technology and architecture functionality are not flexible thus, losing the customers (Aversano et al., 2012). Therefore, a cannot achieve its strategic alignment if the IT developments and architecture solutions are not integrated into business operations (Krotov, 2015).

Partnership maturity explains the interaction that exists between business and IT management. It takes into account the engagement of information systems in the formulation of business strategies, the level of trust between IT managers and businesses, and how one evaluates the contribution of the other (Luftman, 2004). Strategic alignment maturity means both business and IT should have shared understanding and goals towards each other (Reynolds and Yetton, 2015). To improve the partnership between business and IT departments, both senior managers should have a clear understanding of IT's role in strategic decisions (Hussin et al., 2002; Seman and Salim, 2013). Also, senior business managers must maintain a clear perception about the firm's IT and its value, hence, it will be helpful in supporting each other (Johnson and Lederer, 2010). No partnership can maintain if the senior business and IT managers are not communicating with each other and trust each other (Wu et al., 2015). Moreover, in case of urgent business situations, IT managers should represent business decisions (Hussin et al., 2002).

Human resource skills maturity considers regarding employee training and performance development and also future career prospects. Furthermore, it encompasses a firm's preparedness for IT transformation, its capacity for learning, and its capacity to capitalise on innovative ideas (Luftman, 2004). To achieve strategic alignment firms should have an adequate number of employees to support business operations (Hussin et al., 2002). Employee skills development and training are prioritised in this section. Trained employees are supportive of business vision and policies hence, they have well-trained and given further information about it (Johnson and Lederer, 2010). Employees who are not trained might not be helpful in achieving organisational goals (Wu et al., 2015). Further, well-trained employees are one of the sources where firms can harvest entrepreneurial concepts and knowledge (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015). The above mentioned six dimensions are presented in figure 2.5.

Figure 2-5:Luftman’s Strategic Alignment Maturity Model.

Source: (Luftman, 2004).

There is a large number of alignment models in the literature. Table 2.4 summarises some of the models’ features and criticisms.

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Table 2-4: A summary of strategic alignment models.

Model Name	Context	Descriptions of the Models	Factors of Strategic Alignment	Critics of the Model
Strategic Alignment Model (SAM) of Henderson and Venkatraman (1993)	Based on MIT 90's framework data. Reconceptualised model.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The model is based on two specific approaches: strategic fit and functional integration. b) SAM is highly conceptual but provides specific guidelines for business and IT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Business strategy b) IT strategy c) Organisational infrastructure process d) IT infrastructure and processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) SAM is a theoretical and conceptual model (Avison et al., 2004). b) Does not provide how organisations can measure the alignment (Cooper et al., 2000).
Strategic Alignment Model of Sabherwal and Kirs (1994)	244 large academic institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The model discussed the strategic alignment of organisational critical success factors and how technology capabilities are involved in the whole procedure. b) Further, IT involvement is crucial in achieving organisational success. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Organisational integration b) Environmental uncertainty c) IT management complexities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Authors validated model accuracy via academic organisations only. b) There is only a minimal amount of alignment parameters exist in the model. c) Profile which is specialised for IT capability, and it is empirically rich.
Business-IT strategic integration of Reich and Benbasat (1996)	3 Canadian insurance companies (large).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Alignment between business strategy and IT strategy refers to as social dimension. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The aims and plans of both IT and business leaders are understood by both parties. b) Consistency in long-term IT deployment plans between IT and firm executives. c) There are cross-linkages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The authors used a small, limited data sample plot in their study (life insurance firms). b) Focusing only on the social dimension of the strategic alignment.

Model Name	Context	Descriptions of the Models	Factors of Strategic Alignment	Critics of the Model
			between documented business and IT strategies.	
Strategic Alignment Enablers and Exhibitors of Luftman et al. (1999)	500 global organisations.	a) This model specifically identifies elements that enhance strategic alignment (enablers) and also, identify elements that hinder (inhibitors) strategic alignment. This model only concerns harmony between business vision and IT vision.	a) Strategic alignment enablers and inhibitors. (See chapter 2.4.4.1 for further information)	a) The model lacks a more solid theoretical foundation (Liang, et al., 2017).
Strategic Alignment Maturity Model of Luftman (2004)	500 global organisations.	a) This model was specifically developed to measure strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy.	a) Communication maturity b) Competency maturity c) IT governance maturity d) Scope and architecture of the IT maturity e) Partnership maturity f) Skills maturity	a) The model lacks a more solid theoretical foundation (Liang, et al., 2017).
Business-IT alignment model of Hussin et al. (2002)	256 UK food manufacturing SMEs.	a) Alignment of business and IT strategies on a strategic level. The model is very specific about each strategy's content.	a) The dedication of the chief executive to IT development b) Sophistication in technology c) External IT expertise.	a) The model does not have enough factors which are supportive of strategic alignment. b) The model does not count functional integration and organisational factors which are linked to IT alignment.

Model Name	Context	Descriptions of the Models	Factors of Strategic Alignment	Critics of the Model
Six types of IT-Business Strategic Alignment of Gerow et al. (2015)	140 CIO's globally.	a) A meta-analysis of 6 forms of strategic alignment and the influence of these alignments on organisation performance was conducted.	a) Alignment of intellectual and operational with the support of three domains - internal, external, cross-domain. b) Financial performance, efficiency, and customer satisfaction are all important.	a) The model is based on static perspective only. b) It was found that just less research focused on operational alignment.
Strategic Alignment of Luftman et al. (2017)	1000 global organisations (Large firms).	a) Strategic alignment is focused on the linkages that exist among the six components that help to improve IT business integration.	a) Communications between IT and business team b) Importance of value analytics c) Supportive governance practices d) Type of partnership e) Improvement of IT training and skills f) The extent of technology initiatives.	a) The model needs further evidence to support its validity.
Model of Change for Business-IT Alignment of Kawtar et al. (2019)	Moroccan SMEs and large firms.	a) Business-IT alignment is working in harmony. Therefore, change is required to maintain the alignment of business and IT. A meta-model component was included.	a) Stakeholders b) Drivers which can cause change c) Change management d) Specific goals e) How to change impact on a firm.	a) Lacks empirical evidence (Al-Surmi et al., 2020). b) Can model supportive for different business industries or not.
The Triadic Strategic Alignment Model of Al-Surmi et al. (2020)	a) Total 350 Yemen firms selected (large and SMEs). b) Industries include: Telecom,	a) Concerns of triadic strategic alignment (strategic orientation, marketing strategies and IT strategic orientation). How these 3 components support strategic alignment and firm performance.	a) Use contingency theory and configuration theory to investigate triadic strategic alignment. Also, simultaneously, the model considers firms' strategic position.	a) The model requires further data to validate implementation further.

Model Name	Context	Descriptions of the Models	Factors of Strategic Alignment	Critics of the Model
	banks, manufacturing, property, restaurants.			
Model of IT-Business Alignment of Afandi (2020)	a) Saudi Arabian SMEs (retail, food manufacturing, electronic shops, food selling and restaurant chains etc)	a) 3 components were considered (IT flexibility, IT capability, IT-business alignment) to evaluate alignment.	a) IT Flexibility b) IT Capabilities c) Business Industry	a) The model used only Saudi firms to evaluate strategic alignment.
Strategic Alignment of Information Technology of Sharma and Behl (2020)	a) Indian 42 public firms b) Indian 60 private firms	a) To comprehend how IT capability (IT connectivity, infrastructure and human resources) impact strategic alignment in Indian firms.	a) A convenience sampling approach was considered to collect data. An online questionnaire was used.	a) Data validity issues. b) Bias, more data on private Indian firms than public. c) Further data is required to validate the model comprehensively.

2.4.4.4. Selected Model for Assessing Strategic Alignment and Justifications

The SAMM has been examined multiple times and determined to be reliable in recent studies (Alghazi et al., 2017; Alghazi et al., 2020). Luftman conducted an extensive research study in which they enlisted the participation of larger corporations (over 1000 global companies) and they discovered that the SAMM is a balanced model and one of the most encouraging tools in the strategic alignment studies in terms of authenticity (Luftman et al., 2017). SAMM was used to assess the strategic alignment development of Chinese organisations in Chen (2010), whereas Alghazi et al. (2020) used SAMM to perform a research study to determine the maturity of strategic alignment in the Saudi Arabian public sector firms.

Many studies executed SAMM in quantitative studies (use of survey) but use in qualitative studies are lacking (Alghazi et al., 2017). Thus, further research is called upon the use of SAMM in qualitative research studies (Alghazi et al., 2020). Thus, this research employs SAMM in developing the conceptual framework for this research.

While there are numerous benefits that businesses may get as a result of strategic alignment, numerous studies continue to demonstrate that many organisations are continuing to struggle to establish strategic alignment (Gbangou and Rusu, 2016; El-Mekawy et al., 2015). Luftman's SAMM has been empirically validated in previous years, thus this research employs SAMM to measure the case study firm's current strategic alignment. Since, SAMM has been investigated and empirically validated by (Luftman et al., 2017; Chumo, 2016; Khanfar and Zualkernan, 2010; Smits et al., 2009; Sledgianowski et al., 2006) as a trustworthy realistic tool to improve strategic alignment. Not only that, but Gutierrez et al. (2009) also highlighted that SAMM is a well-recognised model globally therefore, it is a valid tool in measuring alignment. Therefore, SAMM's six components will be employed in this research to assess the case study firm's current strategic alignment.

2.4.5. Factors Determining Successful Strategic Alignment

The extensive studies on alignment have resulted in the development of a complete list of criteria that influence strategic alignment. Chan and Reich (2007) have developed extensive findings on

strategic alignment thus, this research has categorised these factors into two major sections: foreground factors and background factors. Table 2-5 summarises critical success factors for achieving strategic alignment.

Table 2-5: Factors determining successful strategic alignment

Factors	Sources
Cross Department Communication and Coordination	Reich and Benbasat (2000); Luftman (2004); Luftman et al. (1999); Alghazi et al. (2017); El-Telbany and Elragal (2014); Njanka et al. (2021)
Competency	Luftman (2004); Chatzoglou et al. (2011); Gerow et al. (2014); Krotov (2015); Wu et al. (2015); Alghazi et al. (2017)
IT Governance	Luftman (2004); Wu et al. (2015); Gerow et al. (2014); Dent (2015); Krotov (2015); Zahir-Irani et al. (2013); Alaceva and Rusu (2015); Seman and Salim (2013)
Scope and Architecture of the IT	Luftman (2004); Alceva and Rusu (2015); Chatzoglou et al. (2011); Aversano et al. (2012); Reynolds and Yetton (2015); Seman and Salim (2013); Krotov (2015)
Partnership	Luftman (2004); Reynolds and Yetton (2015); Hussin et al. (2002); Johnson and Lederer (2010); Wu et al. (2015)
Skills	Luftman (2004); Hussin et al. (2002); Johnson and Lederer (2010); Wu et al. (2015); Alaceva and Rusu (2015)
Senior Management Knowledge and Commitment	Reich and Benbasat (2000); Som and Diekmann (2017); Tallon and Kraemer (2003); Kitsios and Kamariotou (2019); Njanka et al. (2021); Henriques et al. (2019)
Supportive Organisation Culture	Malurent and Avison (2015); Lundberg (1988); Sardana et al. (2016); Sha et al. (2020); McAdam et al. (2019); Utami et al. (2020); Liu et al. (2010)

It was noted in previous studies that, strategic alignment is a process of continuous improvements to business strategy and IT strategy thus, need comprehensive latest knowledge of the factors that could impact the process (Padukkage et al., 2014; Papadopoulos et al., 2020; Chan et al., 2019). One of the key authors in alignment, Luftman et al. (1999) identified enablers and inhibitors factors of strategic alignment which happened to be the practical version of the

SAM model. Luftman's research helped many strategic alignment researchers around the globe, and partnership between business managers and IT managers is a key enabler in alignment. Whilst lack of working relationship between IT and business happened to be the key inhibitor in alignment.

Some scholars highlighted that few factors happened to be most vital in alignment studies, for instance, senior management knowledge (Cataldo and McQueen, 2015; Reich and Benbasat, 2000), IT flexibility (Wetering et al., 2017; Tallon and Pinsonneault, 2011), environmental uncertainty (Tallon and Pinsonneault, 2011; Yayla and Hu, 2012; Baker et al., 2011), investments (Wetering et al., 2017; Loukis et al., 2009). However strategic alignment varies between large firms and SMEs (Street et al., 2017) thus, further research needs in for SMEs. For instance, Afandi (2020) highlighted that strategic alignment in SMEs varies industry-wise. This research believes six dimensions of SAMM is critical when achieving strategic alignment in case company (elaborated in chapter 2.4.4.3).

2.4.5.1. Cross department communication and coordination

It was noted in the literature that good communication strategies assist firms in enhancing strategic positioning thus strategic alignment can be achieved (Cornelissen, 2017; Bruhn et al., 2016). Strategic communication was defined by Volk and Zerfass (2018) and stated that it is the only positive factor that can increase the awareness of strategic alignment and also assist business users and IT users to achieve strategic alignment. Falkheimer et al. (2017) noted in their study that business managers and IT managers must communicate on a regular basis; thus increasing the effectiveness in strategic positioning and alignment in a firm. Some recent scholars have explicitly stated that communication must be aligned with a firm's overall strategic goals and by doing so, senior business and IT managers can involve in the strategic alignment procedure (Slim et al., 2021; Heroux and Fortin, 2018; Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Alghazi et al., 2020). Since communication between departments always evaluate business goals, mission, values and future ambitions in a company; therefore, not only business and IT departments but other departments' coordination can also improve (Rezaei et al., 2018; Cornelissen, 2017).

According to Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017), due to a lack of communication between business and IT departments, many African firms cannot achieve their business targets. Alaceva and Rusu

(2015) found that large Swedish firms struggled to maintain and improve communication, as firms cannot align their business strategy and IT strategy. Wang and Rusu (2018) found in their research that due to lack of communication most Chinese SMEs cannot maintain a partnership with IT managers as they are defensive in communication. Harmonised communication practices increased organizational performance and thus increased excellent customer service in Colombian SMEs (Cataldo and McQueen, 2015). However, Volk and Zerfass (2018) and Falkheimer et al. (2016) stated that most global organisations believe in financial support to strategic alignment although they are not maintaining trustworthy and friendly communication standards therefore, they spend further resources in achieving strategic alignment.

Indeed, frequent communication practices between the business department and IT department enable them to have a shared understanding of firm issues (Oroszo et al., 2015; Teeratansirikool et al., 2013). Further having a higher understanding between business and IT managers can enable them to evaluate business and IT plans formally. According to Invernizzi and Romenti (2015) senior IT users are not maintaining sustainable communication practices with senior business users, therefore IT users are not aware of current business expectations and issues. However, Street et al. (2017) highlighted that SMEs follow simple business structures therefore they are capable of flexible communication standards and support to each other. Cross department communication and partnership in an organisation can enhance organisational performance and employee motivation (Sharma and Behl, 2020). However, a higher partnership between business managers and IT managers effectively engaged with strategic issues in a firm therefore, strategic alignment can achieve effectively (Luftman et al., 1999).

2.4.5.2. Senior management knowledge and commitment

Senior management knowledge is vital in strategic alignment since senior executives make the final strategic decisions for the business. Reich and Benbasat (2000) highlighted that shared knowledge between business and IT executives lead to having better communication between business and IT executives. When a firm has successful IT project history, this leads to good connections in planning between business and IT (Som and Diekmann, 2017; Tallon and Kraemer, 2003). Senior management knowledge should be considered by assessing the current IT experience business managers have and the amount of business experience that IT managers have (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Njanka et al., 2021). When senior managers of business

and IT maintain a shared mutual understanding about the firm business, this can enhance organisational productivity and efficiency (Henriques et al., 2019). Gomez (2015) also stress that having experienced senior managers of business and IT is the winning key in strategic alignment. Baker et al. (2011) highlighted that senior business and IT executives must maintain proper communication practices when they make any changes to current strategic business-IT plans. In order to maintain proper communication between business and IT departments, first, senior managers should have good knowledge about the importance of communication and how it helps to resolve problems strategic alignment (Katsikogiannis et al., 2018; Garg and Goyal, 2012; Spinelli et al., 2013).

Rahimi et al. (2016) stress that though knowledge is important in strategic alignment, however, business and IT managers' communication is more important than their knowledge. Good communication practices between business and IT executives are always helpful in discussing strategic issues and enhancing opportunities for the business (Gerow et al., 2015). Mitropoulos (2021) argued that communication between business and IT managers is one of the key success factors in strategic alignment.

A recent study highlighted that due to senior managers' higher attitude towards their individual decisions; they are not keen on sharing their knowledge with other departments thus, leading to strategic misalignment (Sautter and Clar, 2017). Senior managers' knowledge and understanding can improve, if they are involved in business-IT operational meetings, participating in mandatory business and IT training and also, when speaking to sales and retail clients when they share important information which can be beneficial in growing their current knowledge (Heracleous and Werres, 2015; Mitropoulos, 2021; Ilmudeen et al., 2019). In retail firms, lower-level employees are the first face to customers and they understand customer expectations better than senior managers (Lerner, 2015). Therefore, senior managers' knowledge can improve if they actively speak to ground level staff, as they are the front face to customers' expectations and represent the whole firm. Different business industries have different knowledge about their business and IT; therefore, two different industries' senior management knowledge cannot be the same Al-Surmi et al. (2020) thus, need further research in different industries.

2.4.5.3. Supportive organisation culture

In past, organisational culture was defined as "is shared by some significant portion of members and is largely taken for granted by them or it is a shared, common frame of reference (Lundberg, 1988; p. 39). Recent studies have defined organizational culture as to what extent an organisation can implement change in management and how can things get into work (Sha et al., 2020). However, Sardana et al. (2016) state that organisational culture can be considered as the vehicle which carries organisational meanings and values. According to Malaurent and Avison (2015), organisational culture can enhance new business concepts if the new change is productive.

Sha et al. (2020) and McAdam et al. (2019) identified that organisational culture can have a major impact on financial performance. Whereas some scholars (King and Lawley, 2016; Sinding and Waldstorm, 2014) found that organisational culture does not relate to financial performance. However, supportive organisational culture always enhances overall organisational performance (Kaul, 2019). Supportive organisational culture increases customer trust and their satisfaction towards the firm (Zhou et al., 2018). Retail firms employ customer friendly organisational culture; thus improving organisational performance and decision-making skills (Raja and Lin, 2018). Also, Samaraweera et al. (2018) found in their research that not only supportive culture but open organisational culture also improves employee motivation thus assisting firms in Sri Lanka in achieving organisational goals and strategic alignment. Kaul (2019) strongly believes that supportive organisational culture can be considered as one of the critical success factors in achieving strategic alignment. Some recent scholars stated that organizational culture can be referred to as organizational politics which ultimately decide the final procedure of how organisation decisions should execute (Sha et al., 2020; Utami et al., 2020). Nevertheless, Adeola and Ezenwafor (2016) revealed that organizational culture can have a major impact when the firm undergoes any merger or acquisition procedures. This is because business strategy and IT strategy can have a major amendment which leads to change in firm culture. Therefore achieving strategic alignment is difficult with a stringent organisational culture and may not support sustaining competitive advantage thus achieving excellent customer service is also difficult (Amar and Romdhane, 2019; Liang et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2010).

2.4.5.4. Distribution of organisational resources

It was noted in the literature that many organisations struggle to maintain their business products and services due to resource constraints (Contador et al., 2021; Aydin and Badurdeen, 2019). Most organisations in supply chain and retail industries suffered from financial resources; therefore, they struggle to maintain alignment (Srivastava et al., 2016). According to Aranda and Arellano (2010), large organisations generally maintain substantial resource levels compared to SMEs. Therefore, every SMEs business-owners main concern is how to sustain organisational resources such as financial, physical and human resources (Panda and Rath, 2018; Street et al., 2017). Recent studies have concluded that organisational resources happened to be one of the critical success factors in achieving strategic alignment (Gligor et al., 2020; Sha et al., 2020; Denning, 2018). According to Contador et al. (2021), organisational supply chain systems cannot maintain without having substantial resources such as financial and human resources. Rubin (2015) states that not only SMEs but large organisations also suffered from achieving strategic alignment due to resource constraints from IT departments. According to Ramrathan and Sibanda (2015) and Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017), SMEs in the African regions cannot maintain strategic alignment due to many reasons. First, most African countries' economies are poor and corrupt due to unethical business practices. Secondly, African SMEs cannot maintain IT resources and financial resources due to poor economic structure in their nations thus strategic alignment is a continuous challenge.

There are various debates in the literature regarding how organisational resources impact strategic alignment. Panda (2021) argued financial resources can be considered as the most essential resource category when firms attempt to achieve strategic alignment. Cirjevskis (2017) argued that though strategic financial resources are prioritised, however, human resources must be fulfilled at all times in order to have a harmonious strategic alignment in Indian firms. Yuliansyah and Jermias (2018) believe that retail firms must always have knowledge gaining resources in order to maintain strategic alignment. Harchekar (2018) found in his research that approval of financial resources is the hardest strategic decision for all firms thus, senior managers are not keen on approving those.

However, some studies have encouraged good strategic practices for firms. Luftman et al. (2017) highlighted that firms must maintain regular formal business and IT assessments in order to

understand organisational requirements. Formal assessments in business and IT assist managers in identifying gaps in strategic alignment (Luftman et al., 2008). A study conducted by Sha et al. (2020) in healthcare institution found that due to a lack of strategic support and resources, alignment between business priorities and IT priorities are difficult to maintain. Strategic resources can hold some cost for any organisation; however, no organisation can achieve strategic alignment without having strategic resources (Panda, 2021; Contador et al., 2021).

2.4.5.5. Employee training and development

It is a fact and crucial to highlight that employees are the most valuable asset for an organisation (Luftman, 2015; Alagaraja and Shuck, 2015; Harrison, 1998). According to Luftman (2015) employees' knowledge and their engagement towards strategic alignment is crucial, since employees execute strategies in practice. Therefore, employees' individual knowledge about strategic alignment and how they should support organisational strategies are important for strategic alignment to be successful (Taneja et al., 2015). Well-trained employees can be considered as the greatest strategic resource for an organisation since it positively impacts organisational performance (Hyder and Lussier, 2016; Messeni et al., 2018). Similarly, Li et al. (2016) also stated that an experienced workforce is directly related to organisational overall performance; and further, they encouraged and motivate new employees to work efficiently in an organisation.

There are some debates regarding how employee training can impact on firm's strategic alignment. According to some scholars, large organisations invest so vastly in resources to improve the efficiency and knowledge of employees through their regular training (Gagnon and Michael, 2003; Fabi et al., 2009; Li et al., 2016). However, SME owners recruit more experienced employees to their firms as they don't require thorough training in their work (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2020; Gama et al., 2019). However, employees are not effective in their positions without having thorough training; and their errors could cost the firm lose money and reputation (Alagaraja, 2013). It was noted in recent literature firms who promote self-learning employee training are lower on organisational performance. However, most SMEs cannot afford digital platforms to train and develop their employees; they perform manual face to face training as it is cheaper and more convenient to comprehend work knowledge (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2021). Moreover, some recent literature revealed that each and every employee

can be different and diversified in their nature thus their learning capabilities can also be varied too (Kraus et al., 2019). Excellent customer service is crucial for retail industry therefore employees should be well trained (Ernst and Young, 2012). Retail firms are survived by their employees' performance and efficiency therefore organisations cannot achieve strategic alignment without training them comprehensively (Hedvall et al., 2019). Also, senior managers should be open and patient during their employees' learning cycles and approve required organisational resources for completing training sessions (Schwartz and Porath, 2014).

2.4.6. Challenges for Ensuring Successful Strategic Alignment

Previous studies highlighted many challenges SMEs face during the strategic alignment process. Some of the key challenges identified in the literature include the lack of support from senior management, lack of trust between business managers and IT departments, uncooperative organisational culture and organisational policies that are unresponsive towards organisational performance.

2.4.6.1. Lack of senior manager support

Both senior business and IT management must have an extensive understanding about each other before developing a commitment to strategic alignment. Positive collaboration between business and IT executives is the key to success in strategic alignment (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015). Luftman et al. (1999) postulated that there are six enablers that promote strategic alignment in an organisation and senior management support is one of the six enablers. Luftmans further described that senior management attitude towards business and IT issues and how they committed to solving them is a debatable question. Teo and Ang (1999) found three critical success factors in their study, which influence strategic alignment in a firm. They are senior managers' continuous commitment to strategic IT and business, the level of knowledge in business managers about IS and whether business managers are confident and trust IT managers' decisions. Some literature stated that there are important challenges that need to be resolved urgently, if a firm wishes to achieve strategic alignment such as, lack of senior managers support to business-IT decisions, no rewards and recognition to employees, lack of teamwork and less focus put on financial requirements (Mitropoulos, 2021; Skyrme and Amindo, 1997).

According to Mitropoulos (2021) and Coltman et al. (2015) many firms are unable to achieve strategic alignment because senior executives consider IT solutions as a tool, not a team member or priority in the process. Therefore, senior managers are not well committed to supporting business-IT issues firms face daily. Katsikogiannis et al. (2018) argued that executive officers' individual perceptions and their understanding level about business are other reasons firms receive a lack of commitment from senior officers in the organisation. The author argued that they compared the current business-IT environments based on their previous work environments which are completely different to current. According to Lederer and Mendelow (1989), authors recorded 20 in-depth semi-structured interviews with chief executives in large firms and they found that four issues make strategic alignment difficult. They are unclear business objectives, not maintaining sustainable communication, IT department not attending strategic meetings and business-IT expectations are hard to achieve.

Some senior managers are not keen on listening to mid-level management opinions as they believe it lowers their management power (Ning and Tanriverdi, 2017; Venkatesh et al., 2003). Since mid-level managers are the front face to customers, they are aware of the current business-IT alignment issues and how they impact meeting customer demands on time. Kim and Kaikanhaili (2009) and Mitropoulos (2012) highlighted that senior manager attitude towards IS/IT can impact directly on IT alignment implementation. Senior managers' commitment depends on whether they have worked in mid-level management prior to being promoted to senior managers. Parmenter (2015) and Rathod et al. (2019) asserts that when senior managers have no practical knowledge about business operations, their commitment varies, and their business-IT decisions are not suitable for the industry where the firm is operating.

2.4.6.2. Lack of trust between business managers and IT department

According to Feeny et al. (1992), understanding between business and IT departments is the fuel in the strategic alignment process and they are the main parties involved in the strategic alignment. Past studies in alignment, have argued that the importance of formal coordination between business managers and IT managers; directly impacts organisational performance and development (Ullah and Lai, 2013; Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016). However, the coordination depends on several factors such as senior managers' attitudes towards other colleagues and the

flexibility in the organisational decision-making hierarchy (Kotusev, 2020; El-Telbany and Elragal, 2014).

Rathod et al. (2019) and Mitropoulos (2021) both highlighted in their studies that it is crucial that all departments in an organisation must maintain good communication practices, thus, it is the only way to share their knowledge and issues. El-Telbany and Elragal (2014: 36) conducted a study identifying factors on strategic misalignment and highlighted five main constructs namely, "Business-IT relationship type, Business-IT communication, Business-IT engagement, IT projects and Business-IT misalignment". Authors further highlighted that, when business vision is not properly comprehended and communicated across IT and other departments, coordination is hard to achieve. Business and IT coordination always depend on good communication practices (Gbangou and Rusu, 2016). When senior managers of business and IT do not maintain effective communication, both departments cannot find the right equilibrium in their strategic decisions this, coordination is unsuccessful (Rahimi et al., 2016). Pelletier and Cloutier (2019) also highlighted that less communication between business and IT managers' leads to less coordination between them.

Senior business managers trust their own decision making and judgements therefore, they are in a perception not trusting IT managers' decision-making skills (Kotusev, 2020; Cataldo and McQuen, 2015; Bergeron et al., 2004). Therefore, maintaining coordination is difficult between business and IT. Sophisticated strategies of business and IT can create misalignment between business and IT (Cataldo et al., 2012; Spinelli et al., 2013). Similarly, Alghazi et al. (2020) and Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017) also argued that many firms spend lots of investment on making strategic decisions without understanding their business goals and parameters. Hence, business and IT strategies cannot maintain a close relationship which is healthy for business performance. Luftman et al. (1999) also highlighted six inhibitors of alignment and one of them is business and IT lacks a supportive relationship.

2.4.6.3. Uncooperative organisational culture

Previous studies revealed that the "culture gap", which lives between the IT department and business department, is one of the negative factors which leads to failure in strategic alignment (Ward and Peppard, 2002; Almajali and Dehalin, 2011). Silvius et al. (2009) have highlighted

that culture can be divided into two sub-sections namely, organisational culture and the national culture. The authors further argued that national culture directly impacts on strategic alignment process, and it is crucial. Indeed, organisational culture decides how employees in a firm should work and corporate with each other (Silvius et al., 2009). Resistance to change means there is "no trust" in the current ways; hence, individuals do not wish to adapt (Bouckenooghe, 2010). In general, SMEs always work with flexible and informal work environments to promote their business products and services to customers much more quickly (Abbas et al., 2019). Changes always come with risk factors to any business; therefore, SME owner-manager and employees will not encourage to change themselves as it can alter their current business progress (Hyder and Lussier, 2016). According to Lin et al. (1993) authors highlighted that the only way a firm can be influenced by new IT or business solutions is by adjusting the current firm culture into new work surroundings.

Organisational change can be described as an empirically verified of alterations in the shape, quality, or condition of an entity through time that can be traced back to its inception (Van de Ven and Poole, 1995). The main reason organisations encourage change is to adapt to the new environment or new implementation in business and IT (Leena and Barry, 2000; Keck and Tushman, 1993). Del Val and Fuentes (2003) defined resistance as the process which delays a set of actions or implementation. Whereas others described resistance as a process that fosters learning capacity between organisational individuals (Msweli-Mbanga and Potwana, 2006).

Moreover, employees show resistance to change when organisations introduce change (Lines, 2005). Therefore, there is a possibility that changes in organizational strategies and structure can bring negative momentum to the employees. Not only employees, changes in organisational strategies and structure can also bring firms negative performance, leading to lower revenue (Hollnagel, 2012). New developments and alignments in IT can bring massive changes to current business performance and efficiency (Ward and Peppard, 2002; Bovey and Hede, 2001); hence, firms refuse to accept new IT developments and strategies. Compared to large firms, SMEs tend to show more resistance when adapting to new cultures and practices since they prefer flexibility and informal strategies (Hyder and Lussier, 2016). However, organisations will be obsolete if they do not accept new IS developments and business standards as globalisation create many challenges for them (Baker et al., 2011).

MacDonald and McGill (2013) highlighted in their research that positive behaviour support reduces the level of resistance towards individuals. The authors further assert that employees generate a positive, supportive attitude towards the new environment and culture when organisations provide further seminars and training. Lowe et al. (2007) highlighted that employees develop positive confidence in new processes and procedures at work when exposed to in-depth new information. Sailor et al. (2000) postulated that IT is a great tool when training staff at work, and as there is a different acceptance level in each staff member, they need to have enough time to acquire new knowledge and information. Chinomona (2013) postulated that employee skills training and business performance have a positive relationship, whereas much-trained staff members are willing to accept new challenges. Abbas et al. (2019) state that firm and employee performance can only be developed by providing comprehensive training to staff. Well trained employees and managers are well aware of the business processes and procedures hence, they show supportive behaviour and less resistance towards firm transformation processes (Hyder and Lussier, 2016).

2.4.6.4. Organisational policies being unsupportive towards organisational performance

Rapid decision making is required in order to achieve the competitive advantage of a given firm (Majstorovic, 2016). According to Bruce (1998), strategic alignment is making effective business and IT decisions hence, firms can sustain their business performance. Senior management decides the decision-making procedure of any given firm (Hussin et al., 2002). According to Sabherwal and Chan (2001), strategic alignment can be defined as concluding business and IT strategic decisions in order to sustain competitive advantage and expand business opportunities. In other words, competitive advantage refers to fulfilling customer expectations better than the competitors. Thus, rapid decision making is essential.

Wang (2014) highlighted that one of the factors hindering achieving strategic alignment is a delay in strategic decision making. According to Gbangou and Rusu (2016) and Rahimi et al. (2016), senior managers make slow decision making due to two main reasons, namely, sophistication in organisational and management hierarchy and their level of understanding regarding strategic decisions. This research is focused on SMEs' strategic alignment; Cataldo and McQueen (2015) argued in their study that, employing large firms' strategies and policies into

SMEs are not appropriate thus, it only reduces its decision-making efficiency. Cataldo et al. (2012) highlighted that senior leaders have not decided their business and IT goals prior to making strategic decisions therefore, strategic decisions are not matching for SMEs' organisational performance. Large firms' policies and procedures are not flexible enough to support SMEs therefore, business owners should employ policies that improve business flexibility (Wang and Rusu, 2018; Luftman et al., 2017; Hussin et al., 2002). Moreover, firms cannot make rapid decisions if there are no adequate employees (Hussin et al., 2002).

2.4.7. Strategic Alignment and Organisational Performance

This area assesses how strategic alignment supports organisational performance. Due to the rising strategic significance of IT investment in many businesses, most subsequent research has concentrated on integrating IT strategy with business strategy and the resulting performance benefits (Ilmudan et al., 2019; Luftman et al., 2017; Aboobcker and Bao, 2018). There are various rewards organisations can achieve as a result of strategic alignment. Some research studies have analysed the relationships between strategic alignment and business-IT rewards (Ilmudeen et al., 2019). Whilst, some scholars have concluded that strategic alignment has a direct connection to organisational competitive advantage (Kane et al., 2015; Van Der Zee et al., 1999), organisational performance (Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2016), and value of IT and business (Kane et al., 2015).

The understanding between business strategy and IT strategy was highlighted as a strategic fit or harmony in previous studies and was called intellectual alignment (Street et al., 2017; Gerow et al., 2015). According to Jia et al. (2018) and Yayla and Hu (2012) authors employed this conceptualization to examine the integration between business and IT strategy in firms and their findings were promising. Preston and Karahanna (2009) discovered that having a common understanding of the role of IT in the business had an impact on IT alignment. Bradley et al. (2012) demonstrated that strategic alignment has a favourable and direct conclusion on organisation agility. Wang et al. (2016), as well as Kane et al. (2015), have discovered that higher strategic alignment leads to improved corporate profitability.

Many previous studies focused on strategic alignment in firm-level perspective highlighted there is a significant impact on business performance, however, some argued that there is no impact on

business performance (Luftman et al., 2017; Gerow et al., 2015; Yayla and Hu, 2012; Sabherwal and Chan, 2001). Whereas studies that focused on process level perspective highlighted that there is inconsistency in results regarding alignment and organisational performance. For example, a research study by Tallon and Pinsonneault (2011) highlighted there is no positive impact on process level strategic alignment on organisational performance, however, surprisingly, Tallon's (2007) research highlighted that there is a positive impact for the organisational performance through process level alignment.

Previous studies agreed that financial resources are working as a middle person in strategic alignment in order to increase organisational performance (Kane et al., 2015; Sabherwal and Kirs, 1994). This was agreed by (Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Kraatz and Zajac, 2001) where an appropriate financial budget is a key to improved strategic alignment and corporation performance. Sabherwal and Chan (2001) highlighted that organisational performance and strategic alignment has a direct relationship where separation is impossible. Cataldo et al. (2012) and Reksoatmodjo et al. (2012) discovered that organisations with higher degrees of strategic alignment outperform those with lower levels of alignment in their investigation of the impact of strategic alignment on the performance of a small firm.

To recapitulate, a considerable amount of research has been conducted to determine the relationship between strategy alignment and organisation performance. Indeed, literature highlighted that some studies produced positive outcomes (Kawtar et al., 2019; Kane et al., 2015), whereas others were inconclusive (Imgharene et al., 2018). However, these contradictory findings regarding the relationship between strategic alignment and organisational performance warrant additional investigation in a different research paradigm.

2.5. Knowledge Gaps

Many previous studies were conducted to explore the factor of strategic alignment in the context of large organisations (e.g., Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Gbangou and Rusu, 2016; Baker and Niederman, 2014); however only a few studies have focused on identifying the factors of strategic alignment for SMEs (Henriques et al., 2019; Street et al., 2017). Gerow et al. (2015) highlighted six dimensions that need to be considered to achieve strategic alignment. They include intellectual alignment, operational alignment, and other four types of cross-domain alignments.

Alaceva and Rusu (2015) highlighted that many Swedish large organisations were unable to achieve strategic alignment due to the lack of sufficient knowledge regarding the process of strategic alignment. They also argued that organisations cannot achieve strategic alignment without having higher commitments and support from senior leadership and open communication within the organisation. Kotusev (2020) outlined organisations should follow five phases when achieving strategic alignment, namely positioning, focusing, prioritizing, assessing, and implementing. In terms of SMEs, Street et al. (2017) carried their research on identifying theoretical foundations in strategic alignment. The authors revealed that SMEs are unique compared to large organisations, thus they should consider organisational size and resources, strategic planning, and leadership for achieving strategic alignment. Sharma and Behl (2020) and Majstorovic (2016) highlighted that financial commitment and resource availability are some of the common factors required to achieve strategic alignment. Whilst SMEs tend to be flexible and open-minded in their business nature (Pelletier and Cloutier, 2019), large organisations are more structured due to their rigid organisational policies and strategies (Alghazi et al., 2020; Rahimi et al., 2016). Afandi (2020) noted that strategic alignment in SMEs is one of the emerging topics and indicated that SMEs' organisational characteristics and industry matters when achieving strategic alignment. Therefore, it is important to understand the factors that are specific to the industry an organisation operates in for achieving strategic alignment. A review of the literature indicated that no prior study modelled the factors of strategic alignment in the context of Forex retail SMEs, therefore, there is a substantial knowledge gap in the literature.

Firms face many unanticipated challenges for achieving strategic alignment (Chedrawi and Howayeck, 2019). Particularly for SMEs, as they tend to be dynamic in their business functions, their business challenges can be unprecedented. Many studies have focused on challenges larger organisations face during strategic alignment procedure; some challenges are common for both SMEs and larger firms such as, senior management support (Teo and Ang, 1999), lack of financial support (Gligor et al., 2020) and rigid organisational culture (Abbas et al., 2019). Similarly, Sabherwal et al. (2019) and Bayrak (2018) stated that the lack of sufficient IT investments is a common challenge for both SMEs and larger corporations. Ilmudeen and Malik (2016) and Mitropoulos (2021) both highlighted that trust between business managers and IT

managers are essential for organisations to achieve strategic alignment. Moreover, Cataldo et al. (2012) and Spinelli et al. (2013) highlighted that, due to a lack of trust between business departments and IT departments, SMEs cannot attain strategic alignment. McAdam et al. (2019), Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017) and Utami et al. (2020) noted that due to a lack of necessary intellectual resources, SMEs struggle to achieve strategic alignment. Although the challenges faced by both SMEs and larger organisations for achieving strategic alignment is fairly well-understood, the challenges faced by Forex SMEs, in particular, is not previously reported in the literature. Therefore, there exists a knowledge gap in the literature that this research seeks to fill.

Previous studies noted that achieving strategic alignment is one of the time consuming and complex organisational tasks for every organisation (Wang, 2014; Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2017; Alghazi et al., 2017). According to Chan et al. (2019), strategic alignment is a process of continuous improvement in business and IT strategies and doing so requires organisational agility in adapting new changes. Wang and Rusu (2018) conducted their research on Chinese SMEs and concluded that business owners do not encourage open-end communication practices and flexible IT architecture SMEs, thus achieving strategic alignment is difficult. A review of the literature noted that no prior research explored the critical success factors for achieving harmonious alignment of business and IT strategies in Forex SMEs, therefore, this research seeks to fill this knowledge gap to be able to provide effective strategic recommendations to Forex SMEs.

2.6. Research Conceptual Framework

After extensively reviewing the existing literature, a conceptual framework is developed in this section of the chapter. The framework presented (Figure 2.6) highlights the factors of strategic alignment along with the expected outcomes of successful strategic alignment for SMEs.

Figure 2-6: Framework for strategic alignment of SMEs.

Source: The Author.

The above framework is developed by incorporating Luftman's (2004) strategic alignment maturity model as well as the other factors of strategic alignment identified in the literature. According to Luftman (2004), for achieving harmonious strategic alignment, having maturity in communication, competency, IT governance, scope and architecture of the IT, partnership and skills is essential. Communication maturity assist firms to have a better understanding of the requirements of all business and IT departments (Njanka et al., 2021; Luftman, 2004; Reich and Benbasaat, 1996), competency maturity ensures organisations have formal business and IT assessments in order to identify gaps in strategies and make improvements (Alghazi et al., 2017; Luftman, 2004; Gerow et al., 2015), IT governance maturity ensure firms have access to necessary IT resources and business and IT participants formally engaged with alignment tasks (Wu et al., 2015; Luftman, 2004; Kawtar et al., 2019), scope and architecture of the IT maturity focuses on improving technology solutions and structural flexibility so business strategy can achieve its goals (Semana and Salim, 2004; Luftman, 2004; Luftman et al., 2017), business and IT

managers partnership is essential in achieving strategic alignment (Al-Surmi et al., 2020; Reynolds and Yeton, 2015; Luftman, 2004), and skills maturity concerns about employees' training and their developments (Wu et al., 2015; Sharman and Behl, 2020; Luftman, 2004). Moreover, literature has also highlighted that senior management knowledge and commitment (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Njanka et al., 2021; Henriques et al., 2019) and supportive organisation culture (Malaurent and Avison, 2015; Sardana et al., 2016; Sha et al., 2020) also play important roles in achieving strategic alignment.

The literature also noted that by achieving harmonious strategic alignment, firms can achieve improved organisational performance (Bakotic, 2016; Maduenyi et al., 2015), increased profitability (Onyama, 2021; Zakery et al., 2017) and enhanced competitive advantage (Haseeb et al., 2019; Herera, 2015). Strategic alignment is a process of continuous improvements on strategies and processes thus leading to higher customer satisfaction and increased profits in a firm (Pelletier and Cloutier, 2019; Ilmudeen et al., 2019).

2.7. Conclusions

This chapter reviewed the existing literature and reviewed various models of strategic alignment such as SAM, SAMM, and Duffy's Maturity Models. Upon critical assessment of the key models for strategic alignment, a decision was made to adopt the SAMM of Luftman (2003) as the underpinning model of this research for investigating a UK-based Forex SMEs' strategic alignment. This chapter also reviewed the challenges both large organisations and SMEs face for achieving strategic alignment. As identified, the lack of support from senior management, lack of trust between business managers and IT department, uncooperative organisational culture and organisational policies that are unsupportive towards organisational performance are some of the key challenges faced for achieving strategic alignment. Following the literature review, it was noted that although the factors of strategic alignment and challenges faced by organisations for achieving strategic alignment was well understood in the literature, factors of strategic alignment and challenges faced by Forex SMEs, in particular, was not previously investigated. Therefore, this research seeks to investigate a UK-based forex SME to bridge the existing knowledge gap. The next chapter of the thesis now deals with the methodological aspect of the research.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This research follows the interpretivist research philosophy and utilizes a qualitative research design for exploring the factors of strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. This chapter of the thesis deals with the methodological aspects of the research and provides justification for selecting the interpretivist research philosophy. In order to determine the methodological stance of the research, various research philosophies are critically reviewed along with their associate data collection and analysis methods. This chapter focuses on the two generic questions "what you did and why?". In section 3.2, various epistemological positions available in social science studies are discussed, and the selected position for this study and justifications are presented. In section 3.3, the chosen research approach for this research and justifications are presented. Section 3.4 explains the research strategy employed in this study. Section 3.5 explains the chosen research design and justifications. Selected sampling methods for this study and the profile of participants have been described in section 3.6. The interview approaches used to collect data is explained in section 3.7 whilst analysis of the data is dealt with in section 3.8. Research validity, reliability, and ethical considerations are explained in sections 3.9 and 3.10, respectively.

3.2. Research Philosophy & Philosophical Assumptions

According to Saunders et al. (2016), research philosophy encompasses a broad range of topics; however, it is primarily concerned with the primary source of information, its nature, and how knowledge is developed. Research philosophy is a tool for determining the most appropriate research procedures and approaches for examining research problems (Creswell, 2014). In scientific investigation, research philosophies are deemed essential since they explicitly convey the researcher's point of view while allowing readers to grasp the research context quickly (Burke, 2007). In social science, research assumptions form the foundation, affecting the selection of research methodologies and the design of research studies (Creswell, 2007, 2014). Saunders et al. (2016) highlighted three major assumptions that all research philosophies are based upon. They are ontology, epistemology, and axiology.

3.2.1. Ontology

According to Bryman (2008), in social research, ontological assumptions are focused on the nature of social entities. Ontology can be described as "the very essence of the phenomena under investigation" (Burrell and Morgan, 2005; p. 25). Thus ontology is concerned with whether reality is subjectively formed by individual consciousness or exists purely outside. According to Bryman (2008), Burrell and Morgan (2005), and Creswell (2007), there can be two perceptions that individuals use to observe reality: objectivism and subjectivism. Scientific concepts utilised in natural sciences adhere to objectivism, which contends that social context is an external force (Burrell and Morgan, 2005; Saunders et al., 2016). Objectivists believe that everything can be measured by numbers (Nigals, 2010). Subjectivism, on the other hand, holds that researchers' understanding and feelings about the social issue they are studying have a direct impact on the results (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Table 3-1 summarises and compares subjectivism and objectivism across ontology, epistemology, and axiology.

Table 3-1: Comparisons of objectivism and subjectivism

Philosophy	Objectivism	Subjectivism
Ontology	Actual, Self-sufficient, Extrinsic, Rank	Providing rich information, however, its complicated, Information based on the research context, Providing numerous interpretations and connotations
Epistemology	Facts that can be measured, the use of numbers, scientific methods and principles	Emerging new knowledge into the science, theories, and principles are simplified, focused case studies and stories
Axiology	Open to knowledge and limitless	Values are prioritised

Sources: (Saunders et al., 2016; Saunders et al., 2017; Sekran and Bougie, 2016).

3.2.2. Epistemology

According to Bryman (2004; p. 711), epistemology is "a theory of knowledge". Epistemology is concerned with knowledge, and its authenticity and legality (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). In other words, epistemology is about the process of reaching the truth. In methodological literature, epistemology consists of three major positions, namely, positivism, interpretivism and pragmatism. Below, they are briefly defined prior to selecting an appropriate epistemological stance for this research.

3.2.2.1. Positivism

Positivism is described as "an epistemological position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond" (Bryman, 2004; p. 28). Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991; p. 5) stated positivism as "premised on the existence of a priori fixed relationships within phenomena which are typically investigated with structured instrumentation". Thomas (2017) postulated that a positivist attitude could help reduce bias because researchers frequently behave as impartial observers throughout the study process and avoid compromising the research results with their own opinions.

According to Anderson (2013), positivism approach is founded on scientific theories and more favourable on the deductive approach. The deductive approach assists researchers to define and simplify further their research constructs as they progress, and also less relevant factors are eliminated in the whole research journey to produce a generalisable outcome (Collis and Hussey, 2014). The most common research instruments and tools employed in this approach are online surveys, questionnaires, and observation practices (Sekran and Bougie, 2016). The ability to promote replication is the primary goal of positivist researchers (Saunders et al., 2016). However, Silverman (2014) criticises positivism, claiming that scholars view humans as a repository of attributes. The positivist approach depends on implementing theories that already exist in the literature and is not highly useful for uncovering emerging insights (Bell, 2018). As identified in the literature, strategic alignment in SMEs is an emerging field of research. Therefore, the positivist philosophy is not considered highly suitable for this research.

3.2.2.2. Interpretivism

Collis and Hussy (2009) stated that humans generate their own unique subjective and inter-subjective interpretations as humans engage with the environment around them. The interpretivism philosophy was developed as an alternative to the positivist approach. Human thoughts, ideas, personal feelings and past experiences are complex to define in social sciences as they can broaden our initial understanding of them. The interpretivism philosophy highlights that defining social issues is not a simple task as different researchers can describe human behaviour differently according to their research parameters; hence it would be irrelevant to measure them objectively (Thomas, 2017; Bell, 2018). Interpretivist researchers argue that human knowledge and social environment cannot be investigated in the same way since individuals from various social backgrounds may develop diverse understandings according to their past exposure in social contexts (Blumberg et al., 2014). Interpretivist researchers usually seek to have a deeper understanding of the research problem. Therefore, creativity and open-mind concepts are crucial during an interpretive investigation. According to Sekran and Bougie (2016), the interpretivist philosophy is an innovative and evolutionary philosophy since it allows scholars to include new development and enhance the research methodologies they are using.

Scholars who follow the interpretivist philosophy typically adhere to the inductive approach (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Under interpretivism, qualitative data collection methods such as unstructured in-depth interviews and focus groups are highly encouraged (Saunders et al., 2012). Therefore, instead of focusing on existing information, the interpretivism philosophy seeks to explore fresh concepts and inspires future researchers to enhance their originality and creativity. For this research, interpretivist philosophy is considered applicable as limited work has been done in the area of strategic alignment across SMEs and conducting an interpretivist study could lead to revealing various interesting new insights.

3.2.2.3. Pragmatism

Interpretivist and Positivist researchers have a strict preference for either subjective or objective methods; however, the pragmatism approach does not require strictly following one approach. The primary goal of pragmatist researchers is to address research problems while also informing future practices; pragmatic scholars formulate specific research questions and decide the most

effective research methodologies to address them (Saunders et al., 2016). Further, many research designs use qualitative, quantitative, mixed and action-based research methods under the pragmatism approach (Saunders et al., 2016). A pragmatic researcher's success depends on several factors. First and foremost, the researcher must have qualified knowledge regarding the research methods and tools that should be implemented in the research (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Secondly, the researcher's capacity and the extent of the research problem addressed in the study should match (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

3.2.2.4. Selected Epistemological Position and Justification

As aforementioned, in social science, there are two key philosophical stances: positivism and interpretivism. According to Wilson (2014), researchers who follow the interpretivist philosophy seek to uncover new knowledge using qualitative research tools such as in-depth semi-structured interviews. In comparison, researchers who follow the positivist philosophy seek to statistically test underlying assumptions across a wide range of situations by utilising larger sample sizes. Further, mathematical equations, statistics and information quantification are used by the positivist researchers, whereas the interpretivist researchers avoid mathematical equations and tools (Fotheringham, 2006). Mathematical values can be considered as finite values since their values are defined and whilst human thoughts and feelings cannot be regarded as finite as the values are not limited. As a result, a positivist philosophy may not be highly relevant to social science studies. Wilson (2014) stated that the interpretivist philosophy adheres to the inductive approach because interpretivist researchers tend to consider expanding their understanding of knowledge. On the other hand, positivist researchers adhere to the deductive method to eliminate unnecessary and complex factors (Remenyi, 1997). Nonetheless, studies that follow the interpretivist philosophy can be prone to researcher bias, as scholars tend to emphasise their personal opinions and thoughts when interpreting the outcomes of their investigations (Saunders et al., 2014).

This research seeks to explore the factors of strategic alignment for Forex SMEs and what kind of challenges they face for achieving strategic alignment by evaluating the views, opinions, and perceptions of employees at a UK-based Forex SME. As interpretivist investigations are often extensive and detailed, they are valuable in terms of uncovering new insights and are particularly

more relevant to areas that have not been extensively researched previously, i.e., Forex SMEs. This research, therefore, follows the interpretivist research philosophy.

3.3. Research Approach

Two key approaches in social science are used to develop theories: the inductive approach and the deductive approach (Walliman, 2006; Neuman, 2007). Addressing a research issue by breaking it down into several smaller hypotheses and then answering the main research question is referred to as deductive reasoning (Walliman, 2006). Since deductive theories are typically developed through robust statistical testing of various ideas, this approach is frequently used in positivist research (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Saunders et al. (2016) highlighted there are several advantages of using a deductive approach, such as the replicability and generalisability of the findings. However, this approach takes an objectivist point of view and may not be highly relevant to social science studies (Saunders et al., 2016).

On the other hand, the inductive approach is defined as "an approach to developing a theory that begins with concrete empirical evidence and works toward more abstract concepts and theoretical relationships" (Neuman, 2011; p. 70). Snape and Spencer (2003) highlighted that an inductive approach is advantageous for identifying emergent themes since it provides a comprehensive view of a situation. As the term itself said, 'interpretation' a researcher always prioritises their justification in conclusion, since discovering new knowledge is the primary purpose in inductive approach (Collis and Hussy, 2009). Since this approach is unstructured, researchers tend to focus on new facts and compare them with the existing theoretical body to evaluate the research issues. An inductive approach is usually used in a qualitative research study (Saunders et al., 2012).

As this research seeks to investigate factors of strategic alignment in Forex SMEs through an analysis and interpretations of managers working in a UK-based Forex SME, the inductive research approach is considered most appropriate. Using the inductive approach under the interpretivist philosophy allows the researcher to conduct an in-depth investigation and uncover emerging themes (Creswell, 1994). Inductive approaches are particularly more relevant when a field of investigation is new and there is not extensive existing literature available (Rahimi et al.,

2016). Hence, the inductive approach was considered further relevant as only a small number of empirical research have been conducted on Forex SMEs.

3.4. Research Strategy

Theoretically, research strategy refers to the unique technique that a researcher uses to accomplish a study (Yin, 2013). According to Neuman (2013), a research strategy supports the researcher in effectively designing, implementing, and monitoring the work. In order to explore the factors of strategic alignment in Forex SMEs, this research adopts the case study strategy. Case study strategy was selected for this research because a case study is appropriate to explore and examine the subject matter in great detail (Yin, 2013). By gathering extensive data using semi-structured interviews and conducting a comprehensive analysis of the case, the researcher was able to analyze the strategic operations of Company A extensively. Besides, strategic alignment in the Forex SMEs setting is underinvestigated; hence, a single case study strategy was considered the best research strategy for this research.

3.4.1. Case Study

A case study can be defined as "an in-depth investigation of a discrete entity (which may be a single setting, subject, collection or event) on the assumption that it is possible to derive knowledge of the wider phenomenon from an intensive investigation of a specific instance or case" (Gorman et al., 2005; 47). Similarly, Yin (2009: 18) explained case study as "an empirical inquiry that investigates a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context, when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not evident; and in which multiple sources of evidence are used". Yin (2009) further states that case study research can investigate a research problem thoroughly where researchers can find solutions to their research questions and objectives. The main aim of the case study strategy is "to understand the problem being investigated - where the word understands is used in the phenomenological or hermeneutic sense, and where 'understand' the meaning held by a subject or group is contrasted with the explanation produced by scientific observation" (Gable, 1994: 113). Table 3-2 have summarised the advantages and disadvantages of the case study strategy.

Table 3-2: Advantages and disadvantages of the case study research strategy

Advantages	Disadvantages
A single topic can be thoroughly investigated.	Analysing large amounts of qualitative data could be time-consuming.
It is possible to take into consideration the interaction of elements and occurrences.	The ability to review information to reach a more accurate conclusion.
A variety of data collection methods can be used.	Generalisation of the findings could be difficult.
If a single case study is chosen, the researcher will only have access to a single firm and can investigate the firm in an in-depth manner.	Researchers' decision making depends on the "case" he/she investigate.
A case study phenomenon can be focused to a department or the whole firm.	

Source: (Neuman, 2011; Yin, 2009).

3.4.1.1. Types of Case Study Research

Case study strategy can be of two types: single case study and multiple case study. A single case study research strategy investigates the entire sample as a case. Yin (2003) highlighted that the researcher will prioritise only one case study in a single case study; therefore, the researcher can concentrate thoroughly. Shavelson and Towne (2002) argue that single case studies allow researchers to investigate emerging concepts and even allow generalisations if the research question is in line with the selection of examples. In a single case study approach, the researcher can analyse the research problem in an in-depth manner (Baxter and Jack, 2008).

On the other hand, when there is more than one case (e.g. organisations, individuals or groups of people) in a research phenomenon, researchers tend to consider a multiple case study approach (Yin, 2003). The main difference between a single and multiple case study research is that the researcher who focuses on multiple case studies try to comprehend the differences and similarities between the cases (Yin, 2003; Stake, 1995). Although the findings of a multiple case study research can be more insightful and generalizable, these types of studies can be costly and time-demanding (Baxter and Jack, 2008). When creating an in-depth theoretical understanding,

single case studies are considered the best approach compared to multiple case studies because single case design allows in-depth investigations; hence, it leads to developing richer theories (Dyer and Wilkins, 1991).

As aforementioned, this research seeks to investigate a domain that has not been extensively researched previously. This research primarily focuses on exploring and modelling the factors of strategic alignment for Forex SMEs. In order to do so, it is essential to critically investigate a case in an in-depth manner so that various factors and the roles they play in terms of achieving harmonious strategic alignment within Forex SMEs can be comprehended. Given that very little work has been done in terms of strategic alignment of SMEs and virtually no empirical work has been done on strategic alignment of Forex SMEs, it would be more rational to conduct an in-depth investigation by using the single case study strategy rather than using multiple case study strategy that seeks to compare cases. Additionally, given that the researcher has limited time, resource, and finance to conduct this research, it would have been difficult to successfully execute a multiple case study research within they are given time. Therefore, a single case study strategy was considered most appropriate for this research.

3.4.1.2. Case Selection and Justifications

For the purpose of this research, a UK-based Forex SME, Company A, was selected considering factors such as suitability, accessibility, and time. To achieve the research aim and objectives, a case study approach was chosen since the main research questions begin with "what" and "how." According to Shavelson and Towne (2002) and Stake (1995), a case study is an appropriate research strategy when a study seeks to answer questions starting with "what," "how," and "why." By using this approach, the researcher aims to gather comprehensive data that helps explore the factors involved in achieving harmonious strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. Additionally, the case study approach assists in gaining a deeper understanding of the essential factors for achieving harmonious strategic alignment based on the views and experiences of the research participants (Goman et al., 2005; Flyvbjerg, 2004; Gable, 1994).

Several reasons were considered when selecting the case study approach for this research. Gammelgaard (2017) highlighted that direct access to the case organization is crucial for gathering the required qualitative data. As the researcher is currently employed by the case

organization, there is a direct access to all relevant information needed for this research. Trust and openness of research participants are important factors in qualitative research, as emphasized by Butt (2021). Participants' trust and openness towards the research study lead to positive results (Seawright and Gerring, 2008). In this study, the researcher had access to potential participants, including senior managers of the case firm. Having such access is expected to make the data collection process smoother, especially during the challenging times caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, the case firm faces various strategic challenges, making it interesting to investigate the causes of these challenges and how they can be addressed to enhance organizational performance and profitability. Existing literature has noted that achieving strategic alignment can indeed lead to improved organizational performance (Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019; Wang and Rusu, 2018; Gbangou and Rusu, 2016; Street et al., 2017; Cataldo et al., 2012; Gutierrez et al., 2009).

Mitigating research bias in qualitative research involves being aware of potential biases and taking steps to minimize their influence on the research process and findings. Mackieson et al. (2019) highlighted that mitigating research bias in a qualitative study is challenging; however, it is crucial to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings. This research employed several strategies to help mitigate research bias. Reflexivity aided the researcher in engaging in self-reflection and acknowledging their own biases, assumptions, and preconceptions. According to Johnson et al. (2020), reflexivity helps qualitative researchers question themselves regarding their beliefs and values, which may impact the research process. During the research, the researcher documented all formal and informal advice received during this research journey, and questions such as "Is this the correct way of asking this question?" and "What if I ask the question in smaller parts to gain a deeper understanding?" Moreover, the researcher used a reflexive interviewing approach, allowing for the collection of comprehensive data valuable to this research. The researcher remained open-minded and prepared to ask further questions during the interview sessions, enabling participants to express their personal viewpoints freely. Peer debriefing and review is another strategy that was employed to mitigate research bias (Fusch and Ness, 2015; Chenail, 2011). The researcher attended a knowledge exchange symposium organized by the University of Wales and shared his research proposals, where he received valuable peer and expert feedbacks.

3.5. Research Design: Qualitative

This research adopts a qualitative research design for achieving research objectives. The qualitative research design was selected because strategic alignment in the area of Forex SMEs is underinvestigated. According to Saunders et al. (2012), research design refers to a prepared plan that guides the whole research process. There are two key research designs: quantitative and qualitative research designs. Quantitative research designs are usually used by positivist researchers and questionnaires are usually used as data collection instruments (Blumberg et al., 2014). Questionnaires help researchers to collect a large amount of data in a cost-effective manner (Wilson, 2014; Sekran and Bougie, 2016). However, by using the quantitative research design, researchers may not be able to collect in-depth and rich data (Saunders et al., 2016). Qualitative research designs, in contrast, are usually used by interpretivist researchers and they are considered valuablefull investigating the research phenomenon in an in-depth manner.

Given that this research follows the interpretivist research philosophy, a qualitative research design is used in this research. This research adopted the qualitative research design for several reasons. Firstly, strategic alignment in SMEs is under-investigated. Though it has been noted that there is an abundance of literature related to the strategic alignment of larger organisations, only a few studies have been carried out in SMEs (i.e., Alghazi et al., 2020; Street et al., 2017). Strategic alignment in SMEs is an emerging theoretical area; hence, using a qualitative design would help to further extend the knowledge and develop the area of research. Secondly, the researcher seeks to conduct interviews with employees of the case organisation to investigate the factors of strategic alignment as well as the strategic challenges faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment. Under the qualitative research design, researchers use various data collection instruments such as observations, ethnography, content review, and different types of interviews (Saunders et al., 2014). Through the adoption of a qualitative research design, the researcher would be able to collect data by interviewing various employees (senior area support management team, branch managers, IT department employees, senior IT-Business analysts) of the case organisation. The next section of this chapter now details the sampling procedures, the sample size of the research, and justifications for sample selection.

3.6. Sampling

According to Sekran and Bogie (2016), sampling can be defined as a representation of a portion of the whole population. There are two broad categories of sampling methods: probability and non-probability (Bryman and Bell, 2015; Saunders et al., 2015).

The probability sampling method can be defined as a method in which every element of the target audience has a predefined likelihood of being selected in the study (Saunders et al., 2015). By employing random selection, each member of the population has a definite non-zero probability of being chosen for the study (Sekran and Bogie, 2000). In probability sampling, when selecting participants, researchers have to re-think that the participants should represent the population in the research study (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Probability sampling facilitates generalisations and is commonly used by positivist researchers (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

In *non-probability sampling method*, there is no predefined probability that an individual will be selected in the study (Malhotra et al., 2012). In this sampling method, the generalisability of the findings is not prioritised because studies that employed non-probability prioritise data accessibility, time and resource availability and the cost of research (Blumberg et al., 2014). There are no set parameters for non-probability sampling, rather the researcher uses his preferences and judgments for recruiting the participants. Non-probability selection has four key categories: snowball, judgemental, convenience and quota sampling (Saunders et al., 2015). The non-probability sampling method is generally used by interpretivist researchers.

For this research, upon carefully reviewing the time and costs constraints associated with the probability techniques, a decision was made to use *judgmental purposive sampling* technique of non-probability sampling method. The judgemental purposive sampling technique allows the researcher to carefully select participants that are most appropriate for achieving research objectives (Saunders et al., 2015). As the principal researcher for this study, I used specific selection criteria when shortlisting potential interview participants. Since this research is an explorative case study, I shortlisted experienced participants who are involved in the strategic alignment process in the case company. Participants were required to have at least 6 years of work experience in Company A, and participants should be employed in a senior managerial position at the time of data collection. Lastly, they should have been involved in the strategic

decision-making process of Company A at some stage of their career. For this research, I also utilised some elements of *snowball sampling* techniques. As the interview progressed, some participants recommended their colleagues in Company A that may be suitable for interviewing. I also utilised *volunteer sampling* as all of the participants participated out of their free will (Saunders et al., 2016).

3.6.1. Sample Size and Justifications

In this research, a total of 16 interviews were conducted with employees of a UK based Forex SME, Company A. When deciding the appropriate sample size for the research, a review of the literature was conducted concerning a suitable sample size for a qualitative research study. Sibanda and Ramathan (2017) suggested that, for a qualitative research study, a sample size of 12 or over would be appropriate. Stenfors-Hayes et al. (2013) suggested considering a sample size of between 3 to 20 participants in an interpretive research study. Similarly, Trigwell (2000) highlighted that an exploratory interpretive qualitative investigation that focuses on revealing new insights and understandings should consider a sample size between 10 to 20 participants. Other researchers such as Clarke and Braun (2013) and Fugard and Potts (2014) also stated that a sample size of over 12 participants would be appropriate for reaching data saturation. In a similar research, Chan et al. (2019) conducted 22 interviews whilst investigating digital innovation of a case study of an SME. The number of interviews conducted for this is consistent with the suggestions of the prior researchers and are expected to help the researcher to achieve data saturation.

Nonetheless, initially, the researcher aimed to conduct 20 interviews for this study. However, due to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, Company A made some of their employees redundant, hence the participants denied participation in the research. Nevertheless, a sample size of 16 is considered appropriate, particularly because most of the participants are senior business and IT management personnel that are extensively involved in the decision-making processes and ensuring strategic alignment of Company A.

3.7. Data Collection

Data collection is an extremely important task in a research study as the effectiveness of data collection process determines the success or failure of a study (Clarke and Braun, 2013). Researchers can obtain the necessary data for their research in two unique ways: primary and secondary data collection (Saunders et al., 2016). Primary data collections include data gathered from primary sources in a direct and unmediated manner (Saunders et al., 2016). Secondary data collection, on the other hand, include "the data already collected in some other context than the present study" (Robson, 2002: p. 552).

For this research, interviews are adopted as the primary data collection procedure. In the process of designing interview questions, secondary data sources such as academic journals related to strategic alignment and SMEs were also considered as the inclusion of existing knowledge is critical to strengthen the research findings (Wilson, 2014).

3.7.1. Interviews

Interviews are great tools for investigating ambiguous issues, and they can be highly useful in uncovering new insights (Sekran and Bougie, 2016; Saunders et al., 2015). According to Saunders et al. (2016: 88) interviews can be categorised into three types: "semi-structured interviews, structured interviews, and unstructured interviews". Structured interviews are classified as consistent interviews (questions are fixed) by Healey and Rawlinson (1994) whilst semi-structured and unstructured interviews are classified as non-consistent interviews (questions are fixed to some extent, but the researcher can add or change questions). There are two specific ways interviews can be conducted: "one-to-one and one-to-many" (Saunders et al., 2016; p. 96). One-to-one approach is considered useful for exploring in-depth information whilst the one-to-many approach is suitable for identifying new insights. In this research, a one-to-one interview approach is considered as the researcher seeks to explore the factors of strategic alignment by understanding the perceptions and experiences of practitioners in an in-depth manner.

There are pros and cons of the interview method that need to be considered by every researcher. Interviews aid researchers to gather in-depth data for their studies, which can be very helpful in finding solutions for research problems (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Also, employing interviews

can develop a sense of trust between the researcher and the participants where both parties can have in-depth communication (Saunders et al., 2016). However, the success of an interview is dependent on the competence of the researcher. In an event where the researcher cannot build rapport with the participants, s/he may not be able to collect accurate data.

In the field of strategic alignment, interviews have been commonly used for collecting data (Gustafsson, 2017). Alaceva and Rusu (2015) employed semi-structured interviews as their primary data collection procedure to identify the barriers of strategic alignment in a Swedish firm. Alghazi et al. (2020) also used semi-structured interviews in their qualitative study to comprehend the strategic alignment process in Saudi Arabian public firms. Moreover, Sibanda and Ramratan (2017) utilised semi-structured interviews to understand the strategic alignment issues of IBM South Africa. The researchers noted that, by using interviews, they were able to communicate with participants very sensitively and were able to extract rich data. Considering the existing literature and usefulness of semi-structured interviews, I have used semi-structured interviews as the primary data collection method in this research because it enables me to sustain interview communications with the participants whilst allowing me to ask further questions based on their feedback. The next section now provides more justifications on the application of semi-structured interviews in this research.

3.7.2. Semi-Structured Interviews

As stated above, this case study research employs a qualitative method by adopting semi-structured interviews to obtain primary data. We have used semi-structured interviews because this research study concentrates on comprehending and interpreting research participants' views and feedback (Cresswell, 2007). In a semi-structured interview process, a series of questionnaires are asked, but additional questions may be developed during the interview to clarify responses. Saunders et al. (2016) stated that semi-structured interviews provide the researcher with extensive flexibility during the data collection phase. In this research, semi-structured interviews were highly useful as the researcher was able to add and modify questions to obtain further data from the participants. Further, we also asked further elaborations by asking questions such as "*Can you explain to me why did you mention.....*". Although unstructured interviews would also have provided me with the flexibility, there would have been risks of the conversations flowing away from the research topic (Saunders et al., 2016).

In order to collect the primary research data, we interviewed a total of 16 employees of Company A with interviews lasting between 55 minutes to 1 hour and 15 minutes. Out of the 16 participants interviewed, 8 of them were branch managers, 4 of them were senior area managers, 2 of them were senior IT-Business analysts, and 2 of them were employees in the department. Considering the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, participants were allowed to choose how they want to participate in the interviews. They were given options to participate face-to-face, through telephone (mobile) or via video calls (Skype, Teams or Zoom etc.) According to Saunders et al. (2016), allowing such flexibility to the participants can enhance the reliability of the data. The next section now details the interview procedures followed during the research.

3.7.2.1. Interview Protocols

Interview protocol is the procedure followed by the researcher when carrying out these interviews (Jacob and Ferguson, 2012). Prior to conducting semi-structured interviews, we developed a set of guiding interview questions based on the findings of the literature. The pre-prepared interview guide helped me to stay focused on the main research questions and research objectives during the research process. Appendix C includes the guiding interview questions prepared for this research.

During the interview process, we ensured that every participant is comfortable and voluntarily willing to take part in the research. We briefly explained to each participant the type of question they will be asked in the interview so they can be better prepared for themselves. Before starting the interview, we collected signed interview participant consent forms from the participants. At the starting point of each interview, the researcher introduced himself formally to the participants, stating my name, the university I am studying at, and the research topic. Moreover, all my interview questions were semi-structured, so I was prepared to expand interview questions further based on the participants' answers. Lastly, at the end of each interview, I thanked participants profoundly and asked them whether they have any questions regarding my interview sessions. Importantly, as advised by Company A's HR department, I had to be very concerned about participants' health and safety due to the COVID-19 pandemic, thus I maintained two meters distance during face-to-face interviews and wore face masks. I also made hand sanitiser available to the participants whilst participating in the interviews. I made no physical contact with the participants.

3.7.2.2. Pilot interviews and changes made

In this research, we conducted pilot interviews to ensure my data collection instrument is fit for purpose and the collected data can effectively achieve research objectives. A pilot study can simplify research questions and help to collect rich data. Besides, pilot interviews also prevent potential loss of time and resources due to data collection instruments not being fit for purpose (Saunders et al., 2016). Prior to conducting pilot interviews, we developed separate interview questions for each stakeholder group (Branch managers, Senior area management, IT department and Senior IT-Business analyst) because their job responsibilities are different, and they involve in strategic alignment processes from different perspectives. Upon developing four sets of interview questions, we interviewed four participants from each stakeholder group. Each pilot interview lasted between 30 to 40 minutes. After completing the interviews, I requested the participants to provide feedback on the experience of the interview process. Three of the participants did not understand the concept of strategic alignment clearly. Although they were involved in the process of strategic alignment on a day-to-day basis, I experienced that they were not familiar with the theoretical aspects. Therefore, during the main data collection, we took extra time to explain to participants the concept of a strategic alignment. This was highly effective as participants were able to provide elaborative answers after having a clear understanding of what strategic alignment means.

3.7.2.3. Main Interview Process and Challenges Faced

Prior to recruiting the interview participants, the researcher formally informed Company A's HR department. We contacted the HR Manager of Company A mentioning my research title, scope, the purpose for carrying out this research and how my research recommendations may be beneficial for Company A. After receiving the formal authorisation from the HR Manager, we started contacting interview participants through email, telephone, and face-to-face communications at work. When my targeted participants agreed to participate, we emailed them two forms: Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form for Interview Participation. The forms contained all the essential information about my research. Once completing all the documentation, we then requested the participants to provide me with their availability and their preferred method of interviews. Then the scheduled interviews based on the participants'

availability; all of the face-to-face interviews were conducted in the premises of company A. All of the interviews were recorded after getting permission from the participants to do so.

The researcher faced numerous challenges whilst collecting the main data for the research. During the COVID-19 restrictions, it was challenging for me to conduct interviews as many participants were nervous about their health and safety. Another challenge was due to the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, half of the branches were permanently closed, and most of my participants lost their employment due to the COVID-19 redundancy program in Company A. We had to search for additional participants that are suitable for the research. Making new participants understand the research process and getting their informed consent to participate in the study was a time-consuming process. To recruit new participants, we adopted several strategies such as communicating with them politely and asking for their support for my research. After spending additional months, participants agreed to participate in my interview in work premises. Following COVID-19 restrictions, we cleaned the interview venue before starting the interviews. Moreover, we placed additional hand gel bottles and face masks on the interview venue.

3.8. Data Analysis

3.8.1. Qualitative Data Analysis

As previously stated, qualitative data obtained through semi-structured interviews support researchers to discover emergent patterns and themes (Creswell, 2014). The researcher used thematic analysis - a novel way for categorising and transcribing data into distinct themes (Saunders et al., 2016) in order to analyse the data collected from interviews and subsequently to answer research questions. Prior to conducting the analysis, the interviews were transcribed by listening to the audio recordings again and again on a word-by-word basis. I listened to each interview three times to ensure all of the transcriptions were accurate.

3.8.1.1. Thematic Analysis

After reviewing numerous analytical approaches, we decided to follow the qualitative thematic analysis for the analysis of the data. Thematic analysis was considered suitable as the research topic of strategic alignment in SMEs is an emergent topic in literature and thematic analysis is great for revealing new understanding and themes (Saunders et al., 2016). Thematic analysis can

be defined as "a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data (Braun and Clarke, 2006: p. 79). Further, thematic analysis was defined by Bryman (2012: p. 717) as "a term used in connection with the analysis of qualitative data to refer to the extraction of key themes in one's data". Qualitative data tend to be in-depth, which requires in-depth analysis for generating themes. Hence, the researcher has to re-read the data many times to understand its meaning under thematic analysis. We considered Braun and Clark's Thematic analysis procedure (Braun and Clarke, 2006) and followed their six phases of thematic analysis as follows:

Phase one, "*familiarizing yourself with your data*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 87), is about preparing data for transcription (if required), reviewing and re-reading the material, and making important notes about initial thoughts.

Phase two, "*generating initial codes*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 88), is about coding important elements of the data in an organised manner across the full data set and then compiling information relevant to each code is the goal.

Phase three, "*searching for themes*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 89), is about organising each code under prospective themes and compiling all required data for each potential theme are all part of the third phase.

Phase four, "*reviewing themes*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 91), is about polishing the themes for better understanding in the research analysis. In this phase, themes are tested in connection to the coded extracts highlighted in the phase one stage and the whole database created in phase two, resulting in the creation of a map that supports the research objectives and the analysis.

Phase five is about "*defining and naming themes*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 92). After each theme was reviewed in phase four, the final themes that will be addressed in the research need to be confirmed.

Phase six involves, "*producing the report*" (Braun and Clarke, 2006: 93). After confirming the final themes from the analysed data, this phase is about 'let the information talk'. Finalised themes will be the starting point for the research discussion, where literature findings and research findings will be thoroughly compared and discussed.

Braun and Clarke's six steps are precise; however, this is a manual procedure where researchers have to manually mark code and themes, which can be time-consuming and tiring. Therefore, the researcher employed NVivo 12 software to analyse interview data, following Braun and Clarke's above steps. The knowledge that is gathered through the existing literature review were triangulated with the research findings in the discussion chapter of this study in order to draw broader generalisations of the findings.

3.8.1.2. Use of NVivo 12 Software for Data Analysis

As mentioned above, this research used NVivo 12 for analysing of the research data efficiently. Digital data coding approaches are becoming increasingly popular as they help to achieve greater rigour when working with large amounts of data and using such tools can improve research accuracy and conclusions can be more comprehensive (Bazeley, 2007). By using NVivo 12, I was not only able to save time but also was able to generate more accurate themes and enhance the overall quality of the research (Wong, 2008).

Bazeley (2007) highlighted that there are five steps for how NVivo engages with qualitative data: organising data, organising concepts, analysing data, visual modelling, and reporting. NVivo's graphical user-friendly interfaces supported me to organise my research data clearly. I was able to clearly read and re-read whole transcripts in less time and aggregate all codes so that I could develop main themes. NVivo is a comprehensive software; hence, it requires a thorough good knowledge about its functions before using it (Hilal and Alabri, 2013). Therefore, I attended all NVivo workshops organised by the University of the West of Scotland and watched many NVivo tutorial videos on YouTube. I followed Braun and Clarke's six steps thematic analysis (as discussed in 3.8.1.1) whilst using NVivo 12.

3.8.1.3. Key Findings from NVivo

After conducting the analysis using Nvivo 12, multiple themes and sub-themes were identified. The identified themes included: Exploring strategic alignment in a Forex SME (*Theme 1*), Challenges to face when achieving strategic alignment in Company A (*Theme 2*), Achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business and IT strategy of a Forex SME (*Theme 3*).Please

primary way of data collection in this research, easy to understand interview questions were developed so that participants can provide comprehensive feedback. Secondly, before starting the main interview sessions, I had friendly casual communications with each participant to gain their trust, build rapport, and reduce their nervousness. I maintained a harmonious relationship with the participants to obtain in-depth, accurate information as much as possible during interview sessions (Silverman, 1993; Breakwell, 2000). Moreover, to enhance the reliability of the findings, I used a voice recording device to record the entire interview session. This allowed me to listen to their responses over and over again and ensure I fully understood their perceptions and opinions.

In addition, in a qualitative research study, the idea of *validity* is defined using a variety of terminologies. According to Winter (2000; p. 6), this is neither a singular, fixed or globally recognised concept but "rather a contingent construct, inescapably grounded in the processes and intentions of particular research methodologies and projects". The idea of validity is hard to fit in a qualitative study (Saunders et al., 2016). However, at the same time, researchers have understood that, due to data in-depth data capacities in their research, they do require measuring scale or a definition for their respective study (Creswell and Miller, 2000). For instance, according to Creswell and Miller (2000) the idea of validity depends on the researcher's perception and their personal choices to validate their data. In qualitative studies, validity simply means the "appropriateness" of processes, instruments and the data (Saunders et al., 2016; p. 115). To enhance the validity of the findings, I applied a few measurements in this research. First, the main research questions were developed based on the findings of the literature review, hence achieving content validity (Saunders et al., 2016). Since this research follows a single case study, the methodology must be appropriate; after carefully considering the existing literature and the methods used by previous similar studies, I employed a qualitative research design because it is instrumental for exploring emerging insights. Besides, I employed NVivo 12 software to analyse the collected data and develop main themes; doing so can minimise the possible human errors in the process of data analysis (Gustafsson, 2017).

3.9.2. Research Quality

It is important for every research study to maintain higher standards of quality to produce credible findings. In order to maintain quality, this research employed Lincoln and Guba's four

dimension of evaluative criteria: Credibility, Transferability, Dependability and Confirmability (Lincoln and Guba, 1986; p. 75). Lincoln and Guba highlighted that trustworthiness in research conclusions are important when assessing its worth. Thus, how I considered the four dimensions of research quality is described briefly below.

- **Credibility** - In order to ensure that this research's findings and conclusions are true and credible, I have read and re-read again the interview data for a few days to understand its meanings. Also, prior to starting the interviews, I communicated with the participants giving them a brief explanation about the research goals and type of interview questions that I will be asking so that they can prepare well.
- **Transferability** - To evaluate to what extent the research conclusions can be generalised or whether to what extent the research results can be transferred to different business contexts for future research studies, I carefully considered the existing literature and their findings both during the collection of the data and discussions of the findings. I also used judgemental purposive sampling method by carefully selecting participants that are most knowledgeable for achieving research objectives.
- **Dependability**–Dependability concerns that the findings will be consistent if the research is repeated. Although dependability concerns with mainly with quantitative research, Lincoln and Guba (1986) argue that considering it can also enhance the quality of a qualitative research study. To ensure dependability, all interviews were audio-recorded so that they can be revisited if necessary. I also used NVivo 12 for achieving higher coding accuracy.
- **Confirmability** - It is also important to ensure that the results can be supported by other academic findings in the literature. To achieve confirmability, I used a pre-established framework (SAMM) to guide me through the entire research process. I also discussed the findings by locating them in the broader literature.

3.10. Ethical Considerations

The term "ethics" considers the peoples' rights when they are involved in a research study where there cannot be any harm to their identity or privacy (Hesse-Biber and Leavy, 2010). Numerous ethical norms apply to research investigations, including physical injury considerations, legal,

privacy protection, and psychological (Zikmund, 2000). During this research process, I ensured the anonymity of the participants, the confidentiality of their information, and obtained the participants' informed consent.

I fully followed the UWS research ethics practices and procedures, and my research ethics application was fully approved by the UWS research ethics panel. Before starting the main interviews, I provided comprehensive information to the interview participants regarding this research and gave them a brief introduction about how their responses will be used. This was done by providing them with the Research Participant Information Sheet as well as verbal information when requested. Participants had the right to decline participation in my study without any giving any reason and at any stage of the interviews. Only participants that consented to participate by signing the Participant Consent Form were interviewed. In order to ensure all participants can provide informed consent, no participant under the age of 18 was interviewed.

3.11. Chapter Summary

The main purpose of this chapter was to provide an overview of the most appropriate research philosophy and methodologies for achieving the research objectives and thereby answering the main research question. This research study adopted the interpretivist philosophy as its epistemological position. As noted in the literature, strategic alignment in SMEs is an understudied research area and a new understanding are needed for enhancing the performance and profitability of SMEs through effective alignment of their IT and business strategies. Therefore, a qualitative research design was selected for this research to explore new insights and themes.

This chapter also reviewed different instruments for data collection in a qualitative study and determined that semi-structured interviews provide a path for obtaining in-depth data that is consistent with the existing literature and may prove invaluable for constructing new theories. This research adopted judgemental purposive sampling because the researcher followed his judgements when selecting interview participants. In addition, procedures followed for ensuring

research reliability, validity, and quality were also elaborated. The next chapter (Chapter 4) now presents the findings of this research.

Chapter Four: Research Findings

4.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the research. In order to achieve the research objectives, 16 semi-structured interviews were carried out with the senior business and IT managers of a UK Forex SME, Company A. The interview transcripts were analysed by using the six-steps thematic analysis of Braun and Clarke (2006). The findings of the research are categorised under three different main themes: the factors of strategic alignment, challenges faced in terms of achieving strategic alignment, the critical success factors of achieving harmonious strategic alignment between IT and business strategies. Prior to reporting the detailed findings of this research, profiles of the participants are detailed in the section below.

4.1.1. Profile of the Respondents

As aforementioned, for this research, 8 branch managers, 4 senior area managers, 2 IT department personnel, and 2 senior IT-Business analysts were interviewed. Table 4.1 presents the profile of interview participants.

Table 4-1: Profile of Participants

Participant Code	Job Position	Years of Experience in Company A	Years of Experience in Forex Sector	Highest level of education attained
BM1	Branch Manager	9 years	12 years	Diploma, Bachelor
BM2	Branch Manager	11 years	14 years	Bachelor, Master
BM3	Branch Manager	9 years	10 years	Bachelor
BM4	Branch Manager	7 years	10 years	Bachelor, Master
BM5	Branch Manager	15 years	15 years	Bachelor
BM6	Branch Manager	12 years	12.5 years	Bachelor
BM7	Branch Manager	10 years	13 years	Bachelor
BM8	Branch Manager	10 years	12 years	Bachelor
AM	Senior Area Manager	15 years	20 years	Bachelor, Master
ASM1	Area Support Manager I	13 years	15 years	Bachelor
ASM2	Area Support Manager II	11.5 years	15.5 years	Diploma

ASM3	Area Support Manager III	12 years	12 years	Bachelor
ITD	IT Director	19 years	25 years	Bachelor, Master
ITM	IT Manager UK	10 years	13 years	Bachelor
ITBA1	Senior IT-Business Analyst I	9 years	16 years	Bachelor, Master
ITBA2	Senior IT-Business Analyst II	8 years	13 years	Bachelor

Source: The Author.

Table 4.2 below now details upon the roles and responsibilities of the interview participants.

Table 4-2: Roles and Responsibilities of the interview participants.

Job Position	Role and Responsibilities
Branch Manager	The role of a foreign exchange manager involves overseeing the operations and functions of a branch that specialises in Forex services. Their primary responsibilities revolve around managing the branch, ensuring smooth Forex operations and delivering customer orders on-time. Moreover, branch manager must formally inform any issues that are related to IT systems to the IT department and branch security should be a high priority at all times. Overall, the branch manager plays a crucial role in managing branch's operations, driving monthly sales, ensuring compliance, and providing excellent customer services.
Area Manager	The role of foreign exchange Area Manager can vary depending on the organisation. In Company A, Area Manager is responsible for several specific tasks such as team management, sales and business development, operational oversight, improve customer service, risk management, performance monitoring and reporting. They are also responsible for ensuring the firm follows government laws and regulations.
Area Support Manager	Area Support Managers should continuously communicate with branch managers in Company A and formally report every information in detail to Area Manager.

	Further, he/she is responsible for operational management of all branches in Company A. This includes monthly performance evaluation and customer service relations management.
IT Director	The IT Directors oversees the technology infrastructure and systems related to Forex operations within the Company A. The IT Director should make sure Company A's current IT strategy and business strategy are aligned at all times. Their main tasks and duties include IT strategy development and improvement, system upgrade and maintenance, infrastructure management, business-IT regulatory compliance, IT risk management and reporting current IT progress to senior management.
IT Manager	IT managers must make sure that current IT strategies support the Forex business strategy and they are strategically aligned. The IT manager's main responsibilities revolve around overseeing and managing the IT infrastructures and systems that support the Forex trading operations. In Company A, IT managers are responsible for IT infrastructure management, systems development and maintenance, risk management, regulatory compliance, technology evaluation and documentation. They are also responsible for reporting IT issues to the IT Director.
IT-Business Analyst	The role of an IT-Business Analyst is to bridge the gap between business and IT solutions within an organisation. They play a crucial role in the software development life cycle by gathering and analysing requirements, identifying Forex business problems and recommend solutions to enhance overall Forex operations in Company A. Some of the main roles and responsibilities are, requirements gathering smooth Forex operations, solution design-evaluation and continuous improvements in current business and IT strategies of Company A.

Source: The Author.

The forthcoming section of this chapter now presents the findings of this research in detail.

4.2. The Factors of Strategic Alignment

In this research, in order to explore the factors of strategic alignment, a UK based Forex SME (Company A) was explored using Luftman's strategic alignment maturity model (SAMM). As reviewed in Chapter 2.4.4.3 of this thesis, this model consists of six dimensions namely, communication maturity, competency maturity, IT governance maturity, IT scope and architecture maturity, partnership and skills maturity. Upon aanalysis of the interview transcripts, it was noted that the consideration of six dimensions of SAMM is critical in terms of assessing the strategic alignment of Forex SMEs. The findings of this research revealed that in order to accurately assess the level of strategic alignment of Forex SMEs, it is also important to consider their web system's maturity. The following figure graphically presents the factors of strategic alignment as identified by this research.

Figure 4-1: Strategic Alignment in a Forex SME.

Source: The Author.

4.2.1. Communication Maturity

All 16 participants in the sample asserted that achieving new strategic alignment starts with effective communication between different departments and individuals within an organisation. This is because understanding the need of another department and assisting them appropriately will not be possible if the need itself is not fully understood. One of the branch managers in the sample highlighted that in a lack of effective communication, the head office staffs were not able to effectively communicate the need and trends of the market to the IT department, which led to a lack of coordination between the two departments. This lack of coordination and communication is resulting in the members of IT departments not understanding the recent and actual needs of the market. For example:

To have a proper engagement between business and IT departments, all the people who are already in these two departments must have shared understanding and knowledge. IT departments in our organisation generally do not have a clear insight of how foreign exchange business works in London. This is because they are not willing to communicate with other departments.

(BM 2)

BM 3 also echoed the view of BM 2.

Since acquiring a sister company, we are facing a lack of clarity in terms of the company's future direction, and this is primarily due to the senior managers that are at the decision-making level not communicating effectively with The IT department.

(BM 3)

As can be seen above, both branch managers believe that in the lack of effective communication, there is a possibility that the decisions of different departments do not match with each other. Strategic alignment starts with trust and mutual understanding between different departments and having a mutual understanding and a shared goal helps to achieve strategic alignment.

From the analysis of the data, it is apparent that Company A is struggling with a communication gap. This was also apparent in response to one of the senior managers of the company who is currently working as an area support manager. Whilst recognising the communication gap, ASM1 did acknowledge that communication is essential for a good functioning and coordination of different departments, thus they are working tirelessly to reduce this communication gap.

Our company's working process has changed now; before we used to only work in a certain city but now, we are working all across the country. Prior to the acquisition, we used to be a small team and communicating used to be fairly straightforward, which is not the case anymore as we have expanded, and we need to follow a communication channel so that we can communicate to a larger number of staff. It has indeed caused some delay in terms of effective communication; however, it is a work in progress, and we are working tirelessly to reduce this communication gap.

(ASM 1)

ASM1 felt that the lack of effective communication was having serious repercussions on the business itself. Some branch managers, however, stated that the exchange rate senior managers determined is not competitive enough for retaining existing customers and thus they requested the senior managers to review their rates on a regular basis and also review how rates fluctuate in different parts of the country. However, the senior managers and IT department managers seemed reluctant to take suggestions from the branch manager, rather than rely merely on the communication they receive from senior leadership, who usually are uninformed of changing market needs and consumer demands. The IT director in the sample indicated that he has to follow a structured approach for setting rates rather than relying on subjective recommendations of the branch managers.

We cannot fully depend on branch managers' recommendations for rate updates, and we will not be able to control rate margin profit. [...] So we have confirmed set rates which were confirmed by the retail director. The set rates are designed by reviewing the market that day.

(ITD)

Nevertheless, the lack of effective communication across different departments was observed to affect not only the strategic alignment between different departments but also affected the business process and organisational performance altogether. Therefore, based on the findings of this research, communication maturity is determined as a factor that plays a critical role in achieving strategic alignment in a Forex SME.

4.2.2. Competency Maturity

Competency maturity highlights that organisations should conduct formally approved strategic assessments of business and IT strategies to identify any gaps in the organisational strategies; a review of the interview data indicated that the management of Company A does not conduct

such assessments. Lack of regular monitoring of organisational strategies can lead to the formation of vague and sophisticated strategies which impose inflexibilities for Forex operations. According to one of the senior managers (ASM1), the bureau's flexibility and its profitability have been reduced dramatically due to strict restrictions imposed by the senior leadership.

Yes... there are few bottlenecks hanging around in our procedures, you know, it's a chicken and egg problem really goes to such ease, but it comes it brings along certain restrictions because of the sophistication carries a bit of restriction speaking, in turn, has a negative, knock-on effect on flexibility and profitability.

(ASM 1)

In the Forex industry, it is crucial to maintain flexible and customer-friendly strategies to increase competitive advantage. Indeed, without the IT department's support, Company A cannot execute its business strategies effectively. However, it is important to ensure that key business strategies are first determined, and they are supported by internal subordinate strategies (i.e., IT strategies). One of the participants argued that the new IT strategies and policies are governing the business strategy which poses a great risk of losing customers as the bureau cannot attend customers based on their best judgements thus requiring major improvements in current strategies. For example:

[...] generally, the whole purpose of foreign exchange is to gain and keep a competitive advantage. So in our situation, in terms of competitive advantage, I don't fully agree with that. Because of the current strategic practices, the flexibility in terms of operating in a branch that IT is governing our business and we are being restricted in many numbers of avenues. So, because of that, there's less flexibility and in this day and age, flexibility is the key because customers have different requirements from one to the other. Yes, so there's more of a blanket programme running for, which is not meeting all the customer demands.

(BM 4)

An analyst who has been employed in Company A for more than 15 years and specialises in business and IT strategies believes that strategic alignment and customer satisfaction are interrelated. Business strategy and IT strategy must be strategically aligned to support customer Forex demands on time and failure to do so can result in a negative impact on overall business performance and revenue streams. It was noted that due to IT technical faults and slower customer services, branches have lost a substantial portion of revenues. For example:

There is a 100% positive connection between strategic alignment and customer reactions. [...] there is a worrying part saying increasing 45% of customers are not satisfied with the services we are providing. Some categories mentioned due to longer time in the customer waiting queue they changed their mind of exchanging currencies. [...] worryingly, 70% mentioned in all customer responses the designated branch was closed due to system problems when they arrive at the location.

(ITBA 1)

In the data, it was evident that a lack of formal assessments and regular improvements for organisational strategies can cause severe disruption for Forex operations. IT director's response also creates further questions regarding Company A's strategic alignment procedure. According to him, senior management do not consider improvements for Company A's strategies, rather they focus on maintaining them. Moreover, the IT director also admitted there is no current procedure to assess if there is any gap in the business and IT strategies of Company A. For example:

Correct, there is no assessing procedure at the moment. It's not only the bureau we have to be concerned, but there are also many other business firms in the group.

(ITD)

Based on the above discussions, it was noted that the lack of regular assessments and improvements of organisational strategies can negatively influence strategic alignment and organisational performance.

4.2.3. IT governance maturity

This research also revealed that IT government maturity is another essential factor for achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. In the case company, the governance structure was changed due to an acquisition that took place in 2016. During the interviews, the participants noted that due to a lack of IT governance structures and a lengthy decision-making process for allocating necessary IT resources, the organisation failed to achieve some of its key organisational strategies such as delivering exceptional services to customers. In fact, due to a lack of pre-established structures, the case company had to delay its operations which also caused a severe impact on organisational revenues; this was mentioned by one of the area support managers as stated below:

...and if we require any, any resources or any IT related services, we have to go through an entire path, where we do the reporting and up to the level where the problem is resolved, is that quite a

bit length, which delays the whole process. So, we are a bit lagging behind when it comes to rapid requirements. We, more often losing customers' transactions clearly.

(ASM 1)

BM5 also echoed the view of ASM 1.

I have requested many times, but still, the IT department didn't approve new computers for till positions. Two computers running in Windows XP and the CPU is very old... So with the best conclusion, I am not sure that this IT strategy is matching our business goals.

(BM 5)

In the past, Company A's IT governance structure used to be very generic in practice where branch managers could expect IT solutions or resources made available within the same day or in a few days. However, Company A now has to follow the current IT governance structure; where there are more people involved to finalise a single IT decision thus creating a disruption to branch operations.

many branch managers complained to us formally and informally in branch meetings that the current IT plan is not considering branch operations on time. Further, they said that current IT strategies and plan is consuming more time in branch operations putting customers into angry situations.

(ASM 2)

The current IT governance structure in Company A is not customer friendly as there is less flexibility on business and IT strategic decisions thus affecting the quality of services. Besides, the current IT governance process is lengthy hence supportive for branch operations for delivering exceptional services. One of the branch managers perceived that current strategic IT decisions are not aligned with strategic branch decisions as there is a disconnection between two departments in strategic decision-making processes.

I feel that the IT governance should be more customer focus. Now we are a bit restricted in certain functions, which in turn bounces back on the actual revenue that we are generating at a branch level. So the IT vision, I believe it's to do with the IT strategic team that needs to understand what is happening inside the branches and I think there's a bit of a disconnect there.

(BM 4)

Bureau's area managers and IT directors play major roles in determining IT governance structure, thus their feedback in relation to Company A's current IT governance systems were sought

during the interviews. The area manager in the sample believes that over-openness of strategic decisions can pose challenges as having certain restrictions on information access is extremely important and argued there is no fault in doing such action. He asserted that maintaining certain restrictions can help to protect the organisation from the potential external threats.

Branch managers have access to certain information at the branch. The reason because we have to maintain high network security protocols. We have received many reports saying many branches are infected with viruses and spam emails by visiting other different websites. So for that reason, we have limited their information access for security reasons. But I don't think that's a big deal.

(AM)

Nonetheless, it is evident that due to inflexible and lengthy IT governance structure bureau faced major disruptions to its Forex operations thus reducing organisational performance. However, the IT director asserted that there is no such need for changing current IT governance because there is no evidence that it disrupts case firm operations. For example:

Current IT strategies and goals are very sharp and specific in the group. We have provided an IT infrastructure that is supportive for business operations as this is the foundation stone in the group business. Importantly there are many business entities in the group not only the retail Forex division so therefore, any infrastructure or changes to the current IT governance structure require strong evidence which we have not found yet.

(ITD)

Although a clear negative impact of a lack of IT governance structure on strategic alignment and business process was seen in the sample, the senior managers asserted that the current practices are adequate. Nonetheless, the other participants did not share their views and argued that a clear IT governance structure is necessary for enhancing organisational performance and achieving strategic alignment.

4.2.4. Scope and architecture of the IT maturity

In the responses of the participant, it was observed that the maturity of scope and architecture of IT also plays an important role in achieving strategic alignment. Company A was facing several strategic challenges due to a lack of adequate equipment that is fit for organizational use. In order to address these problems and thereby to be able to achieve organisational goals, Company A has recently invested in sophisticated IT infrastructure and technology. However, the new technology is yet to be synchronised in the business processes and hence there remains

difficulties for achieving organisational strategies. This was seen in the response of one of the area support managers.

...again, it's a bit of a yes and no answer I would have to give you. Now see the corporate organisation has invested quite heavily in quite a sophisticated IT infrastructure and technology. Well, the problem is, it's not so much about the capabilities of the IT infrastructure. It's about aligning that with our group's branches' business strategy. There is a bit of a gap between the two. So, which has a negative impact on our day-to-day business and overall business strategy as a whole. So I would say, delivering the company goals the target and daily work routines - so there's a bit of an issue that we are facing, as opposed to a couple of issues that we are facing. Because of the whole practices that are in place and which are not synchronized with the business strategy.

(ASM 1)

The Forex industry is extremely competitive and providing excellent customer service is important for the success of every Forex firm. Adequate IT infrastructures and network systems allow businesses to provide exceptional experiences for Forex customers. One of the branch managers highlighted that due to major incompatibilities in the current IT infrastructure branches of Company A cannot operate smoothly, thus building an excellent customer relationship is difficult. For example.

But, at the moment, [...] because of the IT infrastructure and IT practices and the regulations surrounding that, I mean the way we work right now...unfortunately I can't fully agree that we meet the standards. So, the customer service is, in my opinion, it's too fold and it's how you present plus what services we offer because they're not there to, you know, build a relationship with the people.

(BM 4)

It was noted in the sample that due to server and infrastructure problems, all branches had to temporarily terminate serving customers on several occasions. This is because branches need active internet connections with the main servers for accessing customer information and delivering services. One of the branch managers argues that this is due to the incompetence of the IT department, which he reported to the corporate office. He shared one of his frustrating experiences regarding not being able to complete a transaction due to IT errors.

...I have personally forwarded many complaints to the corporate office regarding the service and support we are receiving right now. Once, I was with one of my good customers and he wanted to transfer some Euros to his personal bank account in France. I counted all his cash, and it was

£15,000 in the middle of the transaction, the system crashed and I could not finalise the transaction. I was speechless and I quickly called the IT department, but nobody answered the phone, even I tried the IT manager's mobile too. So this is the real scenario sometimes in my branch.

(BM 3)

Nevertheless, in general, it was observed that Forex SMEs cannot smoothly operate without having adequate IT infrastructure and support in place. Due to the issues involving the appropriateness of the IT infrastructure, Company A was unable to deliver satisfactory customer service on multiple occasions, potentially affecting consumer trust and brand reputation negatively. It is anticipated that not being able to deliver the promise to customers adversely affects Company A's long term organisational strategies.

Prior to developing any strategies, organisations should analyse their current data to find what is missing in their systems and what is needed for future business growth. One of the business-IT analysts in Company A highlighted that the current infrastructure is not compatible with Company A's business requirements, thus further assessment and improvements are necessary to enhance strategic alignment. For example:

We noticed that in business performance analysts' reports there is a clear line of lower business performance in the Forex bureau, as they have mentioned the current system's unwillingness to change according to the dynamic business environment they face.

(ITBA 1)

Based on the above observations, it was noted that a lack of adequate IT infrastructure is affecting not only the branch operations but also the process of strategic alignment. Therefore, the maturity of scope and architecture of IT was considered as one of the factors of strategic alignment for Forex SMEs.

4.2.5. Partnership maturity

One of the success factors in strategic alignment is maintaining a viable collaboration/interaction between business managers and IT managers (Reynolds and Yetton, 2015; Wu et al., 2015; Luftman, 2004). All 16 participants asserted that not only business and IT managers, but all managerial employees should collaborate and coordinate for achieving strategic alignment. One

of the branch managers perceived senior managers do not cooperate and communicate with him effectively, which he feels is a common problem the company is facing.

The area manager never joins to assist me in any IT issue or at least help me. All I'm receiving from my email replies is, 'Thank you for your email, can you please look at that issue' and he forwarded it to the IT department. This is the true reality of how senior managers corporate to branch problems.

(BM 1)

It is important that an organisation maintains a supportive environment towards achieving organisational goals. One of the branch managers highlighted that Company A is currently not maintaining a harmonious corporate relationship between business and IT managers, which has a negative impact on achieving strategic alignment. For example:

Before acquisition happened, the bureau had a quite flexible view regarding business and IT strategy alignment. Former CEO and head of IT didn't concern about higher levels of alignment in past. These two maintained a very friendly corporate partnership and that helped us in a lot of in-branch problems. That was our secret recipe in Company A. After the acquisition we don't see any senior manager in the Forex unit maintaining that kind of a partnership with IT.

(BM 3)

ASM 3 also echoed the view of BM 3.

...another learning lesson is that ordinarily there are strategic complexities between SME level and large firm level, the main example is senior executives don't act the way our former CEO worked. So due to different organisational contexts and puzzles... the success rate of achieving business and IT alignment is very lower, to be honest with you.

(ASM 3)

As it appears in the sample, the former founder/chairman maintained a good friendship with the IT manager which helped Company A's overall business and IT implementation structure. Both parties clearly understood about Forex operations which helped them when designing appropriate IT plans and business plans. One of the branch managers postulated that due to a lack of interactions between business managers and IT managers, overall, IT performance does not appear to fully support business strategies.

Sometimes we have to face major server errors and network disruptions during peak hours, and you know what...IT department without informing branch managers ran unplanned IT maintenance on the IT mainframe, every branch system was temporarily shut down. Once I spoke

to the area manager regarding this inconvenience, he said the IT department didn't inform him either. I don't know what's happening here.

(BM 7)

This may have been due to the conflicts between business managers and IT managers in Company A. One of the participants stated that almost half of branch managers are not following IT policies and procedures as they believe it is not in harmony with the main business strategies.

For example:

Company A is very strict on the implementation of their business strategies, and we noticed there is a tension between IT executives, and they are not supportive of what the bureau is seeking to achieve. We noticed there were many IT conflict situations in branch operations and almost half of the branch managers were not following current IT policies and procedures. I spent a great amount of time reading and listening to branch managers' and area support managers' feedback as they confirmed current IT procedures for IT resources are not equally distributed.

(ITBA 1)

As can be observed, there seems to be a rivalry between the IT department and business department in Company A. This has led to managers prioritising their egos above the overall business interests. IT director highlighted that he found maintaining a mutual understanding with executive board members, area managers and the CEO difficult, which has delayed the decision-making processes, impacted strategic alignment negatively, and affected the firm's performance negatively.

...to resolve the problem we have is, CEOs, executive members and senior area managers need to understand that simply having a digital strategy certainly is not the most supportive and it will not be giving an answer. Getting them to understand this is a major problem I face. When we cannot coordinate and talk openly, we cannot develop strategies that are consistent in achieving the organisational objectives.

(ITD)

Therefore, based on the above discussions, it is determined that the maturity or cross-departmental partnership is essential for achieving a good alignment of organisational strategies.

4.2.6. Skills maturity

During the analysis of the data, it was noted that skills maturity also plays an important role in determining a forex SMEs' strategic alignment. In the case of Company A, it was observed that

in some areas, employees did not have the necessary skills to cope with newly introduced systems. For an instance, when a new FxPOS system was introduced, accessing Company A's IT network was made more difficult by introducing new restrictions. Although these new measures were introduced to enhance the security of the network, a lack of appropriate training of employees, made knowledge sharing more difficult and affected the service delivery processes of the organisation. Strategic alignment is a comprehensive procedure; thus, to achieve it, employees should be well trained and matured for the procedure (Venkatraman and Fahd, 2018).

I feel like in the current strategy, there are a lot more procedures now. Lots more training is required for maintaining business standards but sadly we are not getting enough training to do our job. Initially, I was trained to do a simple job, but now I can see that my job is getting complex and complex. The company needs to introduce more face-to-face training to motivate ourselves.

(BM 3)

BM 4 mentioned that, though senior management introduced its improved advanced system to the bureau, it did not improve any overall performance in his branch, but it only reduced the employees' performance. Which made it difficult to achieve his branch's objectives.

I feel at the branch level, for achieving the sales targets, there are few challenges because of the particular IT system that we are using at the moment and the governance that's surrounding the IT system. So, as a branch manager, I feel that our efficiency has been decreased because of the new systems and procedures.

(BM 4)

An organisation in the foreign exchange industry depend highly on their information systems as they need to access the latest information about currency rates that fluctuate every second. In order to be able to succeed in such a marketplace, organisations not only need reliable and efficient infrastructures but also adequate skills to operate them, Therefore, based on the responses of the participants, it is concluded that skill maturity plays a critical role in achieving departmental objectives and thereby achieving strategic alignment.

4.2.7. Web (Internet) systems maturity

In addition to the six factors of SAMM, the analysis of the data also revealed another factor 'Web (Internet) systems maturity' that is essential for achieving strategic alignment of Forex SMEs. As aforementioned, Forex SMEs extensively rely on the information available on the

Internet for setting their rates. In the particular context of Company A, they need to communicate regularly with other branches so that all branches have the same rates available at the same time. Besides, in terms of processing consumer transactions, active internet connectivity is essential as it requires instant coordination with other external parties such as banks. Besides, similar to other Forex SMEs, Company A also used cloud-based systems that need to be accessed each time consumer account is accessed. Therefore, in the lack of active and reliable web systems, Forex companies cannot function. In a present corporate environment, organisations and markets fully depend on the latest information thus, requiring stable internet bandwidth to access them (Kitisios and Kamariotou, 2019; Wetering et al., 2017). Internet, thus, is a critical success factor for a modern organisation's success (Chan et al., 2019). The area manager of Company A in the sample highlighted that the whole bureau is integrated with IP phones and on some occasions due to internet outages, the bureau's communication and security systems were disabled.

I have to admit that, because of these internet issues company had to face major problems in communication systems. This was addressed in branch meetings, and I have highlighted these issues as a top priority in our executive board meetings. The whole company is equipped with IP phones, and we have designed secure IP addresses to maintain a secure environment. If there is an internet disruption insecure lines, whole company operations will be affected as we won't be able to communicate with any branch managers or access security camera systems remotely.

(AM)

The main trading system (FxPOS) of Company A is an online cloud-based system and it requires higher bandwidth of internet connection to fully connect with the main server. In addition, Company A operates other web systems as well, further requiring higher internet bandwidth. One of the branch managers concluded that due to lower internet bandwidth and unreliable internet connections branch systems crashed multiple times and many customers were lost.

This system, FxPOS is a fully cloud-based online system. The management designed it that way, so there is no heavy installation setup in our computers. But they need a huge bandwidth internet line separately. In every branch, we have a WU payment gateway, global bank payment systems, security camera systems and our email systems. All these systems consume lots of bandwidth, so trading systems can't sometimes operate and end up crashing. In a lack of robust web systems, we cannot complete our daily activities.

(BM 6)

Due to internet connectivity issues, company A not only struggled to communicate across the organisations but also lost significant business opportunities. One of the branch managers in the sample highlighted this:

I can tell you an incident that happened years back before COVID-19 happened. One of the corporate clients in my branch ordered 50,000 USD for his business trip to the USA. The day he approached us, branch internet service is gone and there was no internet. I spoke to the area manager and IT manager to get the internet back online because I already complained about internet problems before, they are investigating the issues on that day, so there was nothing we can do for that customer. We lost over £40,000 worth of a transaction due to an internet problem.

(BM 5)

The financial industry must maintain comprehensive robust regulations in order to maintain integrity in financial transactions. Since the Forex industry is operating under the financial industry, every Forex firm must adhere to current government regulations. On one occasion, Company A failed to comply with government regulations due to internet systems failure. One of the branch managers stated that he was unable to transfer necessary information to government authorities due to issues with internet connectivity.

The UK government have advised that we have to maintain physical documents when a customer trades a large amount of Forex. Every 6 months we have to upload any customer evidence if HMRC requests it. There is a secure system where we can transfer this information to government authorities. But once I couldn't send all urgent evidence because suddenly the whole branch network went down because of internet issues. All our security camera systems, WU terminals, online London Forex spot rates trading systems everything collapsed in a second.

(BM 2)

Hence, based on the responses of the participants, it is concluded that web systems maturity is important for completing a Forex SME's daily activities and communicating within the organisations and thereby achieving strategic alignment.

4.3. Challenges faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment

An analysis of the interview transcripts revealed numerous challenges faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment. The identified challenges are categorised in six themes as discussed below:

4.3.1. Lack of senior leadership's support and commitment

Company A has a company structure where senior leadership need to approve all strategic decisions of the company. Managers are unable to finalise or correct a specific course of action to secure immediate business opportunities. This has reduced organisational flexibility. ASM1 feels that this has led to a reduction in sales.

We cannot mention actual figures due to HR regulations, but I can say there's a 15% sales drop every year when correlating the final figures before the acquisition. There's not much input from my side for the final decisions. The whole senior team needs to agree on decisions, not just me.

(ASM 1)

The senior leadership of the company also appears to be not recognising the important role IT plays in ensuring the company's operations are smooth, as noted by ASM3 and ASM 2.

Well, another is...senior team apparently, they don't consider IT issues as a serious problem in the company....to them 'system-down' means a common issue.

(ASM 3)

...they view IT in the company, as a specific mechanic tool, not as a higher priority. This understanding should change.

(ASM 2)

As stated by the branch manager above, it is clear that senior leadership is not fully dedicated to supporting the bureau's branch manager's business requests. Thus, decreasing branch efficiency and performance. The lack of commitment from the senior leadership towards the improvement of the IT department has directly impacted Company A's operations environment. Not only the senior leadership but also the senior management, according to branch managers, are unsupportive. For example:

Senior management will not approve any petty cash claims for branches. Honestly, I like their approaches but in the long run, because of their heavy business culture is somewhat I feel reducing branch revenues and... Forex trading services as we have to adhere to their guidelines first - even business approvals are very tougher - getting a red flag for card transactions sometimes gives them a heart attack.

(BM 7)

I have worked in the company for many years, and I know for a fact that our senior team members don't have a clear knowledge about how this foreign exchange industry works, and how our bureau operates. Their support on changing any organisational policies which we know it's going to be positive for branch...but they won't down their attitudes. Rarely do they visit my branch and ask for their support.

(BM 4)

One of the IT directors also noted the lack of support from senior leadership as he perceives that they are not supportive of new changes as it incurs extra costs.

A difficult challenge is chief executives' positiveness and forwardness about the strategic integration procedure in the group is not at a satisfactory level. Although they supported my IT vision. However, I have to give them extra lessons about what is integration good and bad in it. For example, they are not somewhat keen on hearing IT budget and increments though. So, director board knowledge is unquestionably important.

(ITD)

Therefore, it is concluded that the lack of commitment from both the senior leadership as well as senior managers has resulted in departments not being able to conduct necessary improvements as doing so incurs extra costs. Therefore the lack of senior management support and commitment is identified as one of the challenges faced by Company A in terms of achieving strategic alignment.

4.3.2. Lack of coordination between IT department and business managers

In the sample, it appeared that the IT department and business managers were not effectively coordinating. Which prevented them from achieving shared organisational goals such as increasing revenues and delivering exceptional services to customers. One of the participants highlighted that due to unplanned IT maintenance branch operations was once halted for over 30 minutes. For example:

...they carried out unplanned IT maintenance in the main server and networks, so when this happens, we have to temporarily close the branch for at least 30 minutes. This is integration failure actually because all these IT maintenances happening from Ireland where our London senior management not aware of. IT developers and testers run IT maintenance without telling senior management.

(BM 7)

Another branch manager found it difficult to deal with the IT department as his requests to upgrade IT equipment were ignored.

Some of my branch machines and printers are so old, and I have contacted IT folks and managers and still, I have not received any productive response from them.

(BM 2)

Business managers and IT managers should share mutual understanding between them in order to support overall business performance. The business and IT judgement process must be equally balanced, and a lack of such balance can lead to business inefficiencies and lower performances.

For example:

The IT resources and distribution is done by the corporate management unit at the top level. [...] They have to come through that entire hierarchy of the corporate sector, which, more often than not, is quite complex and time-consuming. They look into different outcomes or different ways of doing things, so the response time is quite lengthy.

(ASM 1)

Currently, there is a lack of coordination between the IT department and business managers in Company A, which has posed significant challenges in achieving strategic alignment.

4.3.3. Resistance to change culture

During the analysis of the data, it was also noted that, following the acquisition, many new changes were proposed. However, the staff appeared to be unwilling to change, which posed substantial challenges for achieving organisational objectives. One of the senior managers stated that after the acquisition senior management have implemented new business and IT systems and procedures that the staffs felt as sophisticated and unfriendly to the SME environment. Employees of Company A have not settled well yet to this new environment and it is a slow ongoing process.

...when the corporate business unit took over they were overwhelmed with the entire system changes, there were few new IT platforms, IT services introduced, and corporate regulations introduced this and that. So there was quite a bit of change that was taking place. So because of that some of the staff members that, there are issues in fine-tuning to this whole new technological platform. We have been noticed by many branch managers and a few Forex

advisors spoke to us directly about their opinions on this new alignment change or getting updated well, it's a slow ongoing process.

(ASM 1)

Another senior manager highlighted senior staff members are unwilling to change into new working culture. He also believed that their personal change acceptance behaviour is the issue.

For example:

Well, we do have a few of our old staffers who have difficulties in adapting to new IT and business changes. That is a bit understandable. Even with the right IT systems, they are still in a position not to change their previous ways. So basically there is debate about human expectations in the company.

(ASM 3)

Two participants highlighted that, presently, there is no comprehensive business-IT training in Company A, therefore employees are nervous about adapting to new changes. Also, Company A employs employees from diverse cultures who have a different level of understanding regarding the work behaviour, hence they need to be trained differently. Providing employees with comprehensive new training might reduce their level of resistance towards new changes and adapt to new environments easily.

I have staffers from Sri Lanka, India, Japan and Africa. Different working cultures, it's hard to understand their views. Some of them still don't like working with the new system, they hate it. Everyone's views are completely different, some ok to go... some not..so for them it's a challenge but, for me it's not.

(BM 7)

many branch managers are not familiarising with social conversation maybe because the culture of their origins is not British. So they are more cheeky in speaking. Well, if we can re-assess our training procedures and add further training maybe there is a possibility they might find these business-IT platforms easy. We haven't given them thorough training sessions that's why they are resistant to change in the bureau.

(BITA 2)

The area manager, however, noted that it is important to understand the differences and respect them. He also asserted that most of the staff in company A are suitably trained.

So we need to.. we keep our differences we maintain that within ourselves anyway. I mean, most of our staff members will be suitably trained, and then suitably informed on what changes will be done, prior to them actually happening to avoid any confusion or misunderstanding. Overall, this is why sometimes hard to run a company when experienced staff members trust their guts rather than the company procedures, even everything in order.

(AM)

Nevertheless, it was clear in the interview transcripts that employees' unwillingness to change was one of the strategic challenges faced by company A.

4.3.4. Slow decision making due to stringent company policies

Rapid decision making in an organisation increases efficiency, customer satisfaction and organisational performance. Company A's productivity and efficiency depend on its business-IT decision-making procedures. Company A's main business portfolio is Forex trading and any delays in crucial decisions can cost lots of money for the firm. Bureau was acquired by another firm in 2016 thus, they have introduced further policies and procedures to the existing organisation hierarchy. One of the branch managers argued that due to long delays in business and IT decisions his branch is not as efficient as before.

I have to expect more and more papers and procedures which they introduced to branches every month or every year. This is much more time consuming, and this reduced our work interest at some level because of the higher workload I am already bearing as a branch manager.

(BM 2)

Due to new restrictions introduced by the senior management, overall branch profitability and performances have been reduced. Branch managers are required to obtain certain additional approvals from the IT department and senior area management, for certain business-IT decisions. One of the branch managers conceded that it affected the service delivery process.

So branch stock limits, insurance limits, and buy and sell order limits, we can't buy as much as we want now. It's all controlled now; borderlines are marked by accounts departments. Even to get new IT machines and tools we need to wait till they confirm us. It's good they try to comply with all decisions fairly but the business has lost its position.

(BM 1)

One of the senior members in the analyst team highlights that, though Company A's business goals and strategies are well communicated with the corporate members generally, the bureau requires freedom to make Forex decisions by their selves. The new policies restrict such flexibilities.

Bureau business plan is clearly explained to all stakeholders in the organisation. By understanding what customers' needs are, what market needs are, and how Company A committed to customer foreign exchange services are clearly explained. As we are going through some branch managers' comments, complaints, we noticed they expect higher organisational space and adaptability to their branch operational tasks. The problem is this can be contradicted with parent firm organisational policies.

(BITA 1)

The area manager also acknowledged that due to complex organisational policies and procedures, organisational performance can be reduced.

So taking the green light from the board is not an easy deal these days. Their decision approval procedures are very complicated and mainly for new IT computers and equipment they are not easily approving those. Same for extending any financial support.

(AM)

Therefore, slow decision making due to stringent company policies was identified as another challenge faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment.

4.3.5. Knowledge and Skills Deficit

Achieving strategic alignment is a complex process and requires thorough knowledge regarding what steps need to be taken during each step of strategic alignment. The Forex industry is volatile in nature; therefore knowledgeable and experienced managers are required to achieve strategic alignment. One of the branch managers highlighted that senior management is not well experienced in the Forex industry; thus achieving strategic alignment is a difficult task for Company A.

From my position, I can provide as much information to senior management. But the problem is, senior management is not well experienced in the Forex field therefore they don't know how to achieve strategic alignment.

(BM 7)

Similarly, another branch manager shared the same understanding as BM 7 highlighted above.

Yes, we need a strategically aligned business strategy and IT strategy to expand Forex operations. But senior management doesn't have a robust understanding and proper skill set to achieve strategic alignment.

(BM 8)

A strategically aligned organisation can enjoy enhanced organisation performance and profitability. However, to achieve strategic alignment business managers and IT managers must have the required knowledge and experiences specific to Forex bureaus. One of the branch managers argued that most IT employees in the IT department are not well experienced in the Forex industry; thus they do not have good knowledge and skill set to identify Company A's business requirements.

I am not sure whether our IT guys have worked in a Forex company; before joining us. Well if they have worked in a Forex company they understand branch managers' stress and expectation much more clearly. This is the main challenge why SMEs like us cannot achieve strategic alignment.

(BM 5)

However, one of the area support managers highlighted that strategic alignment is not a single person's decision; every senior manager should agree on all strategic decisions when achieving strategic alignment.

I understand what is required for Company A, but I cannot guarantee strategic alignment success because every senior business and IT manager's view and understanding level is completely different. There are many voices on the table, and they have different knowledge levels, unfortunately.

(ASM 2)

Nevertheless, SMEs, in general, tend to be affected by skill and knowledge limitations due to the smaller size of their organisations as well as their limited presence in the market. Therefore knowledge and skills deficit is identified as another challenge faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment.

4.3.6. Lack of Sufficient Financial Resources

In general, every financial organisation requires stable financial resources to survive in the volatile business environment. One of the branch managers in the sample highlighted that due to a lack of budget approvals, Company A is struggling to achieve certain business goals and targets.

I noticed one thing that due to lack of money problems they hesitate to approve branch IT facilities. I had to push so much to get new computers for my branch because we lost so many customers due to IT faults.

(BM 5)

The IT manager highlighted that the IT director was not keen on approving IT equipment purchases due to financial constraints.

We are receiving many emails from branch managers asking for new computers, scanners and cash counting machines every month. But it is extremely difficult to approve those because the IT director not giving me green light to purchase those. He said other board members not granting expanding IT budget.

(ITM)

In addition, one of the analysts in Company A mentioned that due to lack of financial resources, they cannot fund research and development programmes, which is essential for understanding market needs and thereby achieving strategic alignment.

We are still waiting for approval of the analyst budget, but still, the senior department has not approved it for us. So, unfortunately, we cannot proceed with important research and development projects which are truly important for alignment projects.

(BITA 1)

Therefore, it was concluded that the lack of financial resources was posing difficulties in the process of achieving strategic alignment in Company A.

4.4. Achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business and IT strategy of a Forex SME

4.4.1. Effective cross-department communication and coordination

An analysis of the interview transcripts revealed that effective cross-department communication is essential for achieving harmonious alignment of IT and business strategy in the context of Company A. Participants in the sample stated that, due to lack of effective communication, departments were unable to understand the problems faced by other departments and hence unable to respond appropriately. This can result in the organisational output being delayed and eventually the overall performance of the organisation being negatively impacted. The IT manager stated that due to the lack of support from the human resource department, they were unable to complete essential daily tasks.

Once, three of our staffs left suddenly around the same time without any notice and immediately requested the HR to recruit someone new as it was a peak season. However, HR did not proceed with the recruitment process right after receiving our request. This put us in an extremely difficult situation as we were unable to even complete our daily tasks.

(ITM)

An area support manager shared a similar view in regard to not getting essential funding approved from the IT and finance department, which severely delayed meeting customer orders deadlines. For example:

Communication practices with the corporate unit are difficult as I see it, there is a disagreement about Forex's business understanding. I remember, we requested important branch computers and cash counting machines for two of our North London branches, but our IT and finance unit managers did not approve the request. They said, they will transfer some unused computers to the branch, but those machines are very inefficient for Forex trading.

(ASM 3)

The lack of coordination was also evident in the case of the IT department. One of the senior managers highlighted that the entire communications across the entire organisation were being disrupted for a whole day due to the lack of coordination from the IT department.

We can't coordinate with the IT server maintenance procedures, it's normally done by the IT department side. Once, without informing me or any of the London area support team, the IT

department shutdown the entire network grid for urgent maintenance. We understand, those maintenances are crucial, but they should inform us in advance, so we can coordinate with branch managers and customer orders.

(ASM 1)

Nonetheless, there was also evidence of good communication and coordination between different departments of Company A. In one instance, when branch staff was sick due to illness, the manager was struggling with staff shortage in the back-office operations, the AML department supported by sending one of their staffs to the Forex business unit. For example:

I never expect such courtesy from our AML department. In my branch every day we cash count and transfer between 50,000 to 65,000 worth of sterling. Two back-office staff members reported they can't come to work because they are not feeling well, so I approved sick leave for them. I was short with two staff members and quickly I called the area manager about the morning rush. AML manager approved two of his staff members to my branch immediately.

(BM 5)

As observed, effective cross-department communication and coordination assisted departments to achieve their objectives in a timely manner. Where there was no coordination, the performance of the entire organisation along with the departments deteriorated. Thus, effective cross-department communication and coordination are identified as a critical success factor for achieving strategic alignment between business strategy and IT strategy in a Forex SME.

4.4.2. Management knowledge and commitment

It was also observed in the sample that senior management knowledge and commitment is critical to have a harmonious strategic alignment of business strategies and IT strategies. Generally, senior management of an organisation decides the strategic pathway of the firm. The Senior management determines organisational vision and mission. One of the participants in the sample noted that some of the members of the senior management team do not have experience of how Forex SMEs operate, rather they are focusing on sales performance. The participant elaborated that they failed to understand sales performance is a result of the successful alignment of key business strategies and subordinate business strategies

The retail director is independent in the group and he is only looking at sales performance. In fact, he does not have any idea or thing of knowledge about IT or making strategic decisions.

(ASM 1)

Compared to other industries in the UK, the Forex industry is one of the booming and crucial industry since it generates a large sum of money to the economy each year. Further, London is one of the main Forex trading hubs in the world. Forex market is dynamic in nature hence, the more experienced employees are most valuable to Company A when developing strategic business and IT plans. One of the branch managers highlighted that, upper management does not have thorough work experience in the Forex industry thus, their strategies do not enhance Company A's performance.

[...] Forex is a very fast-paced, very fast-moving business and it needs a lot of flexibility and operational knowledge which you don't find in corporate bodies or strategies. To answer what you asked me is that corporate bodies should be aware of how to support each other with SMEs and they should have thorough knowledge about how SME's business vision runs and what they expect from the IT vision in simple words.

(BM 4)

Employees who are working in lower or middle management are always encouraged to contact their senior managers when they encounter any problem at work. By doing so, employees believe their senior managers might involve and committed to solving their issues at work rapidly. One of the branch managers conceded that current management is not committed to solving their business and IT problems at branch level.

Oh yes, many, many, many, many times. I have raised so many issues at branch meetings and I have personally forwarded an email to the board as well, but unfortunately, the governance level don't accept...don't understand these problems.

(BM 1)

Strategic alignment is a high-level management area thus, requires some exposure to the academic literature to understand it thoroughly. Senior managers with higher education qualification might contribute to effective strategic decision making at work. One of the participants recommended that senior management having relevant academic qualifications can improve the process of strategic alignment.

... do the people who are in the top seats have enough academic knowledge on how to execute strategic decisions mainly between a larger organisation and a smaller organisation. I don't think so...

(BM 2)

In the sample, participants demonstrated how the knowledge and commitment of management contributes positively to successful strategic alignment. They also explained how the lack of such knowledge contributed to poor coordination and poor strategic alignment in Company A. Therefore, based on the findings of this research, it is noted that management knowledge and commitment is critical to achieving strategic alignment of business strategies such as IT strategy and key business strategy.

4.4.3. Appropriate distribution of organisational resources

In the sample, it was also noted that the appropriate distribution of organisational resources plays a critical role in determining the harmonious alignment of business strategies and IT strategies. This is because strategies cannot be executed if adequate resources are not available for translating strategies into action. In the case of Company A, participants stated that they were unable to achieve departmental objectives due to the lack of adequate IT equipment.

This is a very troublesome problem I have to face. Whenever, I request new computers, scanners and cash counting machines, I have to give lots of reasons and answers to get it approved. We cannot chase branch targets and customer numbers if, the IT department does not approve new computers and equipment to my branch.

(BM 4)

In most stages, we identified that most south London branches are lacking new IT machines and utilities. Some branch managers are nervous to speak to the IT department and they believe that speaking to them gets unnecessary attention from the corporate sector.

(BITA 2)

Having equipment is alone not enough, it is necessary to train people to appropriately use them as well. One of the branch managers stated that some of the equipment is not installed because no one knows how to use the new system properly.

We received extra 3 computers and 2 PDQ card payment machines and they are in the stock room for the last 3 years, I guess.

(BM 6)

It is indeed necessary to understand the specific requirements of different branches and address them appropriately by distributing organisation resources in a balanced manner. A regular audit can be a good way to understand what the needs of different departments within an organisation are. By having formal IT assessments, the IT department can have a good understanding regarding the current IT resources efficiency and its supportive nature towards Forex operations. One of the senior managers highlighted, Company A does not have formal IT assessments regularly.

Normally, to my understanding, the IT manager should approve IT assessments in all branches, but he won't. I believe I have addressed this concern in corporate meetings in Hammersmith, that we should maintain formal IT audits or any assessment criteria to balance branch IT needs.

(ASM1)

Financial resources are also equally important to sustain a business. Company A is still operating under SME standards and allocation of all organisational resources, especially financial resources, must be approved by the senior leadership. All 16 interview participants agreed that the current allocation of resources by senior leadership is not appropriate to address the organisation's needs.

When we compared to 10 or 15 years back, our former Founder approved any financial decision or resources if it's important to the business. He never hesitated. Even he gave the authority to his senior management to approve any financial decision if the business badly needed it. In the current picture, I don't have the authority now, most financial decisions are been rejected. One of north London branch had cement wall damaged in the safe room, it took nearly 1 year to get it to approve.

(AM)

Overall, based on the analysis of the data, it can be summarised that effective allocation of organisational resources allows departments such as IT to achieve their departmental objectives, which subsequently helps in achieving the overall organisational objective.

4.4.4. Regular training and development of front-line staffs

Well trained and knowledgeable employees are a great resource for any organisation. Company A is an SME and currently, it employs between 100 to 150 individuals. One of the area support

managers explained that current employee training procedures do not help employees enhance their understanding of work in the Forex sector. This has caused difficulties related to employees receiving instructions clearly and completing tasks appropriately.

Now, this training was done by the corporate body with very little guidance on it. How it happened was first they trained the senior management which is us, the area management of Company A, myself, the other area support managers and the area manager trained on the new system changes that are coming into play and especially how it will impact Company A's current business strategies. And then in turn we had to provide instructions and we actually had to relay that to the entire branch network which was a very cumbersome process. Because we couldn't reach to all the branches in time - to train all the staff in person so we had to manage it through other modes of communication like telephone or email or things of that sort.

(ASM 1)

Indeed, understanding new significant changes in business and IT procedures can be difficult for employees and require some time to adapt and digest thoroughly. The bureau's senior management introduced an advanced sophisticated Forex trading system since the current system "Fed\$" was obsolete and vulnerable to cyber-attacks. Employee training means providing employees with vital information about current systems and organisational procedures.

There should be proper formal training offered to the staff so that they can, they have enough time to learn it, and then practice it in the branch. Now what has happened is, as in real-time while serving customers in their till my staff have to learn while they are doing their job.

(BM 4)

Branch managers are well-experienced however, they are saying new staff members find the system is not very friendly and flexible. They are asking me to put them into further training.

(BM 7)

Therefore, after considering the above, insufficient training procedures in Company A was leading to employees not understanding and not completing their tasks fully. Besides, senior employees such as managers did not have a total understanding of the rationale for new changes, this created confusion. Hence, it was noted that regular training and development of frontline staffs is critical to achieving short term organisational objectives and thereby contributing to long term strategic alignment.

4.5. Outcomes of Strategic Alignment

An analysis of the research data revealed that when organisations achieve strategic alignment they benefit in numerous ways. One of the area managers of Company A stated that when there is an alignment of IT and business strategies, the *competitiveness* of the organisation increases and SMEs become more capable of grasping market opportunities. For example:

I believe that by ensuring there is a good alignment of business and IT strategies, we can improve our competitive status in the market.

(ASM 2)

Similarly, AM also echoed the view of ASM 2.

After the acquisition we have integrated so many systems and procedures to Company A; therefore we have to find rigid equilibrium between our Forex operations and new systems. On most occasions, we cannot beat our competitor's services and products. However, if we can achieve this balance, we will certainly be more competitive.

(AM)

Similarly, if a Forex SME has achieved its strategic alignment, business operations improve, and they can win *consumer trust*. Two branch managers in the sample stated that when there is an alignment of business strategy and IT strategy, employees can address consumer needs better, and hence achieve higher consumer satisfaction and trust. For example:

I think most customers lost faith in us because we are facing more IT failures or website issues. And we have received more customer complaints via Trust pilot and Google than ever before; most of them actually regarding delays in business and IT.

(BM 5)

Customer expects their Forex orders to be completed on time and they don't want to hear any excuses because they cannot change their travel plans. I think if we are able to align business strategy and IT strategy completely; definitely, we can win consumers' hearts and trust.

(BM 8)

Moreover, if a Forex SME has achieved its strategic alignment, Forex monthly targets can be achieved and overall *organisational performance* is improved. One of the business-IT analysts in the sample stated that when alignment between business strategy and IT strategy is achieved,

Company A can successfully achieve its monthly targets and attend customer orders more effectively; hence improved organisational performance can be achieved. For example:

Of course, there cannot be any doubts or confusion because I know for a fact that; if our business strategy and IT strategy are fully integrated, each and every branch manager able to achieve its monthly targets assigned by the retail team. When business and IT are integrated; Company A's organisational performance will be extraordinary.

(BITA 1)

Therefore, it is concluded that, if Forex firm achieves strategic alignment their competitive advantage, customer trust and organisational performance can be improved.

4.6. Conclusions

This chapter presented the research findings. The qualitative research data collected from 16 employees of Company A were analysed by following the procedures outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) whilst also utilising NVivo 12. The analysis revealed that factors such as communication maturity, competency maturity, IT governance maturity, scope and architecture of the IT maturity, partnership maturity, skills maturity, and web systems maturity play critical roles in terms of achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. Besides, this research also revealed numerous challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment. They include lack of senior management commitment, lack of coordination between departments, resistance to change culture, and slow decision-making. Finally, to achieve a harmonious alignment of IT and business strategies, it was noted that SMEs should ensure effective cross-department communication and coordination, ensure managers are knowledgeable in regard to the process of strategic alignment whilst being committed to the process, organisational resources should be distributed appropriately, and the front-line staffs of SMEs should be regularly trained. The next chapter of this thesis discusses these findings by locating them in broader contexts.

Chapter Five: Discussions

5.1. Introduction

This research investigated the factors for achieving strategic alignment within Forex SMEs along with the challenges faced by Forex SMEs for achieving cross-departmental strategic alignment. The previous chapter of the thesis reported the findings of this research upon conducting an analysis on the data collected from employees of a UK-based Forex SME. This chapter now seeks to discuss the research finding by locating them in broader contexts. Chapter Two of this thesis proposed a research conceptual framework after critically reviewing the existing literature. This chapter now seeks to propose a conceptual model by comparing the findings of the existing literature with the findings of this research in order to draw inferences. Prior to constructing a conceptual model for the research, significant findings of this research are summarised, discussed, and evaluated. Besides, contributions of the findings are also drawn in this chapter to highlight the significance to both the academic literature and the professional practice.

5.2. Exploring the factors of strategic alignment in a Forex SME

A review of the existing literature presented in Chapter 2.4.3.1 of this thesis identified several models (i.e., SAMM model of Luftman (2000), Maturity model of Duffy (2001)) of strategic alignment of an organisation. After critically reviewing the models available in the literature, it was noticed that no strategic alignment model was developed for SMEs, particularly in the context of Forex SMEs. Upon critical assessments of several existing models for this research adopted SAMM model of Luftman (2000) as the underpinning model for exploring strategic alignment of a Forex SME. In order to explore the factors essential for achieving strategic alignment within a Forex SME, this research investigated a UK-based Forex SME ‘Company A’. In order to explore the factors of strategic alignment within SMEs, a qualitative research design was used, and semi-structured interviews were conducted with managers that are currently employed in Company A. The interview questions were designed by carefully considering the dimensions of Luftman's SAMM model as well as other key existing literature.

An analysis of the collected data indicated that all six dimensions of Luftman's (2000)'s SAMM model, namely Communication maturity, Competency maturity, IT governance maturity, Scope and architecture of the IT maturity, Partnership maturity, and Human resource skills maturity are essential for achieving a good level of strategic alignment between different departments within SMEs. Some of the senior managers in the sample stated that 'Company A' focuses on all of these aspects in order to ensure the organisation operates in an efficient manner and delivers exceptional quality of services to customers. However, many of the managers working at the lower levels detailed that, although the organisation focuses on achieving maturity across different organisational aspects, they are far from achieving a balanced strategic alignment across different departments. A further analysis of the data revealed that considering only the six dimensions provided by Luftman's (2000)'s SAMM model is not sufficient in the context of modern Forex SMEs, given that they mainly operate in the digital marketplace. The analysed data revealed that it is also critical to ensure a Forex SME achieves web systems (Internet) maturity when achieving overall strategic alignment.

Communication Maturity, as presented in Chapter 4.2.1, is essential for attaining strategic alignment within Forex SMEs. This is because communication is vital not only for facilitating effective collaborations between different departments but is also necessary for setting out the overall strategic direction of an organisation. This finding of the research is consistent with the existing literature such as Njanka et al. (2021), Alghazi et al. (2017), Volk and Zerfass (2018), Argenti (2016) and Luftman (2004). Numerous other studies have also reported that without having effective communication across departments, achieving perfect strategic alignment is not possible. For instance, a qualitative study conducted in the South African IT industry by Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017) revealed that firms struggled to achieve strategic alignment due to the lack of effective communication across different departments, which was also observed in the context of Company A. In addition, Street et al. (2017) highlighted that sustainable communication between senior business and IT managers is crucial in enhancing SMEs strategic alignment and organisational performance. Alghazi et al. (2017) conducted a qualitative study using semi-structured interviews in the Saudi Arabian SMEs public sector to investigate the problems in strategic alignment. Authors found SMEs could not achieve strategic alignment due to the lack of financial support and miscommunication between business owners and employees.

Dejarnett et al. (2004) conducted a mixed-method study in strategic alignment maturity in SMEs and large firms and revealed that maintaining communication was difficult to most organisations because managers did not clarify their plans and goals to other departments, therefore, cross-department communication was difficult. Indeed, Luftman (2004) highlighted that communication maturity can help organisations to find answers and detect future gaps and risks in their existing business processes and strategies, which was further supported by numerous studies conducted later on. This study also supports the finding of Luftman (2004) and makes a contribution to the literature by confirming communication maturity essential to achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs.

Similarly, *Competency maturity* is also essential for achieving strategic alignment as competent firms can effectively assess their organisational needs and take appropriate actions (Wang and Rusu, 2018; Alghazi et al., 2017; Chatzoglou et al., 2011; Luftman, 2004; Henderson and Venkatraman, 1993). Regular quality reviews are some ways to achieve competency maturity for achieving strategic alignment (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019). A study conducted by Krotov (2015) showed that the lack of competency leads to poor organisational performance. He also stated that firms who are not keen on conducting formal assessments on business and IT processes cannot identify their existing gaps which cause inefficiencies in the customer service product line. An in-depth qualitative investigation conducted by Wu et al. (2015) revealed that Chinese retail firms struggled to maintain sustainable communication since businessowners and managers trust their judgements and never share their understanding with each other. Thus, strategic alignment cannot be achieved between business and IT strategies. This was also evident in the sample of the current research. The analysis of the interview transcripts revealed that managers that were working in strategy and IT departments of 'Company A' did regularly assess the problems faced by the organisation, which hampered the effectiveness of the entire organisational decision-making processes. According to Luftman (2004) and Gerow et al. (2014), firms who conduct regular formal assessments of their business and IT practices and processes effectively serve customers and higher customer satisfaction.

Competency maturity encourages regular formal business-IT assessments so that businessowners can engage with any bottlenecks in the firm (Werder, 2015; Sarhan and McDonagh, 2014; Chan and Reich, 2007). In Company A, branch managers stressed the importance of business-IT

assessments as they identified many bottlenecks in current processes and systems. Further, the branch managers highlighted that branch efficiency has been reduced and this is similar to the findings of Chatzoglou et al. (2011) and Luftman (2004). Area support managers revealed that due to IT outage in the current servers most branch managers were unable to fulfil customer orders; thus customers raised complaints on social websites such as Google and Trust Pilot. Such negative feedback can significantly affect organisations negatively in the long term (Dent, 2015; Kanihan et al., 2013; Yayla and Hu, 2009).

This research also revealed that *IT governance maturity* is another crucial factor for attaining strategic alignment within Forex SMEs. This is because the IT governance structure of an organisation ensures senior business managers and IT managers critically evaluate the business-IT priorities and how they enhance organisational performance (Hsu et al., 2015; Powell, 1992). IT governance maturity focuses on the appropriate allocation of IT resources of an organisation (Hussin et al., 2002). It was noted in the sample that the unbalanced allocation of IT resources and the lengthy approval procedures reduced Company A's performance. Not only branch managers but area support managers also criticised that the current IT plan is not supportive towards enhancing branch profitability as they fail to provide urgent support for in-branch IT issues. IT management participation and involvement in strategic meetings are crucial for strategic alignment (Ilmudeen et al., 2019; Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016), which was also observed in the findings of the research as the lack of involvement of the IT department in strategic meetings led to poor decision making.

Participation of IT managers in decision-making processes resulting in enhanced organisational performance is also emphasised by numerous researchers such as Mitropoulos (2021), Parmenter (2015), Alaceva and Rusu (2015), Seman and Salim (2013), Ravishankar et al. (2011) and Hussin et al. (2002). A study conducted in Iranian public sector firms investigating IT governance and its relationship to strategic alignment by Zahir-Irani et al. (2013) revealed that most Iranian public sector firms failed to achieve strategic alignment due to business and IT managers being unsuccessful in allocating appropriate IT resources and investments to those firms. The finding of this study is also consistent with the findings of Zahir-Irani et al. (2013). Alaceva and Rusu (2015) stated that large firms may have a good IT governance structure since they have access to a large resource pool and guidance. However, this is opposite to SMEs as

they tend to have limited resources and knowledge. SMEs are usually specialised in their products and services thus IT governance must be developed to support the business (Luftman, 2004; Wu et al., 2015; Ilmudeen and Malik, 2016). The findings of this study make significant contributions to the literature by reaffirming IT governance maturity is essential for the success of a Forex SME.

IT scope and architecture maturity deals with how an organisation's IT infrastructure, flexibility in structures, and agility are all aligned. IT scope and architecture maturity tend to depend on how the senior management considers emergent technological solutions to business expansion are also important for strategic alignment (Katiskogiannis et al., 2018; Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Seman and Salim, 2013; Feld and Stoddard, 2004). Flexibility in IT infrastructure and solutions is one of the positive factors in achieving strategic alignment (Kamariotou and Kitsios, 2019; Reynolds and Yetton, 2015). Jorfi et al. (2011) revealed that flexibility in IT infrastructure enhances connectivity to business operations thus, strategic alignment can be successful. This is because, as businesses expand, it is important that IT architecture and its integrated solutions are able to change to adapt to new changes (Majstorovic, 2016). Cataldo et al. (2012) conducted a comparative qualitative research study of SMEs in Chile and Colombia and revealed that SMEs struggled to expand their business as their IT architecture were not integrated into business plans and goals. Kamariotou and Kitsios (2019) conducted an extensive qualitative study on Greek SMEs and also noted that most SMEs do not consider how to change their architecture and scope to support business surroundings. The findings of Kamariotou and Kitsios (2019) and Cataldo et al. (2012) are somewhat consistent with the findings of this research as Company A did not appear to have a plan on regular upgrading of existing IT infrastructures. For example, the FxPOS systems design structure in Company A was rigid and it did not have a backup system when there is an outage in the server.

The findings of this research, as presented in chapter 4.2.4, revealed that maturity in IT scope and architecture is essential for attaining strategic alignment within Forex SMEs. This is because IT architectures such as different hardware, software and IT solutions are essential for Forex operations and having up-to-date IT architectures allow organisations to be more efficient. The findings exposed that the current IT infrastructure of Company A is not highly efficient for Forex operations, therefore, its reducing business performance. Kamariotou and Kitsios (2019)

highlighted that SMEs' IT infrastructure should be developed based on their business products and services and should have higher flexibility to change when needed. This research identified that, due to issues in Company A's telecommunication networks, most branch managers had to temporarily close their branches on an occasion, and this increased negative customer complaints. Thus, based on the findings of the research and the existing works of literature, it is determined that IT scope and architecture maturity is critical to achieve strategic alignment in Forex SMEs.

As identified by this research, *partnership maturity* is another crucial factor for attaining strategic alignment within Forex SMEs. This findingsis consistent with recent literature such as Kawtar et al. (2019), Afandi (2020), Gbangou and Rusu (2016), Ahmed et al. (2016) and Alkhaffaf et al. (2018). An in-depth qualitative study conducted by Sharma and Behl (2020) revealed that Indian public and private firms faced major disruptions while addressing customer demands due to a lack of partnerships with their IT department. Slim et al. (2021) revealed that most SMEs ' IT managers are unaware of their business goals and parameters while attending their systems upgrades. Difficulties in partnership can cause a lack of communication and understanding. Afandi (2020) revealed that Saudi SMEs faced difficulties to maintain good interaction within their management because their senior managers were unaware of the operational functions thus creating misunderstandings and difficulties in partnership.

Similarly, the findings of this research revealed that *skills maturity* is also essential for achieving your strategic alliance in Forex SMEs. This is because skill maturity involves ensuring employees have attended enough training before starting the employment, whilst considering how to increase performance development in employees and how to enhance employees' future career prospects (Luftman, 2004). Hussin et al. (2002) postulated that strategic alignment is a collection of comprehensive work tasks in firms thus requires trained qualified employees to maintain business operations. During the analysis of the research data of this research, it was noted that the employees of Company A were not effectively trained, and that affected their work confidence and performance, eventually affecting organisational strategic alignment negatively. A study conducted by Chivandi et al. (2014) postulated that firms who are operating in the telecommunication industry in Zimbabwe are lacking strategic resources (financial, human and physical) thus achieving strategic alignment achievement was a difficult task for them. Luftman

et al. (2015) conducted their study to identify further knowledge on strategic alignment and its influence on firm performance and revealed that firms must encourage and give recognition to employees as they achieve their monthly targets at work since employee motivation positively impacts strategic alignment. Well-trained and motivated employees are assets to organisations and when they accomplish their work responsibilities, the entire organisation succeeds (Henriques et al., 2019). On the other hand, employees who are not skilled and trained may not be able to contribute much towards achieving strategic alignment (Goepf and Avila, 2015; Wu et al., 2015); this was also noted in the findings of this research. Thus, employee training is the significant factor in skills maturity towards achieving strategic alignment not only for Forex SMEs but also for bigger organisations in various industries (Wirtz et al., 2018; Street et al., 2017; Majstorovic, 2016; Larson and Chang, 2016). The findings of this research add new insight to the literature by confirming skill maturity is not only important to big organisations for achieving strategic alignment, but also important to Forex SMEs.

This research also revealed that *web (internet) systems maturity* is another crucial factor for achieving strategic alignment within Forex SMEs. Existing literature has repeatedly noted the importance of adopting modern technologies such as faster and secure internet connections for being efficient as well as competitive. For example, a study conducted by Kitsios and Kamariotou (2017) highlighted that organisations cannot sustain without connecting their systems to the internet as they have to maintain certain corporate relationships with other organisations. Li et al. (2016) believes that though the internet is required to connect IT systems with customers and every business and IT platform in customer orientation built upon the concept of internet availability. The financial industry is one of the most sensitive industries and safe handling of consumer data is critical to the success of a financial firm (Meijer and Thaens, 2010). Internet is a security method to alert security teams in case of an emergency situation (Boudreau and Watson, 2006). A study conducted by Alaceva and Rusu (2015) on large firms' strategic alignment revealed that the internet is crucial to verify information. Besides, as observed in the sample, web systems are also critical to facilitate coordination between different departments in an efficient manner. The findings of this research are consistent with recent literature and make a contribution to the knowledge by highlighting web system maturity is essential for achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs.

In order to explore the factors of strategic alignment in a Forex SME, this research adopted the strategic alignment maturity model (SAMM) of Luftman (2003) as the underpinning model. Upon critical assessment of the research data, it was noted that the six dimensions were not sufficient for achieving strategic alignment in the tech-driven industry such as the Forex industry. Therefore, based on the finding of this research, as well as after a critical discussion of the finding by locating them in the broader literature, the original SAMM of Luftman (2003) is reconceptualised in the context of Forex SMEs. The new conceptualization now includes an additional dimension named web systems maturity. The figure below presents the strategic alignment maturity model for Forex SMEs.

Figure 5-1: Strategic Alignment Maturity Model for Forex SMEs.

Source: The Author

The next section of this chapter discusses the findings related to challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment.

5.3. Challenges associated with achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs

Whilst identifying the factors of strategic alignment, this research also sought to identify the challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment. In order to identify the challenges, managers working in a UK-based Forex SME were interviewed. Upon thematic analysis of the interview data, this research identified four key challenges faced by Forex SMEs in the process of achieving strategic alignment within the organisation. They include lack of senior management support and commitment, lack of coordination between IT departments and business managers, resistance to change culture, slow this decision making the stringent company policies, knowledge and skill deficit, and lack of financial resources. Figure 5.2 presents the findings of this research.

Figure 5-2: Challenges associated with achieving strategic alignment.

Source: The Author.

In general, respondents of the research argued that strategic alignment itself is a challenge for Company A since the business and IT department are not coordinating properly. Whereas some participants highlighted that the most formidable challenge is the senior managers' dedication to helping business and IT plans work harmoniously. Participants mentioned that, currently,

effective coordination between the IT department and Company A's branch managers also lacking thus, creating a complex business environment for Forex operations. Company A used to be a family business and the decision-making process used to be fairly straightforward; however, since a multinational organisation acquired the firm, many employees are resistant to changing their existing business and IT practices. A further analysis of the data revealed that participants believe that sophisticated organisational policies are not suitable for SMEs as it is slowing the current business and IT decision-making efficiency, which creates a hurdle for strategic alignment.

A critical analysis of the data highlighted that achieving strategic alignment can be impossible without the commitment of the senior managers. In Company A, managers at the operational levels felt that the senior managers were not highly committed towards engaging all parties in the decision-making process and ensuring everyone feels included within the organisation. Besides, most interview participants argued that senior management support depends on the situation they face and there can be various reasons behind the lack of senior management support for branch managers in Company A. Senior managers were found to generally consider IT problems and implementations as a general query not as a strategic issue. According to Alaceva and Rusu (2015), most organisations consider their IT problems and implementation situations as a generic concept; thus, achieving strategic alignment can be difficult. Teo and Ang (1999) identified three significant milestones in their in-depth study and that strategic alignment sustainability depends on the senior business managers and IT managers' commitment to each other. This research also revealed that senior managers' knowledge and their skill levels impact on achieving strategic alignment; thus lack of such was considered to be a challenge in the case of Company A. This is because the success of strategic alignment mainly depends on to what extent senior management involve in the process. It was understood that senior management should maintain a sound relationship with all branches and other departments' employees for achieving strategic alignment. Luftman et al. (1999) also highlighted that senior manager support towards business and IT is crucial when achieving strategic alignment. Mitropoulos (2021) also explained that many organisations failed to achieve strategic alignment in their respective firms because IT was considered a tool, not a team member. Similarly, Williams et al. (2019) and Coltman et al. (2015) highlighted that in strategic alignment, IT should be evaluated as a strategic map, not a generic map or tool to fix generic problems in the business. In the specific case of Company A,

senior management's lack of commitment to engage the IT department in the strategic decision-making process appears to stem from the lack of knowledge regarding the importance of the roles IT strategies play in the success of business strategies.

According to Chaudhary and Uprety (2016), experienced senior executives can be a great fortune for any given organisation. Business and IT executives who have worked in the same market environment understand the business and market dynamics. Thus, their strategic decisions can enhance organisational efficiency (Rathod et al., 2019). Parmenter (2015) believes that business and IT managers' rapid support depends on their basic understanding of their business. Gerow et al. (2014) defined strategic alignment as a commitment of business to IT and vice versa. Overall, the involvement of IT and business departments in the decision-making process was observed as low in the case of Company A and this is due to senior managers not appreciating the role IT strategies play in the success of the business strategies. As this issue was also noted by other researchers, the finding of this research is consistent with the findings of the other previous studies.

Similarly, this research also revealed that the lack of cross-departmental coordination was one of the challenges Company A was facing in the process of achieving strategic alignment. Due to the lack of coordination between the managers from the IT department and branch managers, there were major delays in achieving organisational objectives. The findings highlighted that proper support and coordination between the business department and IT department is the business success point in Company A. This is because every business and IT platform heavily depend on IT solutions and connectivity therefore any outage in IT department service can negatively impact on Company A's profit targets. In addition, another reason is every branch must be connected to online FxPOS systems in order to update the currency rates and approve customer transactions. Thus, IT management must maintain sustainable coordination with every branch manager in Company A since current systems heavily depend on IT solutions. These findings are consistent with several existing literature (i.e., Cataldo and McQueen, 2015; Ullah and Lai, 2013; Rathod et al., 2019; El-Telbany and Elragal., 2014; Jorfi et al., 2011) that also highlight that lack of cross-departmental coordination can be a substantial challenge in terms of achieving strategic alignment.

Rathod et al. (2019) argued strategic alignment is a result of formal coordination and planning between the business and IT departments. The authors further stress that coordination in all non-business and IT departments in a firm is also essential as it assists firms when developing future business vision and goals. Sibanda and Ramrathan (2017) noted that SMEs that develop strategies without having a deeper understanding of their business and IT resources tend to fail to develop the most effective strategies. Moreover, coordination and good understanding between senior business managers and IT managers can enhance building entrepreneurial concepts to the business, since no business can grow without having proper IT strategies (Arundela et al., 2019; Alonso et al., 2018). Therefore, based on the findings and the literature, it is suggested that Company A's senior managers should engage all department managers prior to forming key business strategies.

This research also noted that the culture of change resistance was prevalent in Company A, and it was affecting the organisations' strategic alignment negatively. Most branch managers felt that introducing a new change was difficult when employees were unaware of the new procedures and practices introduced by the senior management. Abbas et al. (2019) carried out a study in SMEs organisational performance and found that SMEs are not keen on welcoming formal business procedures and inflexible business practices to their business portfolio as businessowners believe it can reduce a firm's overall performance. Chinomona (2013) argues that, for SMEs' strategic alignment, it is important to have flexible and user-friendly systems in place. Prior to the acquisition, Company A had a basic system that was easy to operate but only offered limited functionalities. The system that was implemented later was more sophisticated and many employees struggled to cope with new changes. Ning and Tanriverdi (2017), Mithas and Rust (2016), and Bouckenoghe (2010) stressed that complex IT strategies and solutions can lower an organisation's overall achievement and its motivation to achieve business goals.

Hyder and Lussier (2016) carried out a research study on the strategic alignment behaviour of Spanish large organisations. The authors found that senior leadership should introduce employee training sessions annually if they introduce a new business or IT systems and procedures. Employee transition cannot be successful unless they have been well-trained and informed (Gholami et al., 2017). Therefore, in order to make the transition process smooth and to overcome the culture of change resistance, Company A can conduct training sessions prior to

implementing new sessions and after implementing as well. Employees' resistance to new changes is not uncommon as De Val and Fuentes (2003) also found in their qualitative study that employees tend to develop individual resistance when the current business and IT work practices change. Similarly, Bovey and Hede (2001) also highlighted in their research that most SME employees create challenging resistance to businessowners if the current work practices are altered. This may be because senior employees trust their judgements and previous work experience when they work with the latest IT systems, therefore, they reject accepting new culture (Ward and Peppard, 2002; Chinomona, 2013). Nonetheless, such a challenge can be overcome by providing appropriate training to employees, getting them involved in decision-making processes, and ensuring their contributions are valued.

Another challenge noted in the sample was the lengthy decision-making process due to stringent company policies. These lengthy and stringent decision-making processes may be unsuitable to SMEs as SMEs' business operations and functions tend to be far simpler than large firms (Abbas et al., 2019). Also, SMEs employ below 250 employees and maintain unstructured organisational practices overall thus there is often no need for stringent company policies (Hashim et al., 2018; Majstorovic, 2016; Cataldo and McQueen, 2015; Ahmad and Pirzada, 2014). Moreover, sophisticated organisational policies can consume more time on approving customer transactions, which can affect consumer experiences negatively (Hussin et al., 2002; Sabherwal and Chan, 2001). According to Gbangou and Rusu (2016) and Hussin et al. (2002) complex organisational policies and delays in business approvals negatively impact strategic alignment.

It is established in the literature that a delayed decision-making process adversely affects strategic alignment. Wang (2014) investigated Chinese SMEs and found that delay in strategic decision making is one of the hindering factors of strategic alignment. Cataldo and McQueen (2015) conducted their research on SMEs' strategic alignment and concluded that SMEs that employ large firms' strategies and policies can only reduce overall SME performance. Company A is a medium-sized firm and potentially looking to transition into a large firm in the near future, hence it may be implementing stringent policies gradually. However, for the time being, using large firms' policies and practices may not be suitable for SMEs' strategic alignment and it may prevent them from being able to secure competitive advantages. Katzy et al. (2016), Wang and Rusu (2018), and Sabherwal and Chan (2001) described that solid organisational policies can

strengthen the firms' direction for the future however, there is a possibility that stringent organisational policies can reduce the competitive advantage. This finding provides insights regarding a medium-sized firm that is potentially transitioning into a large firm. Given that SMEs, in general, may not operate in the same way as Company A does, this finding may not reflect how Forex SMEs in general operate.

This research also revealed that due to lack of necessary knowledge and skill achieving strategic alignment was an extremely difficult task for the bureau. Tembo et al (2021) concluded that organisations cannot sustain in a competitive marketplace if they do not have enhanced knowledge and skills for achieving organisational objectives. Afandi (2020) revealed from his study that Saudi SMEs could not achieve strategic alignment due to a lack of necessary knowledge and skills and this has negatively impacted organisational performance. Company A's senior managers appeared overly confident in their personal decision-making skills and were not keen to adopt new knowledge and work practices. However, it is important to note that, once most profitable organisations in global markets, "*Nokia and Kodak*", lost a greater portion of their profitability as they failed to adopt new knowledge and practices (Silva et al., 2016; Shahzad et al., 2012; Amar and Romdhane, 2019).

Finally, lack of sufficient financial resources was another challenge faced by Company A for achieving strategic alignment. The data revealed that due to strict budgetary controls by the senior management, the bureau does not invest in research and development, thus failing to incorporate the views and experiences of employees to find the right equilibrium in business strategy and IT strategy. Also, the IT department could not approve critical business decisions as they required more finance, which had a direct impact on organisational performance. Ilmudeen et al. (2019) and Sha et al. (2020) concluded that no organisation can maintain its sustainability without having access to adequate financial resources. Also, Gligor et al (2020) noted financial resources are one of the strategic resources that every organisation should consider. However, as SMEs tend to be smaller in size and tend to have limited financial resources, they cannot invest in the necessary expertise and skills that are necessary for achieving strategic alignment.

5.4. Achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business strategy and IT strategy in Forex SMEs

After analysing interview data, four critical success factors for achieving harmonious alignment of business and IT strategies were identified. They include effective cross-department communication and coordination, management knowledge and commitment, appropriate distribution of organisational resources, and regular training and development of front-line staff.

Effective cross-department communication and coordination between the business department and IT department are crucial when achieving harmonious strategic alignment for Company A. This is because Forex SMEs cannot survive without maintaining sustainable communication in their business processes. Generally, SMEs maintain flexible (Street et al., 2017), friendly operations (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019) in the market therefore SMEs must need communication at all levels of operations to align not only with their business and IT strategies but also with other business operations as well (Sharma and Behl, 2020; Invernizzi and Romenti, 2015). During the interviews, it was interpreted that without maintaining sustainable communication practices Company A cannot achieve strategic alignment. According to Conelissen (2017) and Street et al. (2017), senior management support in strategic decisions is necessary to achieve strategic alignment. Slim et al. (2021) also highlighted senior managers must listen and maintain supportive communication practices on business and IT issues. It was also noted in the findings that IT and finance departments are not coordinating effectively for ensuring Company A purchases necessary IT equipment. Without having necessary IT equipment such as hardware, software, computers, scanners and printers etc; organisations cannot maintain targeted efficiency and performance; thus overall goals and strategies cannot be achieved (Oroszo et al., 2015; Teeratansirikool et al., 2013). Rapid response from senior IT managers is one of the critical success factors in strategic alignment (Slim et al., 2021; Alghazi et al., 2020; Heroux and Fortin, 2018; Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Teo and Ang, 1999). The findings further revealed that due to a lack of communication from the IT department, branch managers were unable to serve customers appropriately and meet their expectations. The IT managers in company A appeared to not be communicating with senior management when they need new resources.

As identified from the analysis of the data, *senior management knowledge and commitment* to strategic decisions are also crucial for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of Business and IT strategies in a UK-based Forex SME. This is because senior management is directly responsible for designing strategic decisions in SMEs. Further, strategic alignment is a higher managerial decision for any organisation (Tallon and Kraemer, 2003). Therefore senior management commitment and involvement are essential to achieve strategic alignment (Kitsios and Kamariotou, 2019; Spinelli et al., 2013), especially for Forex SMEs. It was observed in the sample that senior managers of Company A are not equipped with thorough knowledge about the Forex industry and actions necessary for achieving harmonious strategic alignment that is suitable for Company A. Every branch manager in the sample argued that senior management focuses only on sales performance not strategic decisions or alignment. Wang and Rusu (2018) highlighted that business and IT managers must have a robust understanding and knowledge about strategic alignment, especially when the firm is operating in the financial industry. Financial organisations process sensitive information thus having strategic alignment of business and IT strategies can protect organisation value and customer information (Henriques et al., 2019; Katsikogiannis et al., 2018).

Appropriate distribution of organisational resources was also identified to play a substantial role in achieving harmonious strategic alignment of IT and business strategies in Company A. To execute any organisational strategies, resources such as, financial, IT and human are essential (Sha et al., 2020; Denning, 2018). Six out of eight branch managers of Company A highlighted that the IT department of Company A is not keen on providing urgent IT resources to their branches. Findings further revealed that due to lack of new computers, internet routers and scanners, most branches had to cancel their customer transactions as they cannot execute the Forex transaction formally and legally by printing a confirmation. As stated by Contador et al. (2021), it is mandatory for firms to have proper access to necessary resources in order to achieve strategic alignment. Gilgor et al. (2020) defined strategic alignment as a marriage between business strategy and IT strategy; and substantial organisational resources are needed to develop a strategic plan (Tallon and Pinsonneault, 2011). Therefore, without proper financial and human resources, no organisation can align their business strategy and IT strategy (Fattah and Arman, 2014; Luftman and Derkson, 2012). Further, it was noted in the findings that, currently, Company A is not encouraging any formal business and IT assessments thus bureau is struggling

to verify the requirements of branches that directly deal with customers. Also, a senior area support manager and an analyst mentioned that the IT department has a lack of data in identifying branch IT requirements and audits as they are not following any formal IT assessments, and this has impacted the overall strategic alignment process in Company A negatively. This finding is consistent with Luftman et al.'s (2017) conclusions that firms should implement regular business and IT assessments to evaluate organisational requirements. Moreover, Alghazi et al. (2020) found in their research in Saudi Arabian SMEs that firms struggling to achieve strategic alignment due to a lack of necessary resources. Wang and Rusu (2018) found in Chinese SMEs a lack of investment support hindering achieving strategic alignment. Therefore, financial resources are required to achieve strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. This finding of this research is consistent with the findings of Wang and Rusu (2018) and Alghazi et al. (2020) who also investigated SMEs' strategic alignment. Street et al. (2017) argued that SMEs are founded on the foundation of being a flexible and rapid response to customers thus strategic alignment must be uniquely developed for SMEs characteristics such as firm size and resource availability. Due to financial and resource constraints, SMEs maintain less sophisticated but cheaper IT systems and hierarchy thus requiring a simple strategic alignment procedure (Cataldo and McQueen, 2015; Street et al., 2017; Pagani, 2013; Spinelli et al., 2013). However, the organisational resources, however minimal they are, if they are not appropriately distributed, achieving strategic alignment can be a challenging task.

Finally, this research revealed that *regular employee training and development* is vital for Forex SMEs for achieving strategic alignment. This is because experienced and trained employees are aware of the current organisational strategies and procedures that are necessary for achieving strategic alignment. Strategic alignment is a high-level organisational decision and employees who do not engage in the latest training and development programmes may be unable to understand organisational strategic decisions (Alagaraja and Shuck, 2015; Taneja et al., 2015). The literature highlighted that a well-trained and motivated workforce can motivate other employees in the same organisation to perform better, thus training and development of employees can be a supportive factor for achieving strategic alignment (Hyder and Lussier, 2016; Messeni et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the overall purpose of strategic alignment is to make organisations successful in providing excellent customer service and achieving organisational goals effortlessly (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2020). It was noticed in the findings

that the current employee training programmes were ineffective to train and motivate employees appropriately and it affected the process of strategic alignment. Further, senior managers in the sample revealed that employee training must be face-to-face and should not be conducted via self-learning online platforms as all employees may not fully understand the training modules. According to Chabbouh and Boujelbene (2021) and Hedvall et al. (2019), employees who are trained face to face are much more effective and very motivated in achieving organisational goals and obeying strategic decisions. This is because online training platforms are very famous and also less expensive for delivering training sessions, they are often completed outside of the work environment and employees may not be fully engaged with the training contents (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2021). Recent literature highlighted that SME business owners purposely recruit employees who have higher experiences in past employments. This is because they understand the job role more effectively and do not require to provide further training compared to freshly graduated in higher studies (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2020; Gama et al., 2019). This also further emphasises the importance of training and development for achieving strategic alignment.

As discussed above, the findings of this research are consistent with the prior literature and indicate that in terms of strategic alignment, SMEs operate in similar ways to larger organisations. This may be because Company A is a medium-sized firm and soon to be transitioned into a large firm. Therefore the findings of this research in relation to Company A may not be representative of the entire SME sector.

5.5. Evaluations of the Findings

This study used Luftman's Strategic Alignment Maturity Model (SAMM) to explore the factors of strategic alignment in Company A (case firm). Based on the analysis of the data, this research reconceptualised SAMM in the context of forex SMEs by adding an additional dimension called web systems (Internet) maturity. This research also identified the challenges company A faces in terms of achieving strategic alignment along with the critical success factors of achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business and IT strategies. However, it is important to note that the findings may not fully reflect how Forex SMEs in the UK operate as this research used a case study research strategy by taking one UK-based Forex SME as a case. In addition, this research used a qualitative design and interviewed 16 participants from the case company. Given

that qualitative research findings tend to be not highly generalisable, the replicability of the findings may be questioned. Nevertheless, this research explored an under-investigated territory and added new insights to the literature. A discussion of the findings indicated that most of the findings were consistent with the existing literature, and they make the area of investigation further strong. The added new insights make contributions to the literature by filling the existing knowledge gaps.

5.6. Chapter Summary

This chapter discussed the research findings by locating them in the broader literature and drawing their contributions. In order to find answers to each research question, firstly, this study examined and discussed the current strategic alignment procedure in UK based Forex SMEs. This study used Luftman's (2003) SAMM model to evaluate Company A's (case company) current strategic alignment. Considering the findings of this research, the model was reconceptualised, making contributions to the literature. This research also examined the challenges Company A faces in the process of achieving strategic alignment to understand what kind of challenges Forex SMEs face for achieving strategic alignment. This research identified six specific challenges and the challenges faced by Company A were similar to challenges faced by other organisations and SMEs. Based on the findings of this research, this chapter also presented a conceptual model for strategic alignment of Forex SMEs. The findings of this research make substantial contributions by adding new insights to the literature. However, the contributions may not be representative of the entire UK Forex SME sector as the research data was collected from one UK based Forex SME only. The next chapter of this thesis presents the contributions in detail whilst evaluating their generalisability.

Chapter Six: Conclusions, Contributions and Recommendations

6.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to summarise the research finding and highlight how each research objective was achieved in order to draw the contributions this research makes to both literature and the professional practice. Initially, the entire research is summarised and that is followed by revisiting the research aim and objectives and evaluating whether or not the research objectives have been achieved. Next, theoretical and practical contributions of the findings are highlighted, and their generalizability is discussed. Subsequently, recommendations to Forex SMEs in the UK, managers in Company A, and the UK government is made. Finally, research limitations are highlighted and suggestions for further results are made for extending this study.

6.2. Summary of this Research

This research sought to explore the factors of strategic alignment between Forex SMEs by taking a UK based Forex SME (Company A) as a case. In order to make effective recommendations to Forex SMEs for achieving strategic alignment and thereby enhancing their business performance, initially, the factors of strategic tragic alignment were explored. Then, the challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment was investigated. Finally, how two different organisational departments can achieve strategic alignment was also investigated by taking a case of the IT department and business department in Company A.

An extensive review of the existing literature revealed that most scholars in the area of strategic alignment have devoted their time and resources to finding the factors for strategic alignment for larger organisations (Alaceva and Rusu, 2015; Hussin et al., 2002). Notably, only a few studies have focused on finding critical success factors for strategic alignment for SMEs (Volk and Zerfass, 2018; Street et al., 2017). A review of the literature further indicated that no empirical study was previously conducted in Forex SMEs to explore the factors of strategic alignment and how a Forex SME can achieve harmonious strategic alignment of their IT and business strategy. In order to fill the existing knowledge gaps in the literature, this research investigated Company

A, one of the Forex bureaus in London. Company A qualifies as an SME as it employs between 100 to 150 people and its annual revenue is below €40 million. This research adopted the strategic alignment maturity model (SAMM) of Luftman (2003) as the underpinning theoretical model of the research. SAMM consists of six dimensions' namely, communication, competency, IT governance, scope and architecture of the IT, partnership and skills maturities.

In order to achieve the research aim and objectives and thereby fill the existing knowledge gap, this research followed the interpretivist research philosophy and a qualitative research design. A case study research strategy was used, and a decision was made to adopt a mono case study strategy as it allows researchers to investigate the phenomenon in an in-depth manner. In order to collect the primary research data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a total of 16 employees of Company A with interviews lasting between 55 minutes to 1 hour and 15 minutes. Out of the 16 participants interviewed, 8 of them were branch managers, 4 of them were senior area managers, 2 of them were senior IT-Business analysts, and 2 of them were employees in the IT department. In order to analyse the research data, thematic analysis was used as the main data analysis procedure whilst utilising "Nvivo 12 Pro".

The analysis of the primary research data revealed numerous codes, categories, sub-themes, and themes. In order to systematically answer the research objectives, the findings were categorised into three different key categories: factors of strategic alignment in Forex SMEs challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment and critical success factors for achieving harmonious strategic alignment between IT strategies and business strategies in Forex SMEs. This research revealed that factors such as Communication maturity, Competency maturity, IT governance maturity, Scope and architecture of IT maturity, Partnership maturity, Skills maturity, and Web systems maturity play critical roles in terms of achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. Besides, this research also revealed numerous challenges Forex SMEs face whilst achieving strategic alignment. They include lack of senior management commitment, lack of coordination between departments, resistance to change culture, and slow decision-making. Finally, this research revealed five critical success factors essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business strategy and IT strategy in a Forex SME: effective cross-department communication and coordination, management knowledge and commitment,

supportive organisational culture, appropriate distribution of organisational resources, and regular training and development of frontline staffs.

6.3. Achieving Research Aim and Objectives

This research aimed to make recommendations to the practitioners in UK Forex SME for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of business strategy and IT strategy upon exploring the factors essential for achieving strategic alignment and the challenges SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment. In order to achieve this aim, five research objectives were formulated. The following sections discuss how each research objective was met.

6.3.1. Objective One

The first objective in this study was *to construct a conceptual framework upon critically reviewing academic literature related to the factors of strategic alignment and challenges organisations face in terms of achieving strategic alignment*. In order to gather the existing literature, a wide literature search was conducted by accessing various journal databases such as Science Direct, Emerald Insights, Google Scholar, EBSCO Host etc. Besides, relevant books and government websites and other reliable websites were also accessed. The review of the literature revealed various existing frameworks for establishing and maintaining a strategic alignment across the different departments within an organisation. Some of the key frameworks that have been extensively used in the literature include SAM of Henderson and Venkatraman (1993), SAMM of Luftman (2003) and Duffy (2001)'s Maturity Model. After critically reviewing the existing frameworks and evaluating their applicability in the context of Forex SMEs, a conceptual framework was established in chapter 2.6 of this thesis. The developed conceptual framework provided critical guidance to the researcher not only whilst formulating the interview questions but also during the analysis of the collected data. In essence, the framework successfully guided the researcher during the entire research process, hence the first research objective was fully achieved.

6.3.2. Objective Two

The second objective in this research was developed *to explore and evaluate the factors necessary for achieving strategic alignment by qualitatively examining a UK based Forex SME.* This objective was developed to understand how SMEs operate in general and what factors need to be considered for achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs and whether or not these factors are comparable to bigger organisations and SMEs in other industries. In order to achieve this objective, a UK-based Forex SME, Company A, was taken as a case firm and investigated qualitatively.

For exploring the current situation of strategic alignment of Company A in a systematic manner, Luftman (2001)'s SAMM framework was adopted. The analysis of the data revealed that the overall coordination across different departments within company A was poor with departments mainly prioritising their individual interest rather than the interest of the company. Besides, it was also revealed that the senior managers were not being highly supportive towards managers at the lower levels. These had negative effects on the strategic alignment of the organisation. The lack of coordination also affected the bureau negatively by making the decision-making process slower and affecting the overall quality of customer service. Besides, it was also observed that the business managers and IT department were maintaining friendly communication with each other thus making strategic decision-making process further difficult; evidence of this can be found in chapter 4.2.1. Moreover, the lack of formal assessment of business and IT needs, implementation of sophisticated IT strategies and procedures, the lack of sufficient organisational resources, and limited employee training appeared to have negatively affected the strategic alignment in Company A.

Based on the findings of this research, it was noted that Communication maturity, Competency maturity, IT governance maturity, Scope and architecture of IT maturity, Partnership maturity, Skills maturity, and Web systems maturity play critical roles in achieving strategic alignment in Forex SME. This research also identified that the pre-existing six dimensions modelled by Luftman (2003) are not sufficient for achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs and considerations of web systems maturity are also essential as SMEs operate in environments that are high tech-driven. Therefore, based on the findings of this research, the existing SAMM model was reconceptualised in the context of Forex SMEs by adding an additional dimension.

As this study was successful in identifying the factors of strategic alignment of Forex SMEs, this objective was also achieved.

6.3.3. Objective Three

The third objective in this research was established *to understand the challenges Forex SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment upon exploring a case of a UK based Forex SME.* A thematic analysis of the interview data collected from a UK based Forex SME (Company A) revealed that SMEs face numerous challenges for achieving strategic alignment. They include lack of senior management commitment, lack of coordination between departments, resistance to change culture, and slow decision-making. As identified, in the context of Company A, senior business managers and IT managers were not committed to branch operations thus this became the biggest challenge for achieving strategic alignment (elaborated in chapter 4.3.1). Besides, it was also observed that the departments were not supporting each other when it comes to strategic planning, this led to misalignment in terms of the strategic focus of different departments. Besides, there was a culture of resistance to new changes as employees were observed to be unwelcoming of new changes. Furthermore, the senior management was not able to make prompt decisions in order to take advantage of rapidly transforming market conditions, this was mainly due to the lack of effective communication and coordination. As this research was able to pinpoint several strategic challenges a UK Forex SME was facing in the process of achieving strategic alignment, this objective of the research is achieved.

6.3.4. Objective Four

The fourth objective in this study was developed *to reveal the critical success factors for achieving a harmonious strategic alignment of IT strategies and business strategies in the context of the UK Forex SMEs.* It was noted in the literature that strategic alignment is a continuous process of improvement therefore there can be many critical success factors. Upon critical assessment of Company A's strategic alignment of IT strategies and business strategies, it was noted that several factors were necessary in order to have a harmonious cross-department strategic alignment within a Forex SME. The analysis of the data revealed that effective alignment of business strategies and IT strategies requires effective cross-department communication and coordination, senior management knowledge and commitment, supportive

organisational culture, appropriate distribution of organisational resources, and regular training and development of frontline staffs. In absence of the considerations of these factors, Forex SMEs cannot formulate organisational strategies that optimise the utilisation of organisational resources and deliver the best outcome for the organisation. Given that this research was successful in outlining factors that should be considered for ensuring effective alignment of business strategies and IT strategies, it is considered that this objective is achieved.

6.3.5. Objective Five

The last objective in this research was formulated *to provide strategic recommendations to the UK Forex SMEs for achieving and maintaining strategic alignment for enhanced organisational performance on the basis of the findings of this research*. In order to be able to provide effective recommendations, the findings of this research were critically discussed by locating them in the broader contexts and drawing generalisations in chapter five of this thesis. Based on the discussions, chapter 6.5 Provides recommendations to three different parties. Firstly, recommendations are made to Forex SMEs for achieving strategic alignment. Secondly, recommendations are made to Company A on how they can achieve harmonious strategic alignment of IT strategies and business strategies for enhancing organisational performance, and finally, recommendations are made to the UK government on how they can support Forex SMEs to become more sustainable and profitable so that they can make more economic contributions.

6.4. Contributions of the Research

6.4.1. Theoretical Contributions

6.4.1.1. Reconceptualisation of Luftman's SAMM in the context of Forex SMEs

Based on the discussions presented in the fifth chapter of this thesis, the following conceptual model is developed:

Figure 6-1: Conceptual Model for Strategic Alignment of Forex SMEs.

Source: The Author.

After analysing the research data, it was noted that all six factors outlined by Luftman (2003) are necessary to achieve strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. This research also revealed that web systems (internet) maturity are also important to achieve strategic alignment with Forex SMEs as the Forex industry is highly technology-driven. Recent studies highlighted that internet support is crucial for organisational sustainability (Chan et al., 2019; Lie et al., 2016). Therefore, based on the findings of this research, the existing strategic alignment maturity model of Luftman (2003) was reconceptualised by adding an additional dimension "web systems (internet) maturity" to represent the factors of strategic alignment more accurately in Forex SMEs. They include increased consumer trust, enhanced organisational competitiveness, and improved overall performance. The proposed model makes contributions by providing guidance to the practitioners regarding not only how strategic alignment can be achieved; but how firms can benefit if strategic alignment is achieved. In addition, the framework also makes academic contributions to the SMEs literature by providing a model for achieving strategic alignment of Forex SMEs. This contribution is significant as it not only highlights that Forex SMEs operate

differently than other organisations, but also provides critical guidance to future researchers in relation to the factors essential for achieving strategic alignment maturity.

6.4.1.2. Identification of the challenges faced by Forex SMEs for achieving strategic alignment

A review of the existing literature (presented in chapter 2.4.5) revealed that the challenges faced by SMEs in relation to achieving his strategic alignment were known in the literature; for instance, senior business managers are not committed to strategic IT (Gerow et al., 2014), lack of good communication between business and IT managers (Luftman and Brier, 1999), sophisticated IT structures and solutions (Shehry et al., 2011), insufficient financial support (Coltman et al., 2015), insufficient government support for business growth (Mitropoulos, 2021), heavy workload (Wiltbank et al., 2006), lack of shared domain knowledge between business and IT departments (Skyrme and Amindo, 1997). However, challenges faced by Forex SMEs specifically were not yet known. This research, therefore, was conducted qualitatively to explore the challenges faced by Forex SMEs for achieving strategic alignment by taking a Forex SME based in the UK as a case. This research revealed numerous challenges faced by Forex SMEs such as lack of senior management commitment or support, lack of coordination between IT department and business managers, resistance to change the culture, and slow decision making due to stringent company policies. These finding makes significant theoretical contributions to the body of knowledge by filling the existing knowledge void.

6.4.1.3. Identification of critical success factors of harmonious strategic alignment in Forex SMEs

A review of the existing literature (presented in chapter 2.4.4) revealed a number of critical success factors of achieving harmonious strategic alignment in an organisation: IT agility (Tallon and Pinsonneault, 2011), IT flexibility (Luftman and Derkson, 2012), top management support for IT (Cataldo and McQueen, 2015; Luftman and Brier, 1999), relationship between CEO and CIO (Feeny et al., 1992), IT involvement in strategy development (Padukkage et al., 2014) and IT investment (Wetering et al., 2017). However, critical success factors for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of IT strategies and business strategies for Forex SMEs specifically were not yet known. This research, therefore, was conducted to fill the existing knowledge gap. This research revealed numerous critical success factors for Forex SMEs in

strategic alignment and namely, effective cross-department communication and coordination, senior management knowledge and commitment, supportive organisational culture, appropriate distribution of organisational resources and regular training and development of front-line staffers. Thus, these findings make a substantial theoretical contribution to the body of knowledge by filling the existing knowledge gap.

6.4.2. Practical Contributions

6.4.2.1. Training and development of employees can contribute towards achieving strategic alignment

In the sample, it was noted that when employees are trained properly, they are able to communicate with other departments more effectively. When communication across departments become effortless, employees tend to be more aware of the requirements and resources of other departments, which is critical to achieving a strategic alignment. Therefore, based on the findings of this research, it is suggested that managers should focus on training and developing staffs and creating an environment where everybody supports eachother regardless of the department they are working in. As stated in the literature (chapter 2.4.4.5) well trained and satisfied employees are motivated to follow any organisational strategies and achieve organisational goals. Organisations should provide necessary resources and guidelines on employee training and development programmes as such employees are the first face to customers and employees represent organisational identity (Chabbouh and Boujelbene, 2021; Hedvall et al., 2019). Findings revealed that due to lack of employee training and developments, employees in Company A were unable to comprehend new IT systems and strategies introduced by the senior management therefore not being motivated to achieve shared goals. This has a direct impact on achieving organisational objectives and strategic alignment. These findings provide practitioners with ways for enhancing organisational competence and thereby achieving strategic alignment and thereby making significant contributions to the professional practice.

6.4.2.2. Strategic alignment is the result of collaborative efforts of all business departments within a Forex SME

As highlighted by the literature (Xue et al., 2017; Mithas and Rust, 2016) as well as the findings of this research, achieving strategic alignment require steam work between multiple departments.

Particularly in the context of Forex SMEs effective cross-department coordination is critical to the success of an organisation as they operate in a fiercely competitive market with limited resources. Besides, Forex SMEs have tech-driven business models and without effective alignment of IT strategies and business strategies, SMEs cannot compete in the marketplace. This research identified that even a brief meltdown of the IT department can lead to substantial loss to the organisation both financially and in consumer trusts.

In order to achieve strategic alignment, it is important to engage representatives of different departments in the strategy creation process so that the decision-makers are well informed of the available resources and organisational constraints respective to each department. Such involvements not only lead to the formation of more realistic and appropriate strategies but also different departments will feel involved and are more likely to take ownership of tasks. These findings make managerial contributions by providing a clear pathway for developing strategies that are inclusive and effective.

6.4.2.3. Collecting regular feedback from stakeholders can lead to improved strategic alignment

Encouraging feedback and fostering an environment for sharing innovative ideas can indeed contribute to improved strategic alignment in any organisation (Rezaei et al., 2018; Falkheimer et al., 2017). When Forex bureaus encourage regular feedback from stakeholders, including traders, support staff and loyal customer on their expectations from the bureau regarding the products and services; the management can improve these ideas into action. Establishing open lines of communication within the bureau is important to ensure that employees feel comfortable to share their thoughts and ideas. Moreover, encouraging feedback at all levels of staff can generate innovative business ideas. Identified innovative ideas can be incorporated into the bureau's Forex strategies, potentially leading to gaining competitive advantages in the market.

6.5. Recommendations

The recommendations of this research are depicted under three categories: recommendations to Forex SMEs, recommendations to Company A, and recommendations to the UK government.

6.5.1. Recommendations to Forex SMEs

6.5.1.1. Invest in modern IT infrastructures

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that Forex SMEs should regularly invest in IT systems and solutions and keep them up to date in accordance with the need of the market. This is because Forex SMEs operate in a technology-driven market where the speed, security, and accuracy of a transaction is to deliver high-quality services and meet customer expectations. As chapters 4.2.3 and 4.2.4 discussed, due to lack of investments in IT, a UK based SME's business strategies could not achieve its full efficiency as their IT infrastructures failed on multiple occasions, preventing internal communication as well as effective service delivery. In the sample, it was seen that having ambitious business strategies alone cannot yield effective outcomes if they are not supported by the organisational infrastructures.

Forex trading involves significant financial transactions and handling sensitive client data. Investing in modern IT infrastructures can provide robust security measures to protect against cyber threats, data breaches, and fraudulent activities. Secure systems with encryption protocols, firewalls, and intrusion detection systems help safeguard critical information, maintaining the trust of clients and regulatory compliance. By leveraging these technologies, SMEs can optimise their operations, adapt to market changes, and achieve sustainable growth in the highly competitive Forex industry. As IT infrastructure is in the heart of Forex SMEs' operations, it is recommended that SMEs regularly assess their IT requirements and update their IT infrastructures.

6.5.1.2. Managers at all levels should maintain effective communication with their employees

SMEs are generally smaller organisations with a limited number of employees. In SMEs employees are involved in multiple responsibilities, hence they are likely to face numerous challenges. It is important that managers effectively communicate with all employees and understand the challenges they face as well as seek to explore the experiences of employees that can be valuable for organisational learning and enhancing business operations. Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that SMEs should have open communication

policies where employees are able to communicate openly. Besides, managers should also enable a culture of teamwork so that employees from different departments coordinate in order to achieve the overall organisational strategies. This is because this research identified that communication and coordination play a critical role in terms of achieving strategic alignment whereas miscommunications between employees can prevent efficient sharing of knowledge, eventually leading to strategic misalignment (elaborated in chapter 4.2.1). Communications can be done in various forms such as regular feedback mechanisms, weekly managerial staff meetings, etc. Effective communication not only enables smooth information flow within an SME but also provides them with opportunities to generate much-needed innovative ideas.

6.5.2. Recommendations to the Case Company for Strategic Alignment

6.5.2.1. Regularly assess the gaps in business strategy and IT strategy

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that Company A should undertake regular assessments of their business strategies and IT strategies and review whether there is any gap. This is because overall strategic alignment can only be achieved by making strategic improvements so that subordinate strategies (i.e., IT strategy) support the key business strategies. When the competencies of IT strategies are not regularly evaluated, the organisational IT capabilities cannot be fully understood. This often time results in organisational strategies being overly ambitious. Besides, the organisation's service delivery process cannot be effectively organised as well, this can lead to failures ineffective service delivery and potential loss of revenues.

The long-term goal of Company A is to scale-up their operations and expand their market presence. Assessing the current gaps in business and IT strategies can allow them to identify the areas where technology can enhance scalability and growth. Such assessment can help the case firm to identify systems, tools and processes that can support increased trading volumes, enhanced customer service, and improved operational efficiency. During the analysis of the research data, Company A was observed to be unable to identify the gaps in their current processes. Therefore, it is recommended that Company A conducts regular surveys to understand employees' viewpoints, which in return can provide them with insights regarding the gaps in organisational strategies.

6.5.2.2. Develop and implement rewards and recognition programmes

Some of the participants in the sample noted that they do not feel valued despite the hard work they do for Company A. From the observation of the interview data, it was noted that the reason for company A's lack of information sharing culture may be, firstly, due to the senior managers do not seek to incorporate the views and opinions of other organisational members in the decision-making process and secondly, due to the staff members themselves are not encouraged to share the knowledge they have because they are not specifically rewarded for doing so. Such a lack of information sharing can keep departments disconnected from one another, eventually leading to a lack of alignment in their strategies. Therefore, based on the findings of this research, it is recommended that Company A encourages knowledge sharing within the organisation by implementing rewards and recognition programmes.

6.6. Possible Limitations of the Findings

The findings of this research may have been affected by the following five limitations:

Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the data collection process

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the majority of the interviews were conducted virtually. During face-to-face interviews, the researcher is able to interpret not only the comments of the respondents but also their body language. Although the researcher was keen to conduct all of the interviews in a face-to-face manner, many of the participants preferred to conduct them virtually due to safety concerns. Had the research been able to conduct all interviews physically, it is expected that he would have been able to gather richer information.

Single case study research

The primary research data was collected from one UK-based Forex SME hence case comparison was not possible. By using a single case, the researcher was able to look into the case company in an in-depth manner; however, having multiple SMEs may have helped understand whether or not different Forex SMEs operate differently.

Representativeness

The findings of this research may not be representative of the entire UK Forex SMEs as the data was collected from one London-based SME only. The findings of this research could have been more representative of the UK-based Forex SMEs if more SMEs were considered.

Generalisability

This research used a qualitative research design. Qualitative research studies are often criticised for the lack of generalisability of the findings as findings are usually based on a small sample. Given that this research only investigated one UK based Forex SME and interviewed only 16 participants, the findings of this research may not be widely generalizable.

Size of the case organisation

This research focuses on the strategic alignment aspect of Forex SMEs. Upon investigating a UK based Forex SME, this research outlined various factors of strategic alignment as well as the challenges SMEs face in the process of achieving strategic alignment. The case organisation is a medium-sized organisation that operates in multiple geographical locations. The organization's annual turnover is over £40 million pounds, just under the threshold for large organisations. Given the size of the case organisation, on many occasions, it may operate in the same way as large organisations do. Therefore, the findings may not be relevant to SMEs that are micro or small organisations.

6.7. Further Research

This study adopted Luftman's SAMM model and reconceptualised it in the context of Forex SMEs by adding the seventh dimension called web (internet) systems maturity. However, this study could be further extended by following future studies.

Future Study I: Reassessing the applicability of the reconceptualised strategic alignment maturity model (SAMM) across different contexts.

In this research, Luftman's strategic alignment maturity model was reconceptualised in order to meet the requirement of Forex SMEs. As the re-conceptualisation is based on the data collected from one UK based Forex SMEs, it is recommended that further studies are conducted to verify the applicability of the reconceptualised model across different industries and sectors. Additionally, further studies that examine multiple SMEs are also recommended to enhance the generalizability of the reconceptualised model.

Future Study II: Larger sample size and quantitative research design

This study adopted a qualitative research design and included a small sample size. Given that qualitative research findings are not generalizable, it is recommended that a further study is conducted by using a quantitative research design and collecting data from a large sample.

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8. Appendices

Appendix A: Participant Information Sheet

Research Participant Information Sheet

YOU WILL BE GIVEN A COPY OF THIS INFORMATION SHEET

Title of Study: Exploring the factors essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of Business strategy and IT strategy: A case of a UK Forex SME.

My name is Mesaj Fernando, and I am studying for my Doctor of Business Administration Degree at the University of the West of Scotland (London Campus). I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and how it would involve you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

1) What is the purpose of the study?

This research project aims to explore how a growing Foreign Exchange firm should integrate its IT strategy to its business strategy. Furthermore, this research will look at how the organisation should adapt to its new IT and business practices without affecting its vision and mission. Also, this research study evaluate the organisational performance of Company A, due to strategic alignment. Finally, the conclusions are highlighting the harmonious strategic alignment for better organisational performance.

2) Why have you been invited to take part?

You have been invited to take part in a research study. You have been selected because this research study needs to interview people who have had experience in the foreign exchange business and have a thorough knowledge of how business operations works in the organisation. And, I will be interviewing a range of people who had such experiences.

3) Do I have to take part?

It is completely up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving any reason.

4) What will happen to me if I take part?

If you complete and send back the consent form, I will contact you to arrange an interview at a suitable time and place which is completely convenient for you. We will try to answer any questions you may have about the interview.

5) What would the interview be like?

I will ask you if you are willing to have the interview, audio tape recorded. This is known as a qualitative study that uses the method of face-to-face interviews. You will be given the 'consent form'. You only sign this form if you agree to take part in the interview. You will be given a copy of the consent form to keep. The interview will be a little like a conversation, in which I will help you talk about yourself in your own words. And, then I will ask you to talk about your work experiences in the foreign exchange business and how long you have been working in the Company A. I will ask some questions such as about your job role, does your job role have a connection with strategic alignment and etc.

6) How long would the interview take?

The time it takes for an interview varies, depending on how much you have to say, but most interviews might last at least 30-45 minutes. Remember, if you want to stop the interview at any time, you can do so without giving any reason at all.

7) What will I have to do?

All you have to do is that provide comprehensive feedbacks and information for the questions in the interview. There are no other commitments or restrictions associated with participating.

8) Are there any possible risks and benefits of taking part?

We cannot promise the study will help you but the information I get from this study may help to find answers to what is missing in foreign exchange business's business-IT strategy and the organisation as well. And, the valued information may help the organisation to identify their existing gaps and opportunities in the industry as well. As a benefit, there is a possibility that you will be invited for future studies as well. There is no harm for all participants in this study. Interviewing process is completely voluntary basis, and you can stop it without a reason. There will be no questions in the interview which is focused about your colleagues work patterns, or complaints. All questions are open and focused to the topic. I (main researcher) will be thoroughly looking into your personal opinions about the current IT system/practices, and of course your work experiences in the past. You might feel anxious or discomfort when mentioning about the gaps in the current strategies, or system.

Remember, all the information/opinions you provide will only be used for this research study only and it's only for educational purposes.

9) Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

Yes. Your details will be held in *complete confidence* and we will follow ethical and legal practice in relation to all study procedures. Personal data (name, contact details, audio recordings) will be handled in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act 1998 so that unauthorised individuals will not have access to them. All the information that we collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in this research study. Your institution will also not be identified or identifiable.

10) Is the purpose of this study educational?

Yes. This study is completely taken for educational purposes and the data will only be used for this DBA study only.

11) How will information you provide be recorded, stored and protected?

All the data which is collected in this interview process, will be stored in a password protected USB drive. All data will be protected through stronger passwords and locked in a secure locker, only the main researcher can access it. Every interview session will be recorded through portable voice recorder. All these voice recordings will be stored in a secure safe location, which is only access for main researcher only. In order to check that this research is carried out in line with the law and good research practice, monitoring and auditing can be carried out by UWS Business School.

12) What will happen to the results of the study?

The results of this study will be published in the University library and database. A printed copy of the full research study results will be sent to you by post. You will not be identified in any report, publications or presentation without seeking your full consent. Direct quotes from the interviews may be used in the research discussion; however, the quotes will be anonymised to ensure that you cannot be identified.

13) Who has reviewed the study?

This research has been looked at by an independent group of people, called an Ethics Committee, to protect your interests and legal rights. This study has been reviewed by and received a favourable ethical opinion from Prof. Amare Desta - Director of Studies for this research study and School of Business and Enterprise Ethics Committee of University of the West of Scotland.

14) Who should you contact for further information?

Main Researcher: Mesaj Fernando, < [REDACTED] >.

Director of Studies (Supervisor): Prof. Amare Desta, < [REDACTED] >.

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and for considering to take part in my research study.

Appendix B: Participant Consent Form

School of Business and Enterprise

Research Title: Exploring the factors essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of Business strategy and IT strategy: A case of a UK Forex SME.

Consent Form for Interview

Thank you for reading the information sheet about the interview process. If you are happy to participate then please complete and sign the form below. Please tick the boxes below to confirm that you agree with each statement:

I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet and have had the opportunity to ask questions.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason and without there being any negative consequences. In addition, should I not wish to answer any particular question or questions, I am free to decline.

I understand that my responses will be kept strictly confidential. I understand that my name will not be linked with the research materials, and will not be identified or identifiable in the report or reports that result from this research. I understand that direct quotes from my interview may be used in the study for better discussion.

I agree for this interview to be audio-recorded. I understand that the audio recording made of this interview will be used only for analysis and that extracts from the interview, from which I would not be personally identified, may be used in any conference presentation, report or journal article developed as a result of the research.

I understand that no other use will be made of the recording without my written permission, and that no one outside the main researcher will be allowed access to the original recording.

I agree to take part in this interview.

Name of the participant

Signature

Principal Researcher

Signature

Copies: *Once this has been signed by all parties the participant should receive a copy of the signed and dated participant consent form, and the information sheet. A copy of the signed and dated consent form should be placed in the main project file which must be kept in a secure location.*

Appendix C: Interview Guide

Themes	Sub-Themes	Description	Relevant Literature
1) Strategic alignment and its importance to Forex SMEs.	1.1) What is strategic alignment? 1.2) Difference between strategic alignment for large firms and SMEs 1.3) Is strategic alignment important for SMEs? If so, why it is important? 1.4) Is it hard to achieve strategic alignment in Forex SMEs? 1.5) Requirements for strategic alignment? 1.6) Who involved in strategic alignment process?	It is important to understand what is strategic alignment for Forex SMEs and how strategic alignment impact on Forex SMEs. I should gain much information about strategic alignment for larger firms and how it differ from SMEs alignment. Further, strategic alignment is higher managerial decision therefore who are the participants involve in strategic alignment in Company A.	Distanont and Khongmalai (2020); Street et al. (2017); Cataldo et al. (2012); Prange and Zhao (2018); Bernat and Karabag (2019); Birchall et al. (2004); Sibanda and Ramarathan (2017); Chan and Reich (2007); Wang and Rusu (2018); Jouirou and Kalika (2004).

<p>2) Factors for achieving successful strategic alignment.</p>	<p>2.1) Importance of Communication. 2.2) Importance of Competency. 2.3) Importance of IT governance. 2.4) Importance of scope and architecture of the IT. 2.5) Importance of partnership. 2.6) Importance of human resource skills. 2.7) Senior management knowledge and commitment. 2.8) Supportive organisation culture.</p>	<p>This research is mainly focused on achieving strategic alignment in Forex SMEs. According to Luftman (2004) six dimensions are crucial to achieve strategic alignment (elaborated in 2.1 to 2.6 in sub-themes). However, literature findings further highlighted senior managements' knowledge and their unique commitment assist when achieving strategic alignment for SMEs. Moreover, bureau culture also critical success factor when achieving strategic alignment.</p>	<p>Luftman (2004), Alghazi et al. (2017), Gerow et al. (2014), Krotov (2015), Wu et al. (2015), Alaceva and Rusu (2015), Chatzoglou et al. (2011), Hussin et al. (2002), Reich and Benbasat (2000), Kitsios and Kamariotou (2019), Henriques et al. (2019), Njanka et al. (2021).</p>
<p>3) Challenges faced by organisations in terms of achieving strategic alignment.</p>	<p>3.1) Senior management continuous support on strategic decisions. 3.2) Investment approvals 3.3) Market and government pressure towards strategic decisions.</p>	<p>There are many challenges mentioned in the literature however studies highlighted that most challenges are depends on the industry firm operating. Also lack of corporation from senior management highlighted. But, many studies</p>	<p>Rahimi et al. (2016), Hyder and Lussier (2016), Coltman et al. (2015), Alaceva and Rusu (2015), Teo and Ang (1999), Mitropoulos (2021), Luftman et al. (1999), Leder and Mendelow (1989), Rathod</p>

	<p>3.4) Employee resistance.</p> <p>3.5) Providing employee training.</p> <p>3.6) Approving organisational resources towards strategic decisions.</p> <p>3.7) Flexible organisational governance.</p>	<p>request for exploring new challenges that have not been identified in the literature.</p>	<p>et al. (2019), Abbas et al. (2019).</p>
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Appendix D: Ethical Approval

02/09/2019

Dear W Kurukulasuriya Bossabaduge Fernando,

Your application 8551: Exploring the factors essential for achieving harmonious strategic alignment of Business strategy and IT strategy: a case of a UK Forex SME, submission 6999, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix E: Sample Interview Transcript

Mesaj

Hello, I will formally welcome you. My name is MesajFernando and I am studying my doctoral research in University of the West of Scotland London campus. I am doing my research in strategic alignment in SME business context. The purpose of this interview is to gain an understanding of the current strategic alignment in the Company A. This interview will help me to identify any issues the company currently facing due to strategic alignment of business strategy and IT strategy and to identify any potential areas of improvements which is directly link to strategic alignment. So, whatever information I will get from you will be in the strictest of the confidentiality and will not be shared with anyone. This is only for academic purposes and the information will guide me to have a better result in my research. So, with that in mind, may I ask you the first question, what is your current job title in the bureau?

BM4

I'm operating as a branch manager in the bureau.

Mesaj

And, how long have you been working the company?

BM4

My current role about say 7 years now.

Mesaj

Thank you. can you tell me what is the highest level of education you attained?

BM4

I have a bachelor degree and recently graduated in my MBA.

Mesaj

Thank you. so overall how many years of work experience do you have in the foreign exchange industry?

BM4

Approximately, I would say 10 years now.

Mesaj

For what purposes that you use IT in your work?

BM4

Well, for basic functions like transaction processing and pretty much everything inside the branch is based on IT. Currency ordering, customers stocks ordering, internal communications, AML functions and that sort of things.

Mesaj

What are the products and services your company offer?

BM4

At the branch level we are mainly into buying and selling foreign currency, and the plus, on top of that we do, foreign money transfers, worldwide transfers or any other type of foreign currency transfers which requested by customers. And we do get corporate clients as well so who needs large transactions. It's mostly cash or it can be a transfer as well.

Mesaj

What sort of a technology you think your organisation need?

BM4

Well, quite frankly, for the functions that we perform we need a simple and efficient IT solution. And, it should not be all that sophisticated for us. And the other thing is it should be flexible enough to meet the customer demands on a regular basis because they're ever changing there's no uniform pattern. So you need a flexible and agile operating system and procedures.

Mesaj

thank you. And what is the importance of having a sustainable IT services and practices to your branch?

BM4

Information Technology plays a big role because the in terms of increasing efficiency of the business and gaining a competitive advantage it is a vital fact. And the other thing is to maintain customer information and customer confidentiality because the new GDPR regulations so yeah basically to adhere to new industry regulations and to increase the efficiency of the transactions. Because all our transactions are secure and it is important that our IT services and systems must be sustainable, harmonious at all times.

Mesaj

How does current IT services and practices (or IT goals and mission) support your branch in achieving your branch sales target?

BM4

The IT services do at the moment, do support the current requirements however, I feel at the branch level achieving the sales targets there are few challenges because of the particular IT system that we are using at the moment and the governance that's surrounding the IT system. So, because of that, the branch staff as a branch manager I feel that our efficient, our performance levels, has not been improved in such a way because of the new systems and procedures.

Mesaj

So are you saying the new system should be improved or the people who are involved in the process should be aware of the current situation in your branch?

BM4

I feel that the IT governance should be more customer focus, whereas we could provide a more flexible service to the customers. Now we are a bit restricted in certain functions, which in turn bounces back on the actual revenue that we are generating in a branch level. So the IT vision, I believe it's to do with the IT strategic team that needs to understand what really is happening inside the branches and I think there's a bit of a disconnected there.

Mesaj

So, are you saying because of the disconnected situation, current IT strategic plans and business plans are not in a supportive platform right now?

BM4

Exactly they are not in the same frequency I believe.

Mesaj

Thank you. Do you think the competitive advantage can be achieved with the current IT practices and procedures?

BM4

Generally the whole purpose in foreign exchange business is to gain and keep competitive advantage when compares to your competitors. So in our situation in terms of competitive advantage I don't fully agree to that. Because the current strategic practices, the flexibility in terms of operating in a branch that IT is governing we are being restricted in many number of avenues. So, because of that there's less flexibility and in this day and age, flexibility is key because customers have different requirements from one to the other. Yes, so there's more of a

blanket programme running for, which is not really meeting the all the customer demands. But I should say most yes but there's a bit that we lose and keep losing. We have ignored performance indicators and that what needs to be improve further and shine.

Mesaj

If I may ask you, did you faced these issues recently or are you believe since the bureau was taking over or the acquisition happened you start to face these issues and lost business flexibility?

BM4

Absolutely and absolutely, that's a key thing because we used to be much more flexible and much more customer focused, and Information Technology was to supporting the customer requirements. Now it's kind of the other way around where the customers have to gear into our new IT policies and procedures and our business strategy. Which is not a good situation right now compare to our market and competitor dynamics.

Mesaj

What does excellent customer service mean to your branch or to your company like customer satisfaction as a whole?

BM4

Well, this is one of the key things that the company is actually expecting out of us, and this is the top in the key performance indicators that the company is looking at. So, in the business strategy, the business vision and mission, customer satisfaction, excellent customer service is at the top of the food chain and it's a must. But, at the moment, because of the, like I said, because of the IT infrastructure and IT practices and the regulations surrounding that, I mean the way we works right now...unfortunately I can't fully agree that we meet the standards. So, customer service is, in my opinion it's too fold and it's how you present plus what services we offer, because they're not really there to, you know, make build a relationship with the people.

Mesaj

Are you saying due to current IT and business plans and practices the customer satisfaction is not at a good position?

BM4

Yes, they are satisfied with the, with the staff, however, about the service that the company is delivering there's a bit of a question mark.

Mesaj

How current IT vision and practices are supporting your company, branch products and services towards customers?

BM4

Well, of course the current IT infrastructure is quite capable of communicating with the customers in many levels like - email facilities, SMS automated assembly services, there's a company website, of course. However, the IT department service levels are a bit of.. a bit of, it's not actually at an optimal level, as we expect.

Mesaj

Why are you saying that it's not optimal level?

BM4

because of the current strategic hierarchy that's inside the in terms of providing solutions at the individual branch levels because of the hierarchy that we are supposed to follow..there's been delays in receiving the required services and maintenance for particular situations you don't realise in individual branches. So the full cycle of the strategic plans, the procedures chain and areas. Yeah. So just because of that there has been delays and which in turn knock on effect on the Customer Service Level, Business Level and then affecting at the end of the day. Because of these issues you know, I think our efficiency and of course our productivity in branch level is not at a good position.

Mesaj

Thank you. my next question is, have you faced or currently facing any sort of difficulties when accessing business information at work?

BM4

Internal information I would say is accessible, we do have internet communications running, that's okay I am satisfied with that. However, there can be improvements made in terms of gaining a competitive advantage by providing us with competitive information like, market information, real time updates of market news, the foreign exchange industry related information and what's going on around the world in certain markets, certain countries and especially with the current travel restrictions and travel bans and so on and so forth so we can advise the customers on that. That way we gain more trust from the customers. But that information is not freely available to us right now. So I believe, at branch level we need more information specifically, about what is happening in the environmental information in the industry that we are operating in.

Mesaj

From your answer, I am sensing that information availability should be there freely to grow your company business?

BM4

Of course, that's it.

Mesaj

Before the acquisition did you had this freedom to operate in your branch?

BM4

actually, to a certain extent we had freedom and we could access certain information so we can generate more growth and profitability to the firm overall targets. And plus the management, the IT management at that time actually provided us at the beginning of the day, and throughout the day provided us with current updates on competitor exchange rates and what's going on around the world and in the market, which was relevant to our business..so that was provided to us but at the moment there is nothing. I mean generally, whole idea of having the business vision and IT vision is to support the business performance and growth. Accessing business information is truly vital and without it specially, like Forex firms SMEs like us cannot go further.

Mesaj

Okay, thank you for your answer. In terms of problem solving, how does current IT strategy support your branch? As in how current IT strategy support to solve your branch business problems?

BM4

you see the current IT systems and procedures, and the infrastructure that's been used is fully capable of meeting the operational business requirements, no doubt I mean it's a very sophisticated method. However, with the problem that I see is, there is, I believe there is a communication barrier between the IT department management and branch level management, about what's been really going on in the branch level. And what's required as an IT solution for that particular requirement. There's a bit of a gap between the understanding level between the two parties... from senior management team and the actual branch level managers. To my best understanding senior management does not understand what truly happening in the branch level. So there's a bit of a communication gap, there's a bit of business operations understanding gap.

Mesaj

You mean what sort of strategic solutions branch need, whether current strategic solutions between business and IT supporting or not?

BM4

Exactly..what is exactly needed as an IT solution to carry out the day to day business operations...I think there's a gap.

Mesaj

Do you think before the acquisition branch problem solving skills at the same level like you mentioned now or different?

BM4

I believe, previous management had more support than the current corporate environments. Because the previous management was kind of in sync with what was really going on in the branch level and the IT manager and the IT department in the previous company actually had hands on experience in the branch level. So they had a much better understanding when they were designing the IT plans and procedures and how it should support to business plans and procedures and also how we can improve if we want. But at the moment at the corporate level that our IT experts yes no doubt that this is better IT strategy I am sure....However, their understanding of the branch operations is very minimum. So they may create and design and wonderful IT infrastructure, but whether it's suitable for our SME business culture and sustainability is the question.

Mesaj

Overall, in your opinion, how important is IT to your bureau or branch level?

BM4

IT is a key requirement for the branches. Not to say that it should be complex and it should be high end.. high tech IT system but IT is a must. Because, the industry that we are operating in that's heavily IT based. The foreign exchange industry as a whole and trading platforms, everything swarming on IT, and at the branch level, obviously for us to carry out our day to day stock ordering and other major functions of customer service and transaction processing - IT plays a key role and it's highly important.

Mesaj

Can you tell me your bureau's mission and goals?

BM4

Well, at the moment the company is looking at..honestlyspeaking..I'm not really conversant on the actual vision but about the mission - yes, we have been given certain goals to meet. Some of them are like increase the customer numbers by 10% for the financial year and maintain 100% customer satisfaction. This means to say there shouldn't be any complaints coming out from the customers in relation to customer service levels or personal level, or in terms of unavailability of the currencies that they require, so they expect the good business performance. No complaints whatsoever, coming out from a customer. So that's 100% customer satisfaction level and to increase the average transaction value by 5% for this financial year. So these are the actual key goals that I could remember this is the mission of our current business units.

Mesaj

Thank you. To what extent do you think that current IT strategy supporting organisation mission and goals? Or in what way business strategy and IT strategy supporting to each other?

BM4

I have to say that it's support but it's limited support at the moment. The current IT practices and restrictions actually hindering fully achieving branch goals. because there are certain features and policies that we need to adhere to. This is not to say that we expect IT department to do anything against the regulation. However, from certain customer perspective, there are expectations from the customer side at a branch level. So, current IT vision and practices are not flexible enough and I think our current whatever the IT policies and infrastructure is not flexible enough to meet those demands in the foreign exchange market. These demands are quite dynamic. And demands can change in a second. Although within regulations certain customers have some extreme requirements. And they could be spontaneous you know... their travel plans change at the last minute. To give you an example especially when it comes to changing foreign exchange rates to retain the customer, requesting support from the IT department about any IT issues in my branch - these type of things I think we are lagging behind. Just because of the stringent policies within the IT strategy.

Mesaj

What I understood from your answer now ever since the acquisition has happened the given IT strategy is not supporting the bureau's performance?

BM4

Exactly because previously we had enough branch staff and especially the managers had enough authority to make any significant branch decisions. If I want to override any corporate Forex rates as an example in terms of decision making, there was more authority allocated to the branch managers because they're the ones who had the frontline and very limited time to

coordinate and get approval when there's real time transaction happening. So at the moment there's nothing as such, it's what dictated on a system that we need to follow which is not always the most suitable solution for the customer's current measures.

Mesaj

Are you suggesting due to current IT strategic plan your branch customers are somewhat at a dissatisfied and confusing point right now?

BM4

Absolutely... my corporate customers don't much care about internal strategies or rules what they expect is good efficient service. That's the definition to my understanding.

Mesaj

thank you, do you think the current IT strategy quite flexible to your bureau business operations?

BM4

Actually, this is a good question..the current IT strategy comprises with some complexities. I should say even this question was raised many times in branch meetings and no answer so far. Complexities arise when corporate strategies introduced to SME business environment. I mean the corporate blanket programme that's running across a number of bureaus that's not suitable for the London branches that we are working operating in, because the market itself is quite demanding and quite competitive there's enough and more places for customers to go to collect their currencies, or finish up their transaction, there's enough competition around available in and around London. So having a blanket programme doesn't actually help my branch operations.

Mesaj

Are you suggesting to have good performance in the bureau, management should consider these concerns and improve the flexibility?

BM4

Absolutely mate. there's too much of a hierarchy that's operating in our current IT strategy and inside the IT department.

Mesaj

Did you mean IT department does not have a clear picture about the strategic plans between business and IT?

BM4

that's a another major issue at the moment because the IT team, don't seem to fully understand the current requirements of the foreign exchange market that we're operating in. I am sure really they are experts of the IT side of it, but on the business side of the picture I don't think that they have deeper understanding and knowledge of the market and how to make a move in the foreign exchange market you know.

Mesaj

How well does the current IT strategy fits to your bureau's organisational culture?

BM4

if I were to go back to the previous setup in our bureau it was a very, it was pretty much a traditional culture.... where it was a close with team, communication was very prompt and very understanding because from the higher positions the strategic decision making team to the branch managers and to the staff at each branch, there was a good understanding. Everybody knew what the branches are supposed to be doing. So the IT team, the senior management team, and even the CEO they knew exactly what needs to be done at a branch level to improve customer service and business growth. We were able to reach to people at any level, at any given time it was, it was very open communication that we maintain because of that there was upward and downward communication happening very smooth, and it was very timely and if there was a customer requirement that the obtaining approvals and any IT solutions that we needed was quite prompt. Because the power distance was not that far. Unfortunately, at the moment, the biggest issue is the communication and the because of corporate hierarchy that the business is changing. There's minimum communication that's happening now and then once all, even if we do communicate with them.. then procedures to follow the internal procedures are actually kind of getting things delayed. I mean, If we look at the corporate mission, that the business mission for retail foreign exchange unit; we are not fully free to achieve those targets because we tried to follow the procedures in the company.

Mesaj

You said there' s an issue in the corporate hierarchy and culture and due to acquisition the bureau as a SME now working with a large corporation standards. Do you think there can be conflict on how large firms support SMEs?

BM4

Yes I mean in a corporate environment, obviously...previously, we were a standalone business operating under much freedom SME, but however now that we've been acquired by a corporate organisation, so, obviously, we have to adhere to the internal policies of the corporate body. So, we can't operate in isolation, away from the regulations and their way of doing things. But

foreign exchange branch level... foreign exchange is a very fast paced, very fast moving business and which needs a lot of flexibility and operational knowledge which you don't find in corporate bodies or strategies. To answer what you asked me is that, corporate bodies should be aware of how to support each other with SMEs and they should have thorough knowledge about how SMEs business vision runs and what they expect from the IT vision in simple words. Be much friendlier and senior people must know that SMEs always working under different environmental uncertainties.

Mesaj

Okay. how current IT procedures and technologies are supporting their business objectives? as in like how the current IT procedures supporting organisational objectives.. how the business works and how the IT supporting for that ?

BM4

My personal opinion is the current IT systems and procedures are somewhat overpowering the core business at branch level. I mean we got very complicated, very advanced IT technology and services and systems running, which is not required. But what we need is a reliable, simple operating system, and strategies for us to carry out, day to day transactions plus our day to day activities, which in turn provides us enough flexibility. The more complicated the system and the procedures or strategies become more complicated and more rigid with our functions become and we get tied down. So, currently, we are not flexible enough to meet the very highly demanding customer requirements.

Mesaj

You are saying technology is somewhat trying to control business vision and goals?

BM4

you see most of the branch managers and branch staff they are quite good at understanding the customer requirements and they understand the business. However, the because of the restrictions that's been put on by IT system which was supposed to be supporting us in the answer... the whole purpose of having technology is to support your business, of course, but that's not happening, actually, on the contrary, it's actually restricting us on our day to day business.

Mesaj

thank you for your explanation. Can you explain to me what factors would support on increasing the branch revenues?

BM4

well we essentially we need more flexibility in terms of processing foreign exchange transactions... to certain currencies for certain transactions. it's not to say that we, the first thing that we do retain the customer, but we need when needed, we need to have the flexibility in hand, so that we don't have to call and delay the transaction and in turn, lose the customer some in certain cases. So we need that change of foreign exchange rate flexibility and business understanding. Stock availability more often than not, we have some main currencies unavailable on given days. Also, to my personal believe is that, revenue is not just you know do more transactions and make profits, but how we prepare to external environment changes as well. How we can quickly change or adapt into new changes and make sure bureau's firm vision and targets are achievable with the current circumstances. We need rapid response from senior management if we need to get an approval for any corporate foreign exchange transactions and of course rapid response from the IT department as well in case if my branch facing IT disruption. because of the current hierarchy, it has to go through quite a few people for us to get authorization.

Mesaj

So your saying because of the current business and IT hierarchy your branch facing problems in terms of revenues?

BM4

Absolutely mate. because it's too much of hierarchy that's being put on a very real time fast paced business and so we can't have that delay because we are lose the customer or in words my branch performance.

Mesaj

So, are you saying they design the hierarchy in wrong way?

BM4

It's about support what I meant. The hierarchy is not supporting in terms of flexibility. This structure is not matching for small business like us. Our organisational structure is simple. we have branches in London and outside London and the top leadership in Ireland should know whether their hierarchy is matching for our business environment.

Mesaj

Okay, do you think current IT capabilities are capable of generating more profits and growth for the business?

BM4

well I mean it's twofold I should say, compare to the previous technology.. customer communication has become better, I think, at least a little bit better. However, because of the

complexities of the current system and procedures that we are using right now for transaction processing in branch, that's to advance for us. As a result, the user friendliness now for branch staff that it used to be a 2 or 3 click user actions from start to finish on the transactions; and now we have to go through phases of each transaction that requires about 5 or 6 clicks. That whole is a delay, and then there's some areas that mistakes could happen you know, after all we all human beings... because too many functions and we have to concentrate more on IT functions than the actual transaction. So because of that, there may be chances of making mistakes than own mistakes before. So, I believe although the current system is quite advanced and quite sophisticated, we don't need that. The bureau need a simple solution, which increases the efficiency of the business performance and operations.

Mesaj

Thank you for your explanation. When you at work how do you hear about any updates which is related to IT? specifically to Forex IT network.

BM4

Well, quite frankly, we don't know much of what's going on in terms of why updates are done, or when it's done. To the extent that what the IT department is pretty much doing because we are actually very minimum or mostly no communication or direct communication between the IT team and us of the branch level.

Mesaj

So what I sense from your answer is that, IT manager not that much supportive towards your branch business operations?

BM4

mostly all this is arranged, we don't have direct access... all this is arranged through the area management team who are basically senior business managers. And the communication about what IT amendments are coming up and why it's being done and when it's being done all this is communicated by the area managers. Pretty much area managers and they are the senior management of our bureau now basically. They involved in all senior and strategic decisions in the bureau now. Every decision whether it's IT or account receivable or business related all stuff. So overall, there is no direct communication as such within the IT department. So, in turn, we do have some issues where certain updates and certain functions are introduced. There's this minimum explanation given on what to be done if there's an error, and we had to follow the reverse part where we got the information from here to go first to the area manager, and then they relate it to the IT manager and then it comes back from the same path... so this is a bit of a delay. To put you in write picture, there's a major communication issues I mean business strategic and IT strategic and strategic movements in the company.. in every corner in the

company I mean, how to communicate, what are you communicating, how board level and strategic decisions pass it to staff. These are fundamental bricks mate we are talking about. Not bloody rocket science.

Mesaj

What you just mentioned to me now, have you informed your senior managers about these issues ? when you ask for support what's their reaction? Can you tell me in detail if possible?

BM4

yeah like I said they are not IT experts, and they don't have freedom to provide a solutions directly. Basically, they are just pass the ball to relevant party and do nothing. I mean in a way speaking basically lame way of thinking so rather than me speaking directly to IT department and getting the necessary services or whatever updates or whatever that's needed for the branch what has failed. We had to go through this channel. And because of that, because there's no direct communication. There's very limited response, given for particular scenario.

Mesaj

right. Can you explain to me whether the current technology which is provided by the corporate sector, is it easier to use at your branch business operations? is it helpful to achieve your branch targets?

BM4

I personally believe, I think the technology that we're using at the moment is too advanced, for a simple fast paced SME business that we are running on a day to day basis. We don't need this much of a complex complicated high-end IT solutions or higher IT infrastructures to be, for that matter. So, due to these reasons business plans cannot truly connect with IT solutions because business requests are simple.

Mesaj

Is it possible you can explain to me little bit in detail please?

BM4

I mean first we have to identify our business platform and must have a clear idea that this is what our business targets and goals trying to achieve. Senior leadership should have a clear understanding about what clearly needs for business to achieve those targets or vision. We are not high-tech business or manufacturing business or security firm. This is retail forex industry and it's quite fast. Technological strategies should match 100% or at least let's say be supportive

to business parameters. So to put it in simple terms, actually the tech, it's not so much to do with the technology, not being able to understand - the problem is the technology is too advance for us. And it understands more than it should. also, it requires staff to perform more functions, than necessary to carry out the simple transaction. So, obviously, this is a failure in technology design stage. So most of the team members have had difficulties in understanding the system and following each procedure for per transaction. See, again, on that basis these issues affects our branch revenue, efficiency and productivity and finally aligning purposes.

Mesaj

Have you raised these problems to your senior management attention?

BM4

of course I have raised so many times and I had arguments with them as well. I mean, we do requests, certain times for more simplicity. However, because of the corporate infrastructure because of the corporate leadership in Ireland and they have to maintain their internal policies and strategies, those strategies have to be high priority and we have to follow those strategies.. where the strategies should be aligned with our Bureau and then the integration happens. That sort of integration has not happened, so because of them they made the imposed upon us. This sophisticated IT system and strategies which they have users for their statistical analysis and this and that. Because of that, there are so many functions that we need to perform per forex transaction in our branch now. well that's not the right way you know that's affecting my branch performance and productivity.

Mesaj

Thank you for your answer. Can you tell me, are you satisfied with the current IT resources in the bureau or in your branch?

BM4

Again, going back to what I mentioned earlier, because of the complexity of the systems that we're operating in there and there could many things that could go wrong and actually most often, they do go wrong. And because of the hierarchy that we need to follow up, there's a big delay in receiving the required services or the particular hardware, software, computers, scanners and printers which is truly important for daily business operations. And then we have to go through that process where previously or before the acquisition happened it was quite prompt or quite easily we can get the resources from the senior management and honestly, my life was very much easier that time. But, now since we have to go through this whole steps of procedures and I am facing huge stress and tension in my branch now.

Mesaj

Thank you. Why do you think the technology is so important to your bureau and of course to foreign exchange industry?

BM4

Well, I'm operating in a localised branch and we are very much attached to the global IT Foreign Exchange market, we kind of port that our customers are able to get connected to the international foreign exchange market, which is essentially run by information technology, so our IT is so important to us to keep up with the global foreign exchange market and in turn to manage our stocks in the branch and day to day operations. so it is so important that we need update from what's going on in the market, and our competitors trends, so that we can pass that information on to the customers. So, yes, we are highly heavily dependent on information technology. And that's why our business goals and platforms must aligned with information technology so comprehensively clearly. But that's not to say that we need a sophisticated information technology solution.

Mesaj

What sort of a support are you currently getting from IT department? what is your idea regarding that?

BM4

I personally believe that we need a direct access line to the IT department who will in turn directly deal with the branch requirements and in a prompt way. To do that I think they need more personnel IT resources for the IT department to meet branch requirements. Now for us, in London there's quite a bit of branches, so if there's only a couple of people in the IT department who are dedicated to service... and in branches suddenly when things go wrong many branch managers will expect quick positive responses from the IT support team. And delay in meeting those needs, provide some IT personal to deal with it or to be provided remote access is not enough resources available inside the IT department as number one, and there is no direct communication between us and the IT department also I believe a major issue right now. We need direct communication channel for all our business IT issues, as I said earlier our customers are so demanding and so uncertain about their Forex needs. Most of them are last minute buyers. Theoretically and practically, I cannot put on them on customer queue till we fix our IT issues. It will be a war zone, if I do that in my branch.

Mesaj

Are you suggesting the IT department is busy handling other branches and maybe they do not have enough man power in the IT department to handle all branch queries?

BM4

Exactly so, because of that the response time has been very long and solutions are always temporary and they are not satisfactory to my understanding. Also, it's not rapid enough for our branch performance KPIs to be update.

Mesaj

thank you for your answer. Did you experience any difficulties when you trying to access into main IT system? are you satisfied with the access or not happy ?

BM4

you see on a regular basis, there are issues. The one main issue is that the current transaction processing system is a web based solution. So as you can imagine that the internet connectivity has issues at the moment. Yes...so I would say it's about 98% at the moment. because the uptime should be at least 99.999, and we have on a regular basis this internet ISP issues that have been very annoying and we cannot perform the transactions on peak hours. So there has been that sort of problems that we are facing on a regular basis. In the branches, there are delays because even if there's no ISP issues, because of the web based solution in transaction processing there are lags.

Mesaj

What did you mean by lags?

BM4

For example, this happened many times to me. say when I am with a corporate client who like to purchase \$10,000 and middle of the transaction it could lag and the transaction could hanged and wait and wait for couple of minutes till next step to come up on the screen. So because of that, it's inconvenient because it could sometimes lead up to a several minutes also. By that time, my client will not be pleased and he will cancel the transaction and go to one of our competitors. These are MSB operations and no person would like to stay longer with cash in their pockets or in their hands. The customers are in a hurry and they visit the branch during their lunch time the office staff, and some visit my branch on their way to the airport. So you can see they don't have much time to spend with us, just for this because our IT systems are not working properly. These sort of things I think could have been avoided if we had a simple solution running as a localised on a localised server, which would have been much more faster. Sadly because of the sophisticated IT visions and solutions, our business performance at a confusion point.

Mesaj

Can you explain to me, whether your branch faced or currently facing any constraints or limitations because of the business-IT alignment procedure?

BM4

Well yeah, because of the web based solution that we are operating on, because of the vulnerabilities that are inherent in a web based solution there are so many restrictions, that are being put on us in terms of, accessing certain other financial or competitor/s websites or other services that are required to perform our transactions plus so giving customers information what they asked for. In abstract, web access to other information is currently at a restricted level, just because they can protect the current IT infrastructure, the main IT mainframe from computer viruses and hacks.

Mesaj

Don't you think they are trying to minimise the risk that systems getting expose to other third parties or untrusted IT programs in the internet? or maybe they do not like to get risk chances?

BM4

I cannot agree to you completely actually. If current IT goal is trying to put up restrictions to current business plan, then, of course, our company business and IT strategy alignment will be 100% failure...Let's think in this way, because it's a corporate, there are number of functions that's being carried out on the same platform in the corporate business. But however when it comes to branch level, foreign exchange industry, we need to be isolated from the corporate business and we need to be given a simple solution just to run our day to day transactions. Now that we are part of that entire corporate business, they need to protect that entire system for any vulnerability on the internet. So because of that, their security and the risk they are trying to minimise, minimise the functions that we have access to. Plus, again, like I said, because that's one thing and the other thing is because of the complexities of the system and unfriendly procedures, there are delays in processing each transaction, and of course, the restrictions placed on us, directly affect on our productivity and efficiency no doubt.

Mesaj

Are there any challenges your branch faced because of the business and IT strategy alignment process?

BM4

I've been told by most of my branch staff members that, they find it difficult to understand certain functions and practices that are on the current system, sometimes access issues, it could be system function issues, because it's an over complicated system even the training platform

that we are using it.. has been complicated because it's a web based programme which is run on the cloud called Leap training. Okay, now look, so not most of them, but most of my branch staff are quite savvy on their business on the foreign exchange side of it, but not everybody's IT savvy. When complicated IT strategic procedures and system is introduced to the branch, the good people who knows how to do foreign exchange have difficulties in performance. Because of the unclearness in the system. So there's a deeper conflict between, between the business strategy and the IT strategy. I have worked in the company for many years and I know for a fact that our senior team members don't have a clear knowledge about how this foreign exchange industry works, and how our bureau operates. Their support on changing any organisational policies which we know definitely it's going to be positive for branch...but they won't down their attitudes. Rarely they visit my branch and ask for their support. I think there should be more training provide direct training provide by the responsible parties for these IT solutions to branch staff, rather than guiding them remotely or, you know, when a problem occurs. Or giving solutions rather than that at the beginning of the production of the IT solution or the new IT strategy or system or whatever it is. There should be proper formal training offered to the staff so that they can, they have enough time to learn it, and then practice it in the branch. Now what has happened is, as in real time while serving customers in the their till, my staff have to learn while they are doing their job. And that's not acceptable, not supportive in terms of meeting our branch targets. Resource management is very tidy in the company therefore, as they implementing the alignment, the whole process creates some rigidness in business environment. Another challenge is regulatory compliance and risk management procedures which they have introduced to us, which is very rigid and strict to the point.

Mesaj

Thank you sir for your answer. What are your opinions about the bureau's business strategy and IT strategy alignment? or in terms of whole company?

BM4

I believe that the alignment has not happened in a way that improves the foreign exchange trading business. The main thing is because of the whole complicated strategy and systems that been imposed upon us by the corporate organisation, as opposed to what we were before as an operating as an independent SME, where the power distance was very close and open communication and reaction from the senior management was very quick. That time our CEO was very sensitive for branch performance and issues because there was no acquisition terms. They trusted their strategic plans and their solutions were much more efficient and solutions provided to us were provided in a real time, much faster, which is suitable for real time transaction. Well, because of the corporate organisation now that we have changed into a whole different way of doing things. And this way of doing things were not suitable for a fast paced business, simple business like foreign exchange branch or company.

Mesaj

Based on your work experiences with the company, how would you compare and contrast the current strategic alignment against the previous management strategic alignment? [*researcher explains: previous management means the senior team who controlled the company before the acquisition*]

BM4

Yeah, well, the previous senior management, when the company was operating as an individual, independent SME on its own, there was, much more reliability and flexibility in terms of receiving feedback, in terms of receiving solutions and there was no borders between departments, there was no specific IT department that we cannot directly contact; we could contact anyone pretty much from IT department to the HR to anyone you can easily access them, and then they will provide direct branch level, whatever specific requirements, per branch. There was enough resources, enough work motivation and enough flexibility for the team to operate in. Plus, everyone in the company from IT department to HR to the senior management, everybody understood what the core of the business is and they put the customer at the front. So if there was a customer requirement, they were flexible enough, agile and they had a bigger risk appetite in terms, of exchange rates and so on and so forth; to retain the customers and that's how this business grew. That time, both our business and IT clearly understood customer is the top priority and they are the key terminology in our business. So whatever policies internal procedures, didn't impose many restrictions on, you know on branch staff and operations. However, now as opposed to working with current corporate environment, their risk appetite is very low, which means to say that they will not easily change exchange rates or policies, just because of customer requirement or branch staff requirement. And their understanding, corporate level understanding of the reality of London market or branches, the whole, how it works, and the uncertain environment that we are operating in the challenges and the competition especially; that's available for our customer for us to lose a customer is so easy. So the customer centric approach from this corporate people I think it's very minimum and disappointing. There much of rigid structure suitable for different type of industry maybe, but for this industry very little flexibility.

Mesaj

right. What I understood from your answer is that, since you said customers are the whole point in your industry and all business policies should support to that, including business strategy and IT strategy. So your bureau's business strategy mainly focusing on customer satisfaction and profit growth, it's unique to your company survival. So, in that sense the corporate body should understand that business strategy cannot be change and only the IT strategy should be more cooperative to perform your business tasks? Did I say it right?

BM4

Indeed it is. if I put it in this way, if there were at least once a year consultation is done with the branch managers and the IT department and the senior management team, this would have been avoided. But it has not happened since the acquisition. So they operate under a different mentality, or a different understanding about the business, whereas we operate in a, we are facing the front plane on a day to day basis. So, our information, our knowledge is not passed on to them so that they can design and gear, their internal strategies and policies to suit our environment and industry. So there's this gap is there, and the corporate environment blindly has imposed upon us, the IT strategy, the technology and hierarchy. so, that's not suitable for us in conclusion.

Mesaj

thank you. Do you see any future opportunities for your branch or for the whole bureau itself, in terms of IT ? Are you see any good doors which will bring good profit margins? the way current business strategy gets help from the current technology ?

BM4

yeah, see improvements in the sense there should be changes made to the current IT strategy and the current IT setup. because to begin with, it's over complicated the whole, whole transaction process. And most of the IT functions and practices are not relevant to our branch operations. And there's way too many functions, that are imposed upon us. And then, in turn, the branch business unit mission and vision, especially about the mission, we are unable to reach our goals for a given period. Because of the complexities in the business and in the corporate business as a whole. So, part of that is the IT infrastructure which is, which could be geared, which I believe is customizable or changeable to our particular requirements that would have given us a really good opportunity and good support. but at the moment that's not happening; because there's a bit of understanding issues between what's required and what's provided.

Mesaj

thank you for your answer. my next question, from the alignment process of business and IT strategy, did you noticed any success and failure factors mainly related to strategic use of IT in your branch?

BM4

To some extent, yes I believe. Because the current IT strategic practices in some way heavily focused on IT security. which is really good, because when you hear about the TravelEx unfortunate incident where hackers penetrated their main IT system and terminals where they lost millions of English pounds. So, in that sense, that's been right up maintaining a very good security level infrastructure. We have been exposed the branch staff all the relevant or not we

have been given the opportunity all the exposure to innovative technologies and other related software business platforms. I have to admit that, there are some good support, and some features but how far it's applicable, or relevant is a question. but however, we have been given the opportunity to explore a number of software and other IT services. I believe that the current technology has bit of room. If there's any integration or any future business changes take place I think the current technology is capable of meeting the requirements. Because it is a broad sophisticated IT vision which consists all brand new technological platforms. However, even though it gives problems to our business operations but it is an up to date system. So these are the advantages that I see. although in turn, because of that, there are inherent problems because there is lack of training given to us on the particular systems, and the relevancy of the systems that they're introducing to us, and the practices that we need to follow and the functions that we need to follow on a regular basis per transaction. There are too many unwanted steps, which I can see it as the negative sides.

Mesaj

overall, do you think the IT strategy really connected with the business strategy in your branch or in the whole bureau?

BM4

in a few words I think, I would say that there is a disconnect between our business goals, and the current IT solution that's been provided. The technological applications and the personnel involved in the IT team and of course, the IT software that's being used it does not fully understand the real dynamics of the foreign exchange business. On a regular basis, on a day to day basis, what happens in a branch, I think there's, there's a gap in the understanding < + >. So because of that, it has been somewhat difficult for us, branch staff at the front line to get to the customer and fulfil the customer expectations. We know exactly, what customers are expecting from us, but sadly, corporate and IT procedures are not that friendly and not chasing business productivity or performance anymore, but the satisfaction of rules. So because of that their system is not fully geared or ready for our business to grow. So overall, if I would say there are complications. In terms of customer stock ordering, standard currency stock ordering restrictions, how we request major rate changes, internet disruptions, resource distributions, so all these are actually, in terms of flexibility we are so tied down. So, before it was not the case, we could meet the customer requirements to a much greater extent, as compared to now. Sad to say, it's pretty much has come to take it or leave it situation and, which is not suitable in this day and age, in terms of retail customer service business. I mean, senior leadership should know that, there are quite a few hurdles that we need to jump through, and not all the customers are willing to tolerate that kind of a situation what I mentioned now.

Mesaj

thank you for your answer. my last question for the interview. based on your overall work experiences can you explain your view on this statement, having a clear vision for business strategy and IT strategy integration is an essential part of future success. what is your view on this regard?

BM4

well, quite frankly, IT should not govern the business. we are a small foreign exchange company and our focus should be on meeting customer requirements in terms of foreign exchange. Now Information Technology is only supposed to be a support service in order for us to carry out business transactions and do other necessary business activities. but at the moment what has happened is technology has governed us, in a way, in terms of providing customer service. Now, that is, I believe that's the wrong approach to the entire business because technology or the IT strategy should only be viewed as a support service and should not dictate terms to us. It should actually provide a platform that our daily business operations becomes easier, rather than over complicating and giving more stress at work. It should be able to minimise paper usage, it should be able to minimise time which we spent or utilised per transaction, these sort of things should happen, and provide us with real time information about market, what's going on in the current global financial market and new business trends yes and the news. This is what I expect from, from an IT service; because once when IT gets involved in the business operations in terms of dictating terms and if our functions, if we lose our agility, because of the IT restrictions; now, that's, that's going to become a hurdle, or a challenge.

Mesaj

working on a challenging environment always risky and can negatively impact on your business reputation?

BM4

true mate we run the business risk of losing customers than gaining them because of in simple words that's what's happening. We're losing customers we risk losing customers because we are not flexible in our business operations.

Mesaj

Thank you so much sir for your time. Are there any questions or queries about this interview?

BM4

No, thank you.

Mesaj

The interview will be transcribed and will send you a copy of it once it finish. Thank you sir.

Appendix F: NVivo Screenshot

The screenshot displays the NVivo software interface. The top menu bar includes File, Home, Import, Create, Explore, and Share. Below the menu is a ribbon with various tools such as Cut, Copy, Paste, Merge, Properties, Open, Memo Link, Create As Code, Create As Cases, Query, Visualize, Code, Auto Code, Range Code, Uncode, Case Classification, File Classification, Detail View, Undock, Sort By, List View, Navigation View, and Find.

The main workspace is titled "Nodes" and contains a table with the following columns: Name, Files, References, Created On, Created By, Modified On, and Modified By. The table lists several themes and their associated nodes, including:

- THEME 1 - Exploring Strategic Alignment in a Forex SME (16 files, 168 references)
- THEME 2 - Challenges to face When Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A (16 files, 71 references)
- THEME 3 - Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment of Business and IT Strategy of a Forex SME (16 files, 88 references)

Each theme is expanded to show its constituent nodes, such as COMMUNICATION, COMPETENCY, HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS, IT GOVERNANCE, PARTNERSHIP, SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT, and WEB (INTERNET) SYSTEMS for Theme 1.

At the bottom left, a status bar indicates "MEZI 3 items selected".

Name	Files	References	Created On	Created By	Modified On	Modified By
THEME 1 - Exploring Strategic Alignment in a Forex SME	16	168	6/14/2021 12:01 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 8:15	MEZI
COMMUNICATION	14	27	10/20/2021 2:45 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:45	MEZI
COMPETENCY	14	36	10/20/2021 2:37 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:45	MEZI
HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS	10	11	10/20/2021 2:46 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:45	MEZI
IT GOVERNANCE	13	37	10/20/2021 2:45 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:45	MEZI
PARTNERSHIP	10	16	10/20/2021 2:45 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:45	MEZI
SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT	13	32	10/20/2021 2:45 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:46	MEZI
WEB (INTERNET) SYSTEMS	9	9	11/18/2021 9:35 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:46	MEZI
THEME 2 - Challenges to face When Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A	16	71	6/16/2021 12:11 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 8:20	MEZI
RESISTANCE TO CHANGE CULTURE	7	14	6/4/2021 9:31 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:56	MEZI
SLOW DECISION MAKING DUE TO STRINGENT COMPANY POLICIES	9	17	5/31/2021 8:25 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:57	MEZI
THE LACK OF COORDINATION BETWEEN IT DEPARTMENT AND BUSINESS MANAGERS	12	26	5/31/2021 8:40 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:57	MEZI
THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT	9	14	6/2/2021 5:33 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:57	MEZI
THEME 3 - Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment of Business and IT Strategy of a Forex SME	16	88	6/15/2021 5:13 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 8:20	MEZI
APPROPRIATE DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISATIONAL RESOURCES	10	19	5/31/2021 7:33 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:48	MEZI
EFFECTIVE CROSS-DEPARTMENT COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION	9	11	5/31/2021 8:01 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:48	MEZI
MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT	13	17	5/31/2021 8:03 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:48	MEZI
REGULAR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRONTLINE STAFFS	9	9	11/20/2021 1:28 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:48	MEZI
SUPPORTIVE ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE	12	32	5/31/2021 7:37 PM	MEZI	1/23/2022 7:48	MEZI

Appendix G: Example of Transcript Analysis

This section includes print-out of an interview transcript from NVivo, which was then subsequently manually analysed.

Mesaj

Hello, I will formally welcome you. My name is Mesaj Fernando and I am studying my doctoral research in University of the West of Scotland London campus. I am doing my research in strategic alignment in SME business context. The purpose of this interview is to gain an understanding of the current strategic alignment in the COMPANY A. This interview will help me to identify any issues the company currently facing due to strategic alignment of business strategy and IT strategy and to identify any potential areas of improvements which is directly link to strategic alignment. So, whatever information I will get from you will be in the strictest of the confidentiality and will not be shared with anyone. This is only for academic purposes and the information will guide me to have a better result in my research. So, with that in mind, may I ask you the first question, what is your current job title in the bureau?

BM4

I'm operating as a branch manager in the bureau.

Mesaj

And, how long have you been working the company?

BM4

My current role about say 7 years now.

Mesaj

Thank you. can you tell me what is the highest level of education you attained?

BM4

I have a bachelor degree and recently graduated in my MBA.

Mesaj

Thank you. so overall how many years of work experience do you have in the foreign exchange industry?

BM4

Approximately, I would say 10 years now.

Mesaj

For what purposes that you use IT in your work?

Welcoming Notes

↑

↓

THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT
REGULAR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRONTLINE STAFFS
(R9) Bureau products and services
MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
PARTNERSHIP
(R2) Business & IT literacy (CHECKED)
(R2) Access to training and development
(R2) After problems after acquisition (CHECKED)
(R3) Senior management reaction to problem-reporting (CHECKED)
(R3) Bureau mission and goals
COMMUNICATION
EFFECTIVE CROSS-DEPARTMENT COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION
(R2) IT Resources (CHECKED)
COMPETENCY
(R2) Transparency (CHECKED)
(R2) IT department understanding and communication (CHECKED)
(R3) Importance of IT
SUPPORTIVE ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE
THE LACK OF COORDINATION BETWEEN IT DEPARTMENT AND BUSINESS MANAGERS
SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT
THEME 2 - Challenges to face When Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A
IT GOVERNANCE
THEME 1 - Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment of Business and IT Strategy of a Forex SME
THEME 1 - Strong Strategic Alignment in a Forex SME
Coding Density

1/24

1A

BM4

Well, for basic functions like transaction processing and pretty much everything inside the branch is based on IT. Currency ordering, customers stocks ordering, internal communications, AML functions and that sort of things.

Mesaj

What are the products and services your company offer?

Company A's products & Services

BM4

* At the branch level we are mainly into buying and selling foreign currency, and the plus, on top of that we do, foreign money transfers, worldwide transfers or any other type of foreign currency transfers which requested by customers. And we do get corporate clients as well so who needs large transactions. It's mostly cash or it can be a transfer as well.

Mesaj

What sort of a technology you think your organisation need?

flexible technology

BM4

Well, quite frankly, for the functions that we perform we need a simple and efficient IT solution. And, it should not be all that sophisticated for us. And the other thing is it should be flexible enough to meet the customer demands on a regular basis because they're ever changing there's no uniform pattern. So you need a flexible and agile operating system and procedures.

Mesaj

thank you. And what is the importance of having a sustainable IT services and practices to your branch?

BM4

Information Technology plays a big role because the in terms of increasing efficiency of the business and gaining a competitive advantage it is a vital fact. And the other thing is to maintain customer information and customer confidentiality because the new GDPR regulations so yeah basically to adhere to new industry regulations and to increase the efficiency of the transactions. Because all our transactions are secure and it is important that our IT services and systems must be sustainable, harmonious at all times.

IT Strategy Connecting

Expand through Customer info
Secure information

Competitive advantage Strategic Alignment means connection between business & IT.
GDPR regulation

THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT
REGULAR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF PROTECTIVE STAFFS
MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
PARTNERSHIP
(R2) Business & IT hierarchy (CHECKED)
(R3) Reduce increasing branch revenue (CHECKED)
(R4) Increase customer loyalty (CHECKED)
(R5) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
(R6) Bureau relation and goals
COMMUNICATION
EFFECTIVE CROSS-DEPARTMENT COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION
(R01) IT strategy
(R02) Transaction time (CHECKED)
(R03) Which strategy needs more attention
(R04) IT department understanding and communication (CHECKED)
(R05) Importance of IT department in organisational culture
THE LACK OF COORDINATION BETWEEN IT DEPARTMENT AND BUSINESS MANAGERS
SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT
THEME 2: Challenges to face when Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A
IT GOVERNANCE
THEME 1 - Exploring Strategic Alignment in a force SME
Coding Density

Mesaj

How does current IT services and practices (or IT goals and mission) support your branch in achieving your branch sales target?

BM4

The IT services do at the moment, do support the current requirements however, I feel at the branch level achieving the sales targets there are few challenges because of the particular IT system that we are using at the moment and the governance that's surrounding the IT system. So, because of that, the branch staff as a branch manager I feel that our efficient, our performance levels, has not been improved in such a way because of the new systems and procedures.

Amount Proceed

Grand point for discussion

Mesaj

So are you saying the new system should be improved or the people who are involved in the process should be aware of the current situation in your branch?

But do they need it? what they need it?

BM4

I feel that the IT governance should be more customer focus, whereas we could provide a more flexible service to the customers. Now we are a bit restricted in certain functions, which in turn bounces back on the actual revenue that we are generating in a branch level. So the IT vision, I believe it's to do with the IT strategic team that needs to understand what really is happening inside the branches and I think there's a bit of a disconnected there.

IT govern

Branch manager making a point

Mesaj

So, are you saying because of the disconnected situation, current IT strategic plans and business plans are not in a supportive platform right now?

BM4

Exactly they are not in the same frequency I believe.

Mesaj

Thank you. Do you think the competitive advantage can be achieved with the current IT practices and procedures?

BM4

Generally the whole purpose in foreign exchange business is to gain and keep competitive advantage when compares to your competitors. So in our situation in terms of competitive advantage I don't fully agree to that. Because the current strategic practices, the flexibility in

BM4 doesn't agree!

THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT
REGULAR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRONTLINE STAFFS
REGULAR PRODUCTION AND COMMITMENT
MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
PARTNERSHIP
(R3) Business & IT hierarchy (CHECKED)
(R3) Factors increasing branch revenue (CHECKED)
(R3) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
(R3) Bureau mission and goals
EFFECTIVE CROSS-DEPARTMENT COMMUNICATION AND COORDINATION
(R2) IT responses (CHECKED)
(R2) Transaction time (CHECKED)
(R3) Which strategy needs more attention
(R3) IT department understanding and communication (CHECKED)
(R3) Inspection of IT
ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE
THE LACK OF COORDINATION BETWEEN IT DEPARTMENT AND BUSINESS MANAGERS
SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT
THEME 2 - Challenges to face When Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A
IT GOVERNANCE
THEME 1 - Escalating Strategic Alignment in a Core Skill
Coding Density

Branch manager proposing that IT governance should be more customer focus.

Appendix H: Coding Transcript of ASM 1 (Signposting purposes)

ASMI

Internal information now, the most of the functions are now IT based. So transaction processing and branch stock ordering and all that is done through different systems, within the network. So, this information can be absorbed through the current IT framework, so we can figure that information out. However, the external information is bit tricky, there are dedicated teams that could provide us with the relevant information, market information and so on and so forth. However, in addition to that, we have requested from all branch managers, as we believe they are the main information hub to us, if they come across, special events or anything like that for any information any real live events of politics such as Brexit implications to rate movements, competitor or market movements which has impact on our products and services, new technology advancements if they heard something valuable to the company. I have requested the branch managers to individually report back to me in detail, I will report back to the area manager, if they have potential.

Current information flow

Mesaj

Does the current IT strategy in place at your company to provide a competitive advantage? how do you agree on this?

ASMI

It's a bit tricky question you're asking. Well, like in everything else there's, there's a bit of negatives and positives. If I were to go through the positives, yeah, we do have a higher digital presence. And the customer reaching is quite good and which leads to better customer data collection as well, because you know when customers place online orders and that sort of thing. So, we can collect some information about customers. Obviously, this goes into the area of regulatory adherence also because GDPR coming into play. Our system is geared to provide us the whole framework where we should be operating in. However, there is a knock on effect of all this. Because essentially it's a larger IT network that we are operating in, there are certain conditions that are put on us, certain conditions in the sense, certain regulation restrictions. So these corporate rigid practices designed by the parent organisation, that we're supposed to follow has reduced staff flexibility required to meet certain customer demands. This I noticed by when some branch managers personally spoke to me regarding their genuine thoughts about this business-IT practices. So although we do have customer reach, meeting certain customers demands have been quite reduced when we analysed the sales data 10% reduction especially when reading certain customer complaints. And if we require any, any resources or any service IT related services, we have to go through an entire path, where we do the reporting and up to the level where the problem is resolved, is that quite a bit depth, which delays the whole process. So, we are a bit

IT strategy not straightforward.

This strategy alignment not easy!

Regulation on IT/S.

Can delay business performance.

Branch manager complained!

Sales drop by 10%.

The process delays the FX transactions.

Also, branch competency.

HR skills depends on training employee strengths.

MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
 (R3) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
 THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT (CHECKED)
 (R2) Working with a larger firm (CHECKED)
 APPROPRIATE DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISATIONAL RESOURCES

(R2a) IT Resources (CHECKED)
 (R2b) Involvement in IT strategy
 (R2c) Regulatory training and development of frontline staffs
 SLOW DECISION MAKING DUE TO STRINGENT COMPANY POLICES
 (R2) Technology availability (CHECKED)
 RESISTANCE TO CHANGE CULTURE
 (R3) IT department understanding and communication (CHECKED)
 (R3) Action plan
 (R3) Bureau business strategy
 (R3) Which strategy needs more attention
 SUPERVISORY ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE
 (R3) Information security and privacy (CHECKED)
 (R3) Implement sustainable IT strategy
 (R3) Customer complaints and queries
 THEME 2 - Challenges to face When Achieving Strategic Alignment in Company A
 SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT
 THEME 3 - Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment of Business and IT Strategy of a Forex SME
 IT GOVERNANCE

Coding Density

THEME 1 - Exploring Strategic Alignment in a Forex SME

HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
 COMPETENCY

lagging behind when it comes to rapid requirements. We, more often losing customers transactions clearly.

Mesaj

Have you tell these problems to your area manager or even top board? Are they aware of such problems which is currently presence in the company?

Senior agent communicating

ASMI

Communication System/chain delays Forced upon

Yeah, see these things as you can imagine now from SME going into corporate, their working process has changed because before it was a very close proximity communications with certain business decision makers normally it's not the case we are being clustered into various areas of the entire country now, and they were operated in limited London. Now, business consent was taken over by this company, COMPANY B. Now we have nationwide so we have to go, everyone will have to follow the same channel of communication, which in turn is not really suitable for the London market, not really suitable for SME context. so obviously, yes, there is a bit of a delay in that sense because of the communication distance.

Mesaj

thank you. What do you think excellent customer service mean to your foreign exchange company?

ASMI believe the communication process delays the inputs flow

ASMI

Yeah I mean this is paramount... because in our company, business unit vision and mission according to that, this is number one priority. We look for the highest standards presence in customer service that is going to leadina to referral marketing because the customers, the more satisfied they are, they being repeat the business, plus referral marketing to their close friends or even better when satisfied customers refer our business to corporate clients. In that sense customer service is paramount that's the number one priority for all our branch staff.

Mesaj

Are you satisfied with the current customer satisfaction?

Customer Service is open-minded Not titles, large firm

ASMI

Well, we cannot predict customer expectation but we do our best to serve them at best. But there is no rule in retail that customer is always right.

Mesaj

However, ASMI believe the price needs to improve.

MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
(F3) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
(F3) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
(F3) Working with a larger firm (CHECKED)
APPROPRIATE DISTRIBUTION OF ORGANISATIONAL RESOURCES
COMPETENCY
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
(F3) IT resources (CHECKED)
REGULAR TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRONTLINE STAFFS
SLOW DECISION MAKING DUE TO STRINGENT COMPANY POLICIES
(F2) Technology available (CHECKED)
(F2) Technology available (CHECKED)
(F2) Technology available (CHECKED)
(F3) IT development understanding and communication (CHECKED)
SUPERIOR ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE
(F2) Information security and privacy (CHECKED)
(F3) Implement sustainable IT strategy
(F3) Custom compliance and quality
(F3) Custom compliance and quality
(F3) Custom compliance and quality
SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT
IT GOVERNANCE
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Mesaj

Do you think your company have matching IT strategies to deliver company goals on time? without any delays do you think company have the right IT practices, right IT processes to deliver organisation or your branch goals on time?

ASMI

IT's is Capable of bringing Profits to Bureau.

Bureau could have more simplified Strategy.

gain, it's a bit of a yes and no answer I would have to give you. Now see the corporate organisation has invest quite heavily in quite a sophisticated IT infrastructure and technology. So the IT strategy, so to speak, is fully capable of meeting the demands. It's fully capable I iterate on that, and supporting growth of the business. Well, however, the problem is, it's not so much about at the capabilities of the IT infrastructure. It's about aligning that with our group's branches business strategy. There is a bit of a gap between the two. So, which has a negative impact on our day to day business and overall business strategy as a whole. So I would say, delivering the company goals yeah the target and daily work routines - so there's, there's a bit of an issue that we are facing, as opposed to a couple of issues that we are facing. Because of the whole practices that are in place and which are not synchronised with the business strategy.

Mesaj

Synchronised business

So are you saying due to corporate IT ways there is a backward force to COMPANY A's productivity? or profit sales?

ASMI

This is Country do Luffman

Yes there are few bottlenecks hanging around in their procedures, you know, it's a chicken and egg problem really goes to such an ease, but it comes it brings along certain restrictions because of the sophistication carries a bit of restriction speaking in turn has a negative, knock on effect on flexibility and profitability.

Good point. ASMI confirm due to their issues Company A lost its Competency.

Mesaj

Can you give me an example please?

ASMI

Their IT strategy is very protected from group IT directors side. The system is designed to carry out decent customers, not all customers in other sense. The system does not understand human behaviour, for instance, we understand there can be certain disruptions to system when they carry out certain IT maintenance at Ireland. So when the maintenance starts some branches reported they cannot access the system, internet systems are not working. There is no secondary system to access during that period to serve customers. They have introduced system access time for CMS to order certain currencies for next day or next week. The reason of they introduced is to reduce

Internet is slowing.

PaPOS running on SA failures. internet

Disruption currently.

No backup System links to IT governance

- THEME 1 - Exploring Strategic Alignment in a Forrester SME
 - SCOPE AND ARCHITECTURE OF THE IT STRATEGY OF COMPANY A
 - THEME 2 - Challenges to face when Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment in Company A
 - THEME 3 - Achieving Harmonious Strategic Alignment in Company A
- Competing Externally
- MANAGEMENT KNOWLEDGE AND COMMITMENT
 - (F13) Senior management reaction to problem reporting (CHECKED)
 - (F14) THE LACK OF SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT
 - (F15) WORKING WITH A LIMITED NUMBER OF ORGANISATIONAL RESOURCES
 - APPROPRIATE TECHNOLOGICAL RESOURCES
 - HUMAN RESOURCE SKILLS
 - (F20) IT Resource (CHECKED)
 - (F21) Inexperience of IT
 - REGULATORY TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF FRONTLINE STAFF'S
 - SLOW DECISION MAKING DUE TO STRINGENT COMPANY POLICIES
 - (F22) Lack of training and development (CHECKED)
 - (F23) IT department understanding and communication (CHECKED)
 - (F24) Action plan
 - (F25) Bureau business strategy
 - COMMUNICATION
 - COMMUNICATION
 - SUPPLEMENTARY ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE
 - (F26) Information security and privacy (CHECKED)
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Luffman's framework

COMPETENCY

IT GOVERNANCE